

Efficient trustworthy AI - making the best of data (AI, Data and Robotics Partnership)
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PANDORA

A Comprehensive Framework enabling the Delivery of Trustworthy Datasets for Efficient AIoT Operation

D2.3: Embedded mechanisms to demonstrate progress

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List of Abbreviations

KPI	Key Performance Indicator
V&V	Verification and Validation
GA	Grant Agreement
KR	Key Result
AIoT	Artificial Intelligence of Things
AlaaS	Artificial Intelligence as a Service
CaaS	Computing as a Service
IM	Intent Manager
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
vPLC	Virtualized Programmable Logic Controller
UC	Use Case
UR	User Requirements
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
TBD	To Be Determined
MES	Manufacturing Execution System
HRS	Hydrogen Refueling Station
IBE	Induction Billet Extruder
AI	Artificial Intelligence
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
WP	Work Package
PU	Public
TCP/IP	Transmission Control Protocol/Internet Protocol
OSI	Open Systems Interconnection
RAM	Random Access Memory
CPU	Central Processing Unit
QoS	Quality of Service
PRS	Monitoring Mechanism of Press
ROS	Robot Operating System
RDF	Resource Description Framework
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
3D	Three-Dimensional
HMI	Human Machine Interface
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprise

AMR	Autonomous Mobile Robots
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicles
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
V&V	Verification and Validation
GA	Grant Agreement
KR	Key Result
AIoT	Artificial Intelligence of Things
IE	Industrial Edge
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer

Executive Summary

Deliverable D2.3 details the work completed in Task 2.5, "PANDORA Embedded Mechanisms to Assess and Demonstrate Progress: Real-Life Trial Cases, KPIs, and Metrics Accounting for Data and Energy Efficiency," supporting the objectives of WP2. The main focus areas of the document are:

- defining experimental protocols for each use case, providing an overview of existing systems and data in each pilot case, identifying gaps, collecting user requirements, and aligning use cases with PANDORA strategies,
- establishing the PANDORA experimentation process, which follows an iterative approach comprising two definition phases and two operational phases, enabling continuous refinement and alignment with evolving project requirements and goals,
- developing the Verification and Validation (V&V) methodology, which outlines systematic processes for assessing technical and business requirements, using specific V&V variables as measurable criteria to evaluate the performance and alignment of PANDORA technologies with end-user needs and project goals,
- compiling and organizing all PANDORA KPIs, including those defined in the Grant Agreement (GA) and additional KPIs identified during the use case design phase, into a structured framework to facilitate easy tracking and monitoring of project progress.

The overall assessment of PANDORA outcomes will be an ongoing process aligned with project progress. This evaluation will utilize the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and Key Results (KRs) outlined in the Grant Agreement (GA) and V&V variables outlined in Sections 6.1 and 6.2. These metrics will be continuously monitored and updated within Task 6.3.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

The purpose of this document is to report the work conducted in Task 2.5 of the PANDORA project, focused on establishing embedded mechanisms to assess and demonstrate project progress. Task 2.5 aims to:

- i. provide detailed use case descriptions that address data and energy efficiency in AIoT pipelines,
- ii. gather end-user requirements to define AIoT trial scenarios,
- iii. detail a coherent execution plan for the demonstrations,
- iv. formulate a verification and validation methodology for the evaluation of PANDORA framework against defined benchmarks, KPIs, and objectives,
- v. aggregate project's KPIs and provide an overview including, technical, impact and business metrics.

1.2 Structure of the document

This document is structured to provide a thorough examination of the PANDORA project. In Section 1, the introduction clarifies the purpose and intended readership of the document. Section 2 presents the project's positioning, covering the framework's overview, target groups and their needs, market orientation, and overall context of the project. In Section 3, we delve into the use cases, each representing a unique application of the PANDORA framework. Each use case is introduced and followed by detailed descriptions of specific pilot trial cases. Section 4 describes the experimental protocol, including methodology, KPIs tied to the framework, trial scenarios for AIoT applications, strategies and requirements mapping, and industrial requirements. Section 5 provides an overview of the experimentation process, detailing stages from scoping to analysis. The document proceeds in Section 6 with the V&V strategy for PANDORA, with a draft specification of the V&V variables. Section 7 focuses on the collection, classification, and monitoring of KPIs, offering a comprehensive view of the project's impact through technical, impact, and business KPIs. Finally, Section 8 concludes the document, summarizing key takeaways and setting the stage for future developments.

1.3 Intended readership

The audience of this document includes PANDORA technology providers directly involved in the development of project technologies. Pilot owners are also key readers, as they define validation variables and metrics across both business and technical domains. Their effort will be supported by this document outlining the experimentation process and validation strategies that will guide pilot case implementations, particularly within WP6. Additionally, external stakeholders and potential adopters of the PANDORA framework will benefit from the systematic evaluation methodology, documented here, to address challenges related to the generation of trustworthy datasets and the efficient operation of AIoT systems. This will be especially beneficial in WP7, during the dissemination and communication phase of the project.

2. PANDORA Positioning

2.1 Overview of the Framework

The PANDORA framework enables wise usage of possibly limited real IoT data and improves AIoT system operation by managing the runtime deployment of AIoT applications. PANDORA receives as input a dataset collected from IoT devices. Then, PANDORA's main goal is two-tiered: (i) generate customizable and trustworthy datasets for model training and testing for AIoT application deployment (Phase I); and (ii) support AIoT deployment as well as continual, energy-efficient and robust AIoT operation via a series of AI as a Service (AlaaS) and Computing as a Service (CaaS) components (Phase II).

Phase I proposes six strategies (also called components, see details in D2.2 [1]) related to synthetic data generation, semi-automated annotations of dataset, uncertainty quantification and data summarization. All the strategies work complementary with one another to produce trustworthy datasets for training, testing and deployment of AIoT systems. Then, in Phase II, PANDORA offers several AlaaS/CaaS-based components that enable continual, energy-efficient and robust operation of AIoT systems, with an increased degree of autonomy. More details regarding the PANDORA framework and its components/strategies can be found in D2.2 [1].

2.2 Target Groups and Needs

The PANDORA project is tailored to meet the needs of diverse stakeholders within diverse AIoT ecosystems:

- **Industrial Enterprises and Smart Infrastructure Managers:** These organizations, which oversee operations in factories, smart buildings, and critical infrastructure, can use PANDORA to enhance efficiency with reliable and customizable datasets for AI model training. This helps in applications like predictive maintenance and optimizing energy use.
- **Technology Developers and AI Solution Providers:** Developers can benefit from PANDORA's capabilities for synthetic data generation and uncertainty quantification, which help improve the quality and reliability of AI models. This supports the creation of adaptable applications suited for dynamic, real-world data environments.
- **Regulatory Bodies and Compliance Authorities:** PANDORA aligns with global standards for data security and ethical AI practices, making it a valuable tool for ensuring compliance and fostering trust in AI implementations.
- **Public Sector:** The Public Sector wishes to promote open data sharing to assist building collaborative data value chains. PANDORA provides a starting point with interoperable datasets, data standardization, and facilitation of data-driven decision-making.
- **Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs):** SMEs, often constrained by limited budgets, can leverage PANDORA's scalable and cost-effective solutions. The phased approach offered by PANDORA allows these enterprises to gradually integrate AIoT technologies without significant upfront costs, assisting them in extracting actionable knowledge from the data they own.
- **Academic Institutions and Researchers:** Universities and research bodies can utilize PANDORA's framework for studies on data synthesis, explainable AI, and energy efficient AIoT systems. It also serves as an excellent foundation for educational purposes, providing practical insights and tools for advanced AI coursework and research.

2.3 Market orientation

PANDORA is strategically positioned in the rapidly expanding AIoT market, driven by the demand for intelligent, real-time data analysis and enhanced operational efficiency:

- **Market Trends and Growth:** The convergence of AI and IoT is expanding, driven by the need for better automation and smarter infrastructure. This growth is bolstered by substantial investments in machine learning and data-driven technologies, highlighting the relevance of PANDORA in meeting these market needs.
- **Unique Value Proposition:**
 - **Reliable Data Generation:** PANDORA stands out by creating customizable, high-quality training datasets through synthetic data techniques and uncertainty quantification, enhancing the reliability of AI models.
 - **Explainable and Ethical AI:** By incorporating explainable AI methods, PANDORA fosters transparency and trust, aligning with current expectations for ethical AI solutions.
 - **Operational Efficiency and Sustainability:** Through its AI as a Service (AlaaS) and Computing as a Service (CaaS) components, PANDORA ensures continuous and energy efficient AIoT operations, supporting long-term sustainability.
- **Use Cases:**
 - **Advanced Manufacturing¹:** PANDORA can be utilized to optimize machine operations, such as predictive maintenance, sorting, quality control, by leveraging trustworthy and comprehensive datasets.
 - **Smart Buildings²:** In smart buildings, PANDORA supports real-time and predictive analysis for energy consumption, enabling better resource management and cost savings. PANDORA strategies can be employed to facilitate continuous, energy-efficient, and robust operation of AIoT systems, while improving their autonomy.
 - **Critical Energy Infrastructure³:** A framework for delivering trustworthy datasets can ensure the accuracy, reliability, and integrity of data used in AI applications for monitoring and managing critical plant operations. PANDORA aims to enhance operational safety by accurately predicting potential anomalies within targeted AIoT systems.
- **Challenges and Barriers:** One of the main challenges to adopting advanced AIoT solutions is the high initial cost and concerns over data security. PANDORA addresses these issues by offering flexible, scalable solutions that cater to budget-conscious organizations while ensuring data protection.
- **Regulatory Compliance:** With a strong emphasis on data privacy and adherence to ethical AI standards, PANDORA provides a compliant and reliable platform, making it an attractive option for industries in highly regulated environments.

¹ https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/jrc-news-and-updates/advanced-manufacturing-industry-growing-significantly-eu-2024-07-02_en

² <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/8810715>

³ https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/jrc-news-and-updates/whos-energy-poor-eu-its-more-complex-it-seems-2024-09-25_en

2.4 Research landscape and technological assets

In this section we focus on research efforts and technical solutions developed in the context of European research and innovation initiatives. Moreover, the section describes software tools, platforms and assets stemming from the developers' community.

2.4.1 Related projects

The methodology developed to identify relevant projects within the PANDORA framework focuses on systematically gathering, organizing, and integrating insights from EU-funded initiatives, particularly within the AI & Robotics sector. The primary goal of this initiative is to create a comprehensive repository of projects that offer valuable knowledge, tools, and methodologies to support PANDORA's objectives. This process results in a Projects table that provides strategic information for PANDORA's Work Package & Task Leaders, listed in the Appendix of D2.1.

Methodology Overview:

- **Comprehensive Review of EU-funded Projects:** First, the methodology involved detailed review and in-depth analysis of past and ongoing EU-funded projects in which the PANDORA project partners were directly involved. This review focused on projects that produced key advances in science, tools, methodologies and systems relevant to the objectives of PANDORA. Emphasis was placed on the selection of projects that dealt with specific issues related to AI, Data and Robotics.
- **Relevance-based Selection and Classification:** Once the pool of projects was identified, each project was analyzed in trying to precisely identify its individual contributions and relevance to the PANDORA framework. This involved mapping relevant projects on specific strategies and tasks of PANDORA. The resulting Projects table includes project title, partners involved, tools, related strategies and Tasks. This categorization therefore gives a clear basis of how the outputs at each project correlate with work packages, tasks and strategies of PANDORA.
- **Mapping Strategies to Tasks:** An essential part of the methodology was to link the identified projects to specific strategies and tasks within PANDORA. This linkage in the Projects table provides the WP Leaders with a detailed reference from each project's contributions. It allows them to create links between existing project outcomes and the needs of PANDORA, focusing on the integration of knowledge and tools.

Purpose of the Process:

- **Knowledge Integration:** The process facilitates the collection and structuring of a set of relevant projects in one repository, allowing smooth integration of existing methodologies, tools, and systems to avoid duplications, hence allowing the PANDORA framework to exploit the latest advancements developed through EU-funded projects.
- **Supporting Strategic Alignment:** The Projects table is a strategic reference tool that WP Leaders can refer to with the express intention of keeping activities in tune with established methodologies and approaches which have proved successful. This tool will enable proper planning and implementation of objectives set by PANDORA.
- **Promoting Collaborative Knowledge Sharing:** The primary objective is to identify consortium partners and the relevant projects they are involved in to enhance integration and knowledge sharing within the project lifecycle. An opportunity for collaboration may arise in the context of PANDORA's framework. In that way, insights and expertise will cross over from one discipline to another, reaching solutions that are even more innovative and comprehensive.

2.4.2 Identified assets

Similarly, to the approach outlined for the Projects, a systematic method was followed focusing on identifying scientific Assets produced by relevant EU-funded projects. This effort has developed an asset repository that will provide significant inputs toward achieving the PANDORA framework objectives. The respective assets that were identified included research papers, datasets, and software tools supplying the knowledge base and resources needed for the strategies and tasks of PANDORA. These assets were listed based on each strategy in the Assets table provided in the Appendix of D2.1.

Methodology Overview:

- **Identification of Key Scientific Resources:** Asset identification initially involved the overall review of EU-funded projects. This involved the extraction of scientific outputs such as peer-reviewed publications and curated datasets, along with software tools from projects that could possibly contribute to a number of key objectives of PANDORA. The selection would be based on those assets providing major insights or data for major strategies under focus in the framework.
- **Categorization based on Strategy Relevance:** Once found, the assets were organized within PANDORA by related strategies. The outcome is a more direct linkage between the asset and how it could contribute to fulfill a particular task or objective. The sorting of the assets by strategy contributes to accessibility and ensures that Task and Strategy Leaders can effectively locate relevant resources supporting their work.
- **Assets table Documentation:** These scientific resources were systematically documented in an Assets table, covering information such as type of asset (e.g. research paper, dataset), project source, related partner, description, and related strategy in PANDORA. This therefore provides a structured reference to the project partners in accessing these scientific resources.

3. PANDORA Use Cases

3.1 Overview

Use Cases play a crucial role in defining the direction of the project. They provide valuable insights for the development of necessary software, as they integrate the user's perspective. Specifically, Use Cases link user requirements with the technical solutions to be developed, aligning user needs with business objectives.

The following sections will help define the environment in which the system will operate, including the infrastructures and processes of Siemens, Ericsson, Philips, Framatome and HALCOR. Differences in specific needs and objectives within the PANDORA project will be highlighted to ensure alignment in development and implementation.

Each Use Case will include key elements such as the Actors (i.e., individuals interacting with the developed system), the nature of these interactions, and the high-level operation of each component. This structure ensures clarity and consistency in documentation, facilitating effective communication among stakeholders.

3.2 Use case 1 – Predictive edge in production cells (SAG)

3.2.1 Introduction

Business context

Siemens Industrial Edge (IE) is an open, ready-to-use edge computing platform, with edge devices, edge applications (apps) and connectivity through an integrated app and device management infrastructure. It allows customers to easily connect, manage and operate globally distributed edge installations, with their own or the diverse apps available through the IE Marketplace. Once the system is setup, the data flows seamlessly across the IE value chain providing customer satisfaction. However, downtime is expensive, especially when it's unplanned. Predicting failures lets the customer see into the future, thanks to the know-how of cutting-edge technologies like AI. And thanks to optimized maintenance planning, the customer even can avoid unpleasant surprises and benefit from a new degree of reliability. Using data from the manufacturing plants, the customer or the Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM) vendor can focus the attention exactly where it's needed to prevent outages from the outset. By concentrating on the actual condition of production machines, IE devices and networking infrastructure, the customer can increase their manufacturing plants' availability, enable precise and timely maintenance, and minimize downtimes.

Business needs/opportunities

The business needs and opportunities for the Siemens AG emerging from the realization of the use case described here are manifold. Long-term, the developed technologies will be able to increase the productivity of production cells at customers. Additionally, the PANDORA technologies will allow the definition, analysis and adherence to service-level agreements around the infrastructure of the production cell. This is a great value generation that focuses on system uptime and availability, reflecting the reliability of the infrastructure and minimizing downtime due to resource overloads. Further, an increase in production efficiency, e.g., measured by the average cycle time per work piece, will remain low even during peak demand periods. Looking at the Siemens product landscape, these advantages will largely benefit the product lines "IE" and "SCALANCE" in providing elements for highly reliable, IE/network infrastructure. Therefore, in Phase I, it is crucial to create dataset(s) that enable the training of AI models to predict failures in IE / network infrastructures. In Phase II, the creation of the actual AI model(s) that predict critical failures in IE / network infrastructures is important. The focus is on ensuring the smooth and efficient functioning of the production cell during high-demand periods like shift changes. Hence,

the business needs lay on developing AI-based methods for predicting network and compute resource consumption and based on those, implementing real-time monitoring and adaptive resource management to maintain operational efficiency during peak access times. Additionally, historical data could be used to predict peak usage times and implement load balancing strategies to prevent future overloads.

Desired outcomes by PANDORA

The outcomes of PANDORA needed for being able to implement the outlined scenarios below, are as follows:

- development of enhanced models to predict failures in the networked edge infrastructure as soon as possible (e.g., device failures or disallowed traffic patterns in the network),
- development of (semantic) models for networked edge infrastructures that feed simulators (e.g., Digital Twin) to produce synthetic data about the state of the infrastructure,
- creation of synthetic data that realistically reflect failure events,
- distributed execution of AI models for monitoring the edge infrastructure and detection of disruptions,
- re-allocation of the installed apps prior to failures and avoid negative impacts on the production process.

3.2.2 Detailed Pilot Trial Cases description

Overall system description

Today, the EU’s manufacturing sector employs over 30 million people, contributes 21.4% to the EU’s employment, and generated €1,912 billion of economic value added in 2016⁴. This economic branch is currently amid an immense transition, which has been termed the 4th industrial revolution. This “Industry 4.0” is seen as the most disruptive change emerging in manufacturing industry. Heavy use of virtualized control and compute processes (especially AI) to increase productivity, efficiency and product quality are key for this new technological era of the manufacturing domain. For providing this required computing power, which needs to be close to the manufacturing machinery to avoid higher latencies, the edge computing paradigm in combination with advanced industrial communication networks are emerging. This is the driving force for this PANDORA pilot trial

Figure 1: Overall system environment

case: it aims at supporting the management of edge computing and network infrastructures for the modern industrial environment. This is widely recognized as a crucial feature of Industry 4.0 for the manufacturing plant of the future. As shown in **Figure 1**, this pilot trial case aims to implement such a future-looking industrial environment consisting of a conveyor belt that transports work pieces, which are then sorted according to quality. The compute processes to control this are thereby running in an edge environment, or on a local data center within the industrial plant. In the production cell, the work pieces transported by the conveyor belt are passing by a light barrier, whose detection signal is received by the control logic which in turn triggers a camera. The taken camera image is passed to an AI app that classifies it and accordingly the work piece is sorted into “good” or “bad”. I.e., if the work piece is identified as “bad”, a sorter arm is triggered to sort out the work piece. This control logic is implemented with a programmable logic controller (PLC), or more specifically, a virtualized PLC (vPLC) that is running as an edge app in a (edge / data center) server of the environment.

Pilot infrastructure, main components, tools and deployment environment

The pilot infrastructure will be setup as depicted in **Figure 1** and will be a laboratory that implements a small-scale production environment consisting of:

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Manufacturing_statistics_-_NACE_Rev._2

- industrial communication networks,
- edge computing devices and data center that run apps,
- virtual PLC and AI apps to compute control logic and AI inference,
- conveyor belt, arm sorter, camera and light barrier to transport work pieces.

To follow the future trend of virtualization (with the purpose of cost saving and improved maintenance), a vPLC (instead of a PLC) is utilized for the logic control. The vPLC is running as an edge app (which is essentially a Docker container) in an edge computing device or within the data center of an industrial plant. For data collection in the infrastructure, we will measure at different routers and switches traffic metrics, such as queue length, used bandwidth, packet loss. We will use protocols such as Netconf and SNMP to collect those data. Further, we will collect statistics about the network traffic (e.g., OPC-UA requests) on the servers and will collect at the same time CPU load and RAM usage. We will use tools such as OpenTelemetry to collect the data in Prometheus, Jaeger, or similar systems.

Data description

Multiple tables with various observation attributes will be collected (see below). These observations will be growing in number by about 10 per second. The format of the data will be structured, tabular data. Ownership and accessibility rights will be with SAG. Access to the newly created dataset can be provided as foreground according to PANDORA's consortium agreement.

For server machines, a table consisting of a selection of the following metrics will be acquired:

- Time tag (in ms)
- Server MAC address (as ID)
- System Uptime: The amount of time the server has been running since the last reboot
- System Temperature: The overall system temperature
- CPU Metrics:
 - CPU Usage Percentage: The percentage of CPU time being used by all processes
 - User CPU Time: The amount of CPU time spent in user mode
 - System CPU Time: The amount of CPU time spent in kernel mode
 - Idle CPU Time: The amount of CPU time spent idle
 - I/O Wait Time: The amount of CPU time spent waiting for I/O operations to complete
 - Load Average: The average system load over 1, 5, and 15 minutes
 - Per-Core CPU Usage: The usage percentage for each individual CPU core
 - Context Switches: The number of context switches per second
 - CPU Interrupts: The number of hardware interrupts per second
 - CPU Temperature: The temperature of the CP
- RAM Metrics:
 - Total Memory: The total physical memory available
 - Used Memory: The amount of memory currently being used
 - Free Memory: The amount of memory currently available
 - Available Memory: The amount of memory available for allocation to processes
 - Buffers: The amount of memory used for buffering I/O operations
 - Cached Memory: The amount of memory used for caching files and data

- Total Swap: The total swap space available
- Used Swap: The amount of swap space currently in use
- Free Swap: The amount of swap space currently available
- Swap Memory Total: The total swap memory capacity
- Page Ins: The number of pages read from disk into memory
- Page Outs: The number of pages written from memory to disk
- Per-Process Memory Usage: The amount of memory used by each individual process
- Network Metrics:
 - Bytes Sent: The total number of bytes sent over the network
 - Bytes Received: The total number of bytes received over the network
 - Packets Sent: The total number of packets sent over the network
 - Packets Received: The total number of packets received over the network
 - Packets Dropped (In/Out): The number of packets dropped during transmission or reception
 - Send Errors: The number of errors encountered while sending packets
 - Receive Errors: The number of errors encountered while receiving packets
 - Active Connections: The number of active network connections
 - Connection Attempts: The number of connection attempts made
 - Failed Connection Attempts: The number of failed connection attempts
- Disk Metrics:
 - Disk Space Used: The amount of disk space currently in use
 - Disk Space Free: The amount of available disk space
 - Disk Space Total: The total capacity of the disk
 - Disk Read Bytes: The total number of bytes read from disk
 - Disk Write Bytes: The total number of bytes written to disk
 - Disk Reads: The number of read operations per second
 - Disk Writes: The number of write operations per second
 - Read Latency: The time taken to complete read operations
 - Write Latency: The time taken to complete write operations
 - Read Errors: The number of errors encountered during read operations
 - Write Errors: The number of errors encountered during write operations
- Process Metrics:
 - Total Processes: The total number of running processes
 - Running Processes: The number of processes currently in the running state
 - Blocked Processes: The number of processes that are blocked and waiting for I/O
 - CPU Usage per Process: The CPU usage of individual processes
 - Memory Usage per Process: The memory usage of individual processes
- Thread Metrics:
 - Total Threads: The total number of threads across all processes

- Threads per Process: The number of threads for each process
- System Load Metrics
- System Load Average
- 1-minute Load Average: The average system load over the last minute
- 5-minute Load Average: The average system load over the last five minutes
- 15-minute Load Average: The average system load over the last fifteen minutes

For routers, a table consisting of a selection of the following metrics will be acquired:

- Time tag (in ms)
- Device MAC address
- Router Health:
 - CPU Usage: Router's CPU load
 - Memory Usage: Router's memory usage
 - Uptime: Duration the router has been operational without a restart
- Packet Counts:
 - Total Packets: Number of packets transmitted and received
 - Packets per Interface: Packets handled by each network interface
- Byte Counts:
 - Total Bytes: Amount of data (in bytes) transmitted and received
 - Bytes per Interface: Data volume handled by each network interface
- Bandwidth Utilization:
 - Current Bandwidth: Real-time usage of network bandwidth
 - Peak Bandwidth: Maximum bandwidth usage over a period
 - Average Bandwidth: Average bandwidth usage over a period
- Network Protocols:
 - Protocol Distribution: Breakdown of traffic by protocols (e.g., TCP, UDP, ICMP)
 - Port Utilization: Traffic distribution across different ports
- Connection Statistics:
 - Active Connections: Number of current active connections
 - Connection States: States of connections (e.g., established, listening, closed)
- Error Counts:
 - Packet Errors: Number of erroneous packets (e.g., CRC errors, collisions)
 - Dropped Packets: Number of packets dropped due to errors or congestion
- Latency and Jitter:
 - Round-Trip Time (RTT): Time taken for a packet to travel to a destination and back
 - Jitter: Variation in packet arrival times
- Throughput:
 - Ingress Throughput: Rate of incoming traffic
 - Egress Throughput: Rate of outgoing traffic
- Flow Statistics:

- Top Talkers: Hosts generating the most traffic
- Top Conversations: Most active communication pairs
- Quality of Service (QoS) Metrics:
 - QoS Queues: Statistics for different QoS queues (e.g., queue lengths, drops)
 - Traffic Classification: Traffic categorized by QoS classes
- Application and User Data:
 - Application Traffic: Distribution of traffic by applications
 - User Traffic: Traffic data per user or device
- Security Metrics:
 - Firewall Hits: Number of packets matching firewall rules
 - Intrusion Detection/Prevention Alerts: Number of security alerts triggered

For switches, a table consisting of a selection of the following metrics will be acquired:

- Switch Health:
 - CPU Usage: Switch's CPU load
 - Memory Usage: Switch's memory usage
 - Uptime: Duration the switch has been operational without a restart
- Packet Counts:
 - Total Packets: Number of packets transmitted and received by the switch
 - Packets per Port: Packets handled by each port on the switch
- Byte Counts:
 - Total Bytes: Amount of data (in bytes) transmitted and received
 - Bytes per Port: Data volume handled by each port on the switch
- Bandwidth Utilization:
 - Current Bandwidth: Real-time usage of network bandwidth on the switch
 - Peak Bandwidth: Maximum bandwidth usage over a period
 - Average Bandwidth: Average bandwidth usage over a period
- Port Status and Statistics:
 - Port Utilization: Percentage of bandwidth utilization per port
 - Port Errors: Errors per port, such as CRC errors, alignment errors, and collisions
 - Port Status: Status of each port (e.g., up, down, admin down)
- Error Counts:
 - Packet Errors: Number of erroneous packets (e.g., CRC errors, alignment errors)
 - Dropped Packets: Number of packets dropped due to errors or congestion
- Latency and Jitter:
 - Port Latency: Time taken for packets to traverse a port
 - Jitter: Variation in packet arrival times
- Throughput:
 - Ingress Throughput: Rate of incoming traffic on each port

- Egress Throughput: Rate of outgoing traffic on each port
- VLAN Statistics:
 - VLAN Traffic: Traffic statistics per VLAN
 - VLAN Membership: Port membership and traffic distribution across VLANs
- Flow Statistics:
 - MAC Address table: Learned MAC addresses and their associated ports
 - Top Talkers: Devices generating the most traffic
 - Top Conversations: Most active communication pairs
- Quality of Service (QoS) Metrics:
 - QoS Queues: Statistics for different QoS queues (e.g., queue lengths, drops)
 - Traffic Classification: Traffic categorized by QoS classes
- Application and User Data:
 - Application Traffic: Distribution of traffic by applications (if supported by the switch)
 - User Traffic: Traffic data per user or device (if supported by the switch)
- Security Metrics:
 - Access Control Lists (ACL) Hits: Number of packets matching ACL rules
 - Port Security Violations: Number of security violations per port (e.g., unauthorized devices)
- Spanning Tree Protocol (STP) Metrics:
 - STP Status: Status of STP on each port
 - STP Topology Changes: Number of topology changes

As ground truth / labels a table consisting of the following metrics will be acquired:

- Time tag (in ms)
- Delay between vPLC and ET200
- Cycle times of the vPLC

For tracking the physical environment, a table consisting of the following metrics will be created:

- Time tag (in ms) when the disruption event was started
- Conveyor belt speed
- Count of work pieces per minute
- Count of “good” work pieces per minute
- Count of “bad” work pieces per minute
- Light barrier currently “detecting” (true / false)
- Last camera image taken (link to image file)
- AI result of last camera image (“good” or “bad”; confidence)
- Arm sorter position (“good” or “bad”)

3.3 Use case 2 –5G enabled Smart Building (EAB)

3.3.1 Introduction

Business context

The evolution of cellular 5G and 6G technologies has brought into forefront new use cases, especially in the context of industrial wireless networks. Of particular interest are enterprise use cases where 5G/6G can provide differentiated QoS guarantees to serve different types of services: robotic automation, IoT sensing, AI workloads, video feeds. While Ericsson is a leader in the outdoor cellular 5G deployments, the deployments within enterprises primarily rely on WiFi or proprietary (wired) communication technologies. While initial pilot studies have been conducted in the mobile robot use case with companies such as Bosch and ABB, Ericsson is still trying to demonstrate the superior reliability and differentiated QoS of 5G networks. Through this research project, we want to demonstrate the ability of 5G networks to provide reliable, differentiated and adaptive communication for indoor robotic deployments. Another challenge is the autonomous nature of deployments. The 5G networks should reconfigure for changes in robot trajectory or smart space deployments. Such changes will involve AI techniques. Using autonomous 5G deployments, the vision is to provide reliable and assured communication services for the robot production line. In addition, the trustworthy aspects of AI would be needed to elaborate the context and reasoning for decision making.

Business needs/opportunities

Compared to non-cellular technologies, 5G/6G services have the potential to provide superior coverage, reliability and QoS differentiation. The superior benefits are particularly suited for robot and IoT scenarios where the combination of communication constraints, AI workloads and uncertain deployment environments add to complexities. As these are safety-critical environments, trustworthy-AI aspects would have to be considered within the design-phase to ensure safe and explainable runtime execution. PANDORA technologies would be crucial to demonstrate and tackle the above challenges. Through synthetic data generation and smart annotation techniques, the collected 5G and robot sensor data can be improved for superior model training. The continual learning techniques could then be applied to ensure robot and 5G deployment autonomy. Federated representational learning techniques could ensure superior coordination among the deployed nodes. In addition, explainability techniques would be needed to add trust to the use case. These outcomes would be business critical and can demonstrate the AI driven properties of indoor 5G networks.

Desired outcomes by PANDORA

Given an indoor enterprise 5G/6G deployment scenario with multiple types of services, the objective would be to demonstrate:

- improved connectivity (throughput/latency) of robots and devices,
- AI driven robot trajectory and closed loop 5G control for autonomous operation,
- trustworthy operations demonstrated over different scenarios.

3.3.2 Detailed Pilot Trial Cases description

Overall system description

Figure 2 provides an overview of the communication aware indoor robot environment. We have an Autonomous Mobile Robot (AMR) or Autonomous Guided Vehicle (AGV) deployed to perform an indoor task. The robot has to move from one point to another while ensuring the following constraints:

- traversing the path in the shortest trajectory to limit battery usage,
- maintaining communication requirements for all services (differing throughput, latency),
- preventing unsafe states provided by high level intents to both robot and the communication system.

Note that we have an on-premise edge server to perform core operations of the 5G network. The robot also has a local server to perform on board computations. AI driven path planning algorithms may be employed to perform intelligent path planning, specially with dynamic obstacles. In addition, a software defined 5G network controller may be employed for intelligent communication/computing resource allocation.

Figure 2: Communication-aware indoor robot scenario

Pilot infrastructure, main components, tools and deployment environment

The following tools are used to collect data from the environment:

- TCP Dump a packet analyser that allows tracking transmitted packets and their properties (e.g. payload, size of the packet). During the data collection process, TCP Dump will be run on both server and the linux kernel of the AMR/AGV. This allows reconstructing e.g. the packet delay (Uplink and Downlink, respectively).
- Iperf: a speed test application that enables measuring the bandwidth and jitter of a UDP or TCP connection. This is measured with a granularity interval of 1s.
- Ping: Terminal command to measure packet delay.

ROS Sensor data: Data is collected via the robot operating system and is used to map various obstacles. Data collected via the Robot Operating System (ROS) includes various metrics such as obstacles, odometry, and LIDAR, which are detailed in

- **Table 1.** These parameters are crucial for mapping obstacles and monitoring the robot’s environment in real-time.

Table 1: ROS Data Collection Parameters for Autonomous Mobile Robot (AMR) / Autonomous Guided Vehicle (AGV)

Topic	ROS message type	Update period	Description
Map static elevation	nav_msgs/OccupancyGrid	-	Single precomputed map of the whole area
Far map obstacles	nav_msgs/OccupancyGrid	50 ms	400 obstacle map around the AGV
Near map obstacles	nav_msgs/OccupancyGrid	20 ms	36 obstacle map around the AGV
Odometry	nav_msgs/Odometry	10 ms	Sensor-fused position, orientation and speed of the AGV
Inertial Measurement Unit	sensor_msgs/Imu	10 ms	Conventional IMU data
LIDAR	sensor_msgs/PointCloud2	100 ms	3D point cloud with obstacles

The capabilities and specifications for both the robot and 5G nodes are summarized in Table 2. This includes sensor, actuator, and processing specifications, all of which are essential to ensuring robust communication and control in the smart building environment.

Table 2: Specifications and Capabilities of Robot and 5G Nodes

Device	Sensors	Actuators	Processing	OS	Computing capabilities
Robot Node	Obstacle detection Odometry Lidar	Robot speed control Robot direction	On board and edge computing	ROS	Intel Celeron Processors, ~32 GB RAM
5G Node	Performance measurement counters for throughput, latency and other QoS parameters Power / energy measurements	5G configuration including power allocation	On board and edge computing	Proprietary or software defined radio	Snapdragon X50

Data description

For the communication-aware AGV/AMR environment, the following data parameters will be collected with some variations in sensing rate granularity based on the source. **Table 3** summarizes the data sources categorized by device, data parameter, collection source, and data type.

- **Devices:** This column lists the devices involved in data collection, such as 5G RAN (Radio Access Network), Robot, and core systems.
- **Data:** Specifies the parameters being measured, such as signal strength, latency, robot position, or throughput.
- **Source:** Describes the method or tool used for data collection, including tools like Iperf (for bandwidth and jitter), Ping (for delay), ROS (for robot sensor data), and Manual (for manually configured parameters).
- **Data type:** Indicates the data format (e.g., float64), which is used for precise numerical measurements.

Table 3: Summary of data sources for communication-aware AGV/AMR environment

Devices	Data	source	dtype
	time[s]		float64
5G RAN	serving_cell_rsrp_1	Script	float64
5G RAN	serving_cell_rsrq_1	Script	float64
5G RAN	serving_cell_rssi_1	Script	float64
5G RAN	serving_cell_snr_1	Script	float64
Robot/5G	datarate_client	Iperf	float64
Robot/5G	jitter_client	Iperf	float64
Robot/5G	port_local_client	Iperf	float64
Robot/5G	port_remote_client	Iperf	float64
Robot/5G	target_DL	Iperf	float64
Robot/5G	throughput_DL	Iperf	float64
Robot/5G	jitter_DL	Iperf	float64
Robot/5G	device_id_client	Iperf	float64
5G RAN/core	datarate_server	Iperf	float64
5G RAN/core	jitter_server	Iperf	float64
5G RAN/core	port_local_server	Iperf	float64
5G RAN/core	port_remote_server	Iperf	float64
5G RAN/core	target_UL	Iperf	float64
5G RAN/core	throughput_UL	Iperf	float64
5G RAN/core	jitter_UL	Iperf	float64
Robot/5G	device_id_server	Iperf	float64
Robot/5G	ping_size_bytes	Ping	float64
Robot/5G	icmp_seq	Ping	float64
Robot/5G	ttl	Ping	float64
Robot/5G	ping_ms	Ping	float64
Robot	Latitude	GPS	float64
Robot	Longitude	GPS	float64
Robot	device_id	Manual	float64
Robot	meas_id	Manual	float64
5G RAN/core	cell_load_UL	Manual	float64

5G RAN/core	UE_UL	Manual	float64
5G RAN/core	cell_load_DL	Manual	float64
5G RAN/core	UE_DL		float64
5G RAN/core	delay_mean_DL	TCPDump	float64
5G RAN/core	delay_std_DL	TCPDump	float64
5G RAN/core	delay_mean_UL	TCPDump	float64
5G RAN/core	delay_std_UL	TCPDump	float64
Robot	position_x	ROS	float64
Robot	position_y	ROS	float64
Robot	position_z	ROS	float64
Robot	orientation_x	ROS	float64
Robot	orientation_y	ROS	float64
Robot	orientation_z	ROS	float64
Robot	orientation_w	ROS	float64
Robot	distance_to_bs	ROS/preprocessed	float64

SLAM sensing data:

In addition, we have historic SLAM data that may also be used for experimentation. The sensor data was collected inside a former Ericsson office in Brazil (Indaiatuba). Therefore, the configuration of the Ericsson premise will be exposed. However, it is highlighted that this office is not used anymore. Although there are other 3D mapping datasets available such as the TUM RGBD dataset [2], we see that the one we are planning to provide has the following advantages:

- contains data from a multitude of sensors: lidar, 3D camera, wheel encoder,
- is compatible with the latest version of ROS (<https://www.ros.org/>), with existing datasets usually outdated and not compatible with the latest ROS libraries,
- has fiducial markers (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fiducial_marker) captured for a more precise localization,
- is ready to use with the open source RTAB-Map SLAM library,
- can be used for other purposes such as object detection task,
- motivates other partners to enhance the dataset by for example, providing labels for training a particular model.

3.4 Use case 3 – Enable flexibility in automated visual inspection (PCL)

3.4.1 Introduction

Business context

Philips Drachten is one of Philips largest development and production centers in Europe and located in the Netherlands. Here we work together with more than 1500 people on Personal Health products, such as the newest shavers, Philips Avent Mother & Childcare products, OneBlades, Ladyshaves and beard trimmers. To remain competitive, we must streamline our time to market and accommodate an increase in the diversity and smaller custom batches, including personalized products. A key aspect of this strategy is reducing labor costs by eliminating manual quality inspections. The adoption of AI-driven autonomous systems is a strategic imperative for PCL that aligns with the principles of Industry 4.0 readiness. In the current situation, numerous visual product inspection tasks are required, mostly conducted on a large-scale mass production

basis. Many visual product inspection tasks rely heavily on manual labor and are prone to human error, leading to inefficiencies and increased costs. To stay competitive as a factory for Philips, it is important to eliminate these labor costs and replace manual visual quality inspections with flexible automated inspections. But the current automated visual quality control methods all rely on rule-based algorithms, which lack adaptability and consequently drive-up expenses. This means that we must improve the flexibility of these automated visual inspection systems and make them smart and are able to teach them fast, ultimately making automated quality inspection of personalized products possible.

Business needs/opportunities

PANDORA technologies address Philips' needs by offering solutions to be able to replace manual visual quality checks with automated quality checks, resulting in lower operational costs while enabling a fast marked introduction and personalization. Therefore, PANDORA will enable synthetic data generation for fast teaching vision check algorithms and will offer real time update & learning capabilities to improve quality checks based on real time data and judgment. In this use case we will focus on the vision check of ink jetted shaver parts, but the solutions can also be used in other areas. Currently, our inkjet printing process for shaver parts does not incorporate a vision inspection system, as this process is relatively new, and the production volumes are still low. However, we anticipate a significant increase in inkjet printing volumes soon. To address this anticipated growth and ensure consistent quality, we plan to implement an automated visual inspection system. This system must be capable of quickly and easily incorporating new graphics into the quality check process without requiring extensive manual programming or learning. This will prevent excessive time and cost expenditures when new graphics are introduced. We seek an AI solution that enables seamless integration of new graphics into the inspection system, ensuring efficiency and adaptability in our production workflow.

Desired outcomes by PANDORA

The implementation of the PANDORA framework aims to revolutionize the quality inspection process for shaver parts at Philips Drachten by leveraging cutting-edge AI technologies. This initiative seeks to address current limitations in adaptability, efficiency, and scalability of automated visual inspection methods. By focusing on AI-driven solutions, PANDORA aims to streamline production workflows, enhance fault detection accuracy, and reduce costs associated with manual inspections

Goals and objectives:

The following goals and objectives outline what PANDORA must achieve to meet Philips' requirements:

- **Fault detection:** The primary goal is to develop an AI-driven system capable of accurately detecting faults in the inkjet printed design on shaver parts. This system will utilize computer vision (AI) algorithms to analyze images of individual shaver parts obtained from a camera system and identify any defects present.
- **Training on synthetic dataset:** Initially, the AI system will be trained on a synthetic dataset of images generated from the new print design template only.
- **Real-time update capability:** Once deployed, the AI system should have the capability to update its knowledge base with real images captured by the camera system during production. This continuous learning process ensures that the system remains adaptive and effective in detecting new and evolving faults.
- **Explainability:** In addition to detecting faults, the AI system should incorporate explainability features to provide insights into the nature of detected defects. This may

include indicating the type of defect present and providing explanations or reasoning behind why a print is deemed faulty by the AI system.

- Scalability: The AI system should be scalable to accommodate multiple design templates and product variations and should have the capability to adapt to future design templates, for example by utilizing transfer learning techniques from designs that are already being printed on shaver parts.

Measurable outcomes:

The measurable outcomes serve as KPIs to evaluate the success and impact of the PANDORA framework in production:

- Accuracy: The primary technical KPI is to achieve an accuracy higher than 95% in detecting faults within the prints on the shaver parts. This metric should be continuously monitored to ensure that the inspection system meets the desired level of performance.
- Trustworthiness of synthetic images: Another crucial KPI is to measure the credibility of synthetic images used for training the AI system. The target is to maintain less than a 10% deviation from a benchmark test conducted on real dataset images. This ensures that the synthetic images accurately represent real-world scenarios and contribute effectively to the training process.
- Impact on process efficiency: Productivity KPIs will be used to assess the impact of the inspection system on process efficiency. The target is to ensure that the implementation of the AI-driven vision system does not have a negative impact on overall production efficiency.
- Financial impact: Cost savings KPIs will evaluate the financial impact of implementing the inspection system. The target is to eliminate manual labor costs, thereby achieving significant cost savings for the company.

3.4.2 Detailed Pilot Trial Cases description

Overall system description

Inkjet printing of shaver components:

Inkjet printing offers remarkable flexibility, making it ideal for producing small, specialized batches such as EK shavers, Star Wars-themed shavers, or even personalized designs. Currently, five different variants are in production as the process has just been introduced. Figure 3 analyses the basic inspections steps while in Figure 4 a schematic overview of the process steps and layout is presented.

Figure 3: Basic inspection steps

Figure 4: Schematic overview of the process steps and layout

Production volumes:

Approximately 3,000 units are produced per week, with a significant increase anticipated in the future as process stability improves. A full transition from tampon printing to inkjet printing across all shaver models is expected as process reliability is enhanced.

Quality control:

Currently, quality control of shaver parts is done manually. Quality control of hinges, which are produced on the same Digi7 inkjet printer, is already automated with a vision inspection unit. A similar system is being considered for shaver parts in the future, potentially using the same setup as for hinges. For hinges, each individual blade is inspected by a camera, with up to 40 blades inspected simultaneously on a carrier. The inspection process is currently governed by a rule-based algorithm. Plans for automating the quality control of shaver parts will be developed in alignment with this approach

Operational environment characteristics:

The following characteristics define the operational environment for the project:

- Test setup availability: A dedicated test location with the necessary skills is available and can be adapted to meet the specific needs of the project. Camera, lighting, and lenses can be optimized for the specific use case. The specific PANDORA setup needs to be built the coming weeks in the Shared Knowledge Innovation Learning Lab (SKILL) at Philips Drachten.
- Current capabilities: The current inkjet production line is only capable of inspecting hinges. There are plans to extend automated vision inspection to shaver parts as well.

Pilot infrastructure, main components, tools and deployment environment

The technologies/systems and infrastructure(s) to be used are the following:

- Manufacturing-IT: An advanced manufacturing IT/OT infrastructure including, but not limited to, edge devices, Kafka data pipeline, Kubernetes cluster managed by Rancher

(IRIS platform), and on-prem hosting and storage facilities. This infrastructure is illustrated in **Figure 5** and **Figure 6**, which show two different pilot infrastructure options using the Iris platform and Iris platform+edge. The Iris platform provides the foundational software for integrating various manufacturing technologies and data systems, enabling efficient data management and system coordination. The Iris platform+edge enhances this by incorporating edge computing capabilities, allowing for real-time data processing and decision-making directly at the manufacturing edge.

- Vision lab: Experimental environment for prototyping automated vision inspection systems.
- Rapid prototyping department: The Rapid Prototyping Department is a typical One Stop Shop for all prototyping requests. Within the department we distinguish eight different competences like model making, additive manufacturing, geometric measurement solutions.
- MES system: A new state-of-the-art data acquisition, storage, and MES system. This system consists of highspeed Ethernet and commercially available solutions to record and present data: e.g. Data Historian (Inmation) and MES system (MPDV Hydra).

Figure 5: Pilot infrastructure option A: Iris platform

Figure 6: Pilot infrastructure option B: Iris platform+edge

IoT components: sensors, actuators, processing, operating systems:

Regarding the key IoT components—sensors, actuators, processing systems, and operating systems—that will be utilized for the project, the current status is as follows:

- Sensors
 - Camera, Type, and System: The specific camera, type, and system needed for shaver parts will be determined in collaboration with the PANDORA team, FMI, and Philips.
- Processing:
 - Current System for Hinges:
 - Utilizes a Commercial available vision system from HALCOR with an extensive algorithm for quality inspection.
 - Currently, fixed rules are defined to determine acceptable quality
 - Future System for Shaver Parts
 - The best processing solution for shaver parts will be identified using the test setup.

Data description

The following data will be collected and utilized for the project:

- PDF file with design graphic
- ISI design file for printer input, converted from design PDF file
- Camera images from test setup in raw format from good and wrong products upon request. Experimental Protocol and Scenarios for validation

3.5 Use case 4 –AI driven Operations in Critical Hydrogen Infrastructures (FRA)

3.5.1 Introduction

Business context

Framatome is a leader in nuclear energy solutions, with a presence in over 20 countries and a strong legacy in reactor technology. Expanding its impact in sustainable energy, Framatome has developed its Covalion brand, which has been aiming at the transition to sustainable energy with

embarking in specializing in hydrogen and energy storage systems, which provides a comprehensive value chain of products, including feasibility studies, concept development, design, engineering, and full-system integration and delivery. It offers hydrogen solutions from generation and storage to handling, such as hydrogen refueling stations, supporting a climate-neutral transition in the mobility sector. The brand aims at bringing innovations to enhance energy systems by providing scalable and flexible hydrogen storage solutions. Through the PANDORA project, Framatome aims to apply AI within its hydrogen refueling station technology to advance predictive maintenance and ensure operational safety, cybersecurity, and efficiency. This approach aligns with PANDORA's framework for AI trustworthiness, reinforcing Framatome's commitment to innovative, reliable, and sustainable energy solutions.

Business needs/opportunities

The foundation of AI lies in the use of datasets. As acquiring data by itself is not an easy task, the even more challenging part is having it trustworthy and reliable. Hence the motive of the PANDORA project. Multiple sectors that use AI have cases that clearly showed the result of decisions taken based on biased datasets. For example, there is a healthcare-study [3] showing that an AI algorithm used in public hospitals in the USA has been biased in its decisions of kidney transplant, where it has favored patients with light skin color to patients who have darker skin color. That was due to the use of biased and underrepresented data when the use of variable extraction method has helped improve the reliability of the AI algorithm. AI has not yet been fully deployed in the field of sensitive infrastructure as it can cause major issues, such as data breaches, service disturbances or disruptions that could lead to severe consequences. That is why experts are cautious with the implementation of AI in such fields. However, if applied carefully AI has potential to help enhance safety, reliability, trustworthiness and efficiency, in various areas of even sensitive infrastructure such as:

- anomaly detection,
- prevention of hazardous situations,
- predictive maintenance,
- automated inspection (Framatome already does this with VTS⁵),

Having a framework for trustworthy dataset can help play a pivotal role in enhancing the overall quality, reliability and trustworthiness of AI systems.

Desired outcomes by PANDORA

The PANDORA project shall help to create trustworthy datasets for AI systems, which play a pivotal role in enhancing trustworthiness, quality and reliability of AI systems. The desired outcome shall contribute to various aspects but not limited to:

- improved data quality,
- transparency and traceability,
- enhanced data diversity,

⁵ Framatome's technology VTS(Visual testing Software) has aided making preventive maintenance easier. VTS uses video segments, to scan and detect for any existing damages. VTS provides time efficiency that can outperform human visual analysis. VTS preforms on site, also post analysis with real time capabilities up to 30 fps

- elimination of bias,
- introducing concept of fairness,
- security,
- flexibility,
- more reliable and trustworthy AI.

The availability of a trustworthy framework for dataset can be extremely beneficial for the area of hazardous technology (nuclear power generation, hydrogen handling) as the use of accurate data help the AI system in detecting safety issues, predict equipment failures and identify abnormal patterns. Some of the benefits that could be enabled by this framework, are the following:

- safety and risk mitigation,
- early fault detection and predictive maintenance,
- enhanced operational efficiency.

3.5.2 Detailed Pilot Trial Cases description

Overall system description

Under the brand Covalion, expert teams are leading the development of hydrogen refueling stations and large lithium-ion battery-based energy storage solutions to meet the increasing use of renewable energies for low-carbon transportation and temporary storage of electricity. Distributed systems in this area require more flexible remote maintenance concepts. Note that these facilities are usually critical infrastructures, which places additional reliability, functional safety and security requirements. Considering the current challenges of increasing cybersecurity threats, Covalion aims to ensure reliable operation of critical infrastructure, effective predictive maintenance strategies and a resilient cybersecurity posture. The fueling stations handle up to 100 buses per day, which requires a reliable and efficient process with necessity for a secure and transparent implementation. As the system has multiple access requirements to the different services it provides, different stakeholders need different access requirements (**Figure 7** shows how the access policy works), like the operator itself (“Operator A”), hydrogen providers, and the providers of different technical components for service activities and optimization (“Remote Maintenance XYZ”). The web-access is implemented in 2 different types according to the customers’ needs:

- By a secure gateway (product: ewon flexy) using 2-factor authentication and gives the remote staff just the right amount of access (using least privilege principle): 2FA Server grants Operator A only access to the internal Server and Remote Maintenance XYZ only access to PLC XYZ) to the internal network to interact with dedicated systems
- Demilitarized Zone (DMZ) with one jumper server in between to enhance network protection. With this option, external access is isolated from the internal network providing Operator A and Remote Maintenance XYZ with secure regulated access

Secure global communication

Figure 7: Secure communication

Operational environment characteristics:

The UC description refers to a hydrogen refueling station of Ruhrbahn Essen which is currently under construction. The refueling stations are already built and those in planning do not differ significantly in their design and functionality. The main refueling time for the buses is between 7 p.m. and 3 a.m. due to the current operating schedule. The total number of vehicles to be refueled is up to 120 fuel cell buses and fuel cell vehicles. The maximum refueling time is 10 minutes (including vehicle change), whereby the pure refueling time should last between 5 minutes and a maximum of 8 minutes. In addition, the entire process should take place without staff supervision. These specifications apply to all three dispensers installed. The hydrogen is initially delivered to the refueling station by trailer, whereby this can take place at any time. The maximum amount of hydrogen stored must not exceed 4.2 tons due to the Hazardous Incident Ordinance. Nevertheless, the buffer storage must be dimensioned in such a way that another refueling cycle of the entire bus fleet (101 buses) is possible in the event of a failure of the H2 delivery. **Table 4** lists some of the circumstances that can affect the operation of a hydrogen refueling station:

Table 4: Operational parameters affecting hydrogen refueling station

Parameter	Description
Ambient conditions especially temperature	Refueling is only possible at an ambient temperature between -40°C and +50°C in accordance with SAEJ 2601. Refueling is not possible outside this range.
Initial pressure (bus tank)	Refueling is not possible if the initial pressure is too high for certain ambient temperatures according to the refueling map.
Hydrogen availability	The operation of the refueling station may be impaired if there are insufficient supplies of hydrogen.
Maintenance	Regular maintenance of various components (storage tanks, compressors, sensors, etc.) is required. Failures may occur despite redundancy.

Error in measured values	Incorrect measured values from sensors can lead to unpredictable operating states that impair the functionality of the filling station.
Mechanical faults	Problems with mechanical parts such as pumps, valves or pipes can lead to interruptions in operation.

Pilot infrastructure, main components, tools and deployment environment

Figure 8 shows the structure of a hydrogen refueling station. The following components have not been included in the overview:

- Nitrogen supply (for inertization of the system),
- Compressed air supply (to control the pneumatic valves),
- Weather station.

Figure 8: Construction of the hydrogen refueling station

The hydrogen is supplied via connection panels A and B at 200 bar and 300 bar. The hydrogen then flows into the storage tanks, either directly or via the installed compressors, depending on the inlet pressure. The compressors are responsible for compressing the hydrogen so that it can flow into the bus to be refueled. The refueling process of the hydrogen-powered buses takes place via the three installed dispensers, whereby countless standards and guidelines must be observed (max. pressure increase, max. temperature). The software is programmed using a programmable logic controller from Siemens in the TIA Portal and is to be tested on a digital twin. This is programmed using the WinMOD simulation software and is currently still in the development phase. **Figure 9** graphically visualizes the distribution and connection of the individual I/O groups. Components from third-party providers and the client are color-coded. A consideration of IT security regarding the interfaces outside the company's own network (remote maintenance, client control room connection, client tank charging connection) has yet to be considered and is not part of this concept.

Figure 9: Network plan TCP/IP & Profinet

IoT components- sensors, actuators, processing, operating systems:

To ensure smooth operation and safety, a range of sensors and actuators are integrated into the hydrogen refueling station, monitoring and controlling various processes throughout the system. The most relevant components are listed and described in **Table 5**.

Table 5: Sensors and actuators in the hydrogen refueling station

Component	Description
Flow sensor	Measures the amount of hydrogen gas flowing through the pipe. This information is used to monitor and control the refueling process.
Temperature sensor	Measures the temperature of the hydrogen gas in the tanks and pipes to ensure that it remains within safety limits.
Pressure sensor	Measures the pressure of the hydrogen gas in the tanks and pipes to ensure that it remains within safety limits.
Concentration meter	Measures the concentration of the hydrogen in enclosed rooms to ensure it remains within safety limits.
Light Intensity sensor	Measures the ambient light conditions and can be used to control lighting systems, especially in areas with limited daylight.
Automatic valve	A valve that opens or closes automatically based on predefined parameters such as pressure difference or maximum flow to control the flow of hydrogen
Manual valve	A manually operated valve that can be opened or closed by an operator to control the flow of hydrogen.
Additional valves	Various types of valves such as check valves, needle valves, safety corner valves and control valves used for specific applications in the filling station to regulate hydrogen flow and safety.
Compressor	Compresses the hydrogen, which is then temporarily stored in storage tanks or refueled in the bus.
Heat exchanger	Heat exchangers are used to control the temperature during the refueling process. For example, a heat exchanger is installed in the dispenser to keep the refueling temperature within the required limits.

The sensors are installed in various versions as indicators and/or as transmitters for transferring the current value to the PLC. The valves can be controlled manually or via the PLC. Depending

on the application, binary or digital signals are used. The other installed components such as the compressor or the heat exchanger can be controlled via the manufacturer-specific signals.

Data description

Data generation:

The components installed in the hydrogen refueling station are generating various data. The generated data is described below before the structure and the format is explained.

Figure 10: Data transmission between a sensor and the PLC

The sensors generate a current signal between 4 mA and 20 mA and transmit this to the corresponding modules connected to the PLC. In the PLC, the signal is converted according to the limit values, with 4 mA representing the lower limit value and 20 mA the upper limit value. The following example of a pressure sensor with a measuring range of 0 to 600 bar demonstrates the data transfer. **Figure 10** shows that a current of 7.1 mA results for a pressure of 117,9 bar. This is related to the previously defined limit values of 4 mA to 20 mA and 0 bar to 600 bar. This method can be applied to all other measured variables (e.g. temperature, brightness, etc.).

Data format:

The generated data is converted into the corresponding unit values in the PLC as described above. The signals measured in real time are written to a CSV file and are then available. Trustworthiness of the real-life data from operating refueling stations is not guaranteed and the acquired data will go through a preprocessing phase to be synchronized, annotated and labeled. Whether existing solution is already sufficient or need to be improved to allow trustworthy AI results needs to be investigated. Simulated data exists only to some extent and currently without validation.

Data structure:

In the overall system of Bielefeld HFS, the data that is being received accounts for 275 input and 112 output data. Among the input data, 184 are binary, 60 are numerical, and 31 are data groups. For the output data, there are 100 binary attributes, 2 numerical attributes, and 10 data groups. Examples of input and output data are presented in Table 6 and Table 7, respectively. The first column in both tables lists the sensor names, the second column represents the attribute, the third column indicates the data type, and the last column provides the logical address used to locate the PLC in the network.

Table 6: Input data

Name	Path	Data Type	Logical Address
E_Kuehl_Annen_Allgemein	VAT_E_Annen	"udt_Annen_Recv_Allgemein"	%E2000.0
E_Kuehl_Annen_BetrZustand	VAT_E_Annen	"udt_Annen_Recv_BetrZustand"	%E2004.0
E_Kuehl_Annen_Energiedaten	VAT_E_Annen	"udt_Annen_Recv_Energiedaten"	%E2310.0
E_20ProzUEG_GaswarnKanal	VAT_E_Schaltsschrank	Bool	%E17.6
E_AnschlIT_ZustimmT_Entlueft_0	VAT_E_Anschlussstafel	Bool	%E1104.0
E_AnschlIT_ZustimmT_Entlueft_1	VAT_E_Anschlussstafel	Bool	%E1104.1
E_AnschlITafel_H2_20Proz	VAT_E_Anschlussstafel	Bool	%E1104.4

Table 7: Output data

Name	Path	Data Type	Logical Address
A_Annen_KontrBit	VAT_A_Annen	Bool	%A20520.0
A_Beleuchtung_Kreis01	VAT_A_Schaltsschrank	Bool	%A32.0
A_Beleuchtung_Kreis02	VAT_A_Schaltsschrank	Bool	%A32.1
A_DCS_Hofer01	VAT_Hofer01	"udt_DCS_Hofer_Steuerbits"	%A6006.0
A_DCS_Hofer01_Failsafe	VAT_Hofer01	"DCS_Hofer_I_DEVICE_Failsafe"	%A6200.0
A_DCS_Hofer02	VAT_Hofer02	"udt_DCS_Hofer_Steuerbits"	%A7006.0
A_DCS_Hofer02_Failsafe	VAT_Hofer02	"DCS_Hofer_I_DEVICE_Failsafe"	%A7200.0

Data collection has been ongoing since 2022. The most important data attributes identified so far are as follows:

- Bus refueling,
- Dispenser,
- Compressed air,
- Pressure changes,
- Flow,
- Pressure,
- Compressor,
- Temperature,
- Valve positions,
- Weather,
- Error Logs

Table 8 provides an overview of the analyzed error log data, enabling the identification of the frequency with which specific error IDs occur, their percentage relative to total error messages, and the associated components and error descriptions. Each ID corresponds to a distinct error type, offering insights into the source of issues within the system. The error log annotations have been completed and **Figure 11** presents a sample annotation for these logs.

Table 8: Error logs sampling

ID	Count	Percentage	Component	Log
2	2	0,017904	Notaus	Notaus: Knopf Kühlung betätigt / Notaus: Knopf Kühlung oder Dispenser betätigt
3	3	0,026855	Notaus	Notaus: Knopf Schaltschrank Innen betätigt
4	4	0,035807	Notaus	Notaus: Knopf LT-Container Aussen betätigt
5	13	0,116373	Notaus	Notaus: Knopf Brandschutzwand betätigt / Notaus: Knopf Brandschutzwand T01 betätigt
7	5	0,044759	Notaus	Notaus: Knopf Feuerwehr betätigt
12	2	0,017904	Notaus	Notaus: Knopf Brandschutzwand T02 betätigt
13	3	0,026855	Notaus	Notaus: Knopf Dispensersäule betätigt
19	5	0,044759	Platz A	Platz A: (V-005) 300 bar EL ZU nicht erreicht

```

{
  "datetime": "2024-01-03 22:28:27.890",
  "ID": 824,
  " Meldetext": "K\u00fchlung: 280_04_KM 12.2 - Kreislauf 2 - Niederdruck (=04+12.2-B8)",
  "component": "K\u00fchlung"
},
{
  "datetime": "2024-01-03 22:28:27.890",
  "ID": 930,
  " Meldetext": "K\u00fchlung: 65_04_KM 12.2 - Kreislauf 2 - Niederdruck (=04+12.2-B8)",
  "component": "K\u00fchlung"
},
{
  "datetime": "2024-01-03 22:27:33.889",
  "ID": 1982,
  " Meldetext": "Disp02: Sammelalarm",
  "component": "Disp02"
},

```

Figure 11: Annotation for the error logs

3.6 Use case 5 – Manufacturing AIoT Sensing Infrastructures (HALCOR)

3.6.1 Introduction

Business context

HALCOR is the copper and alloys extrusion division of ELVALHALCOR S.A. HALCOR Tubes Plant in Greece occupies 350 people and has significant expertise in copper tubes manufacturing. It produces approximately 80.000 tons of copper tubes per year. It is the largest plant of its type in Europe. HALCOR is committed to enhancing its energy efficiency and reducing consumption as part of ELVALHALCOR's broader strategy focused on energy transition. The company aims to increase the use of renewable energy sources (RES) in its energy mix, leveraging existing technologies and energy providers. This commitment is evident in their continuous efforts to improve overall energy efficiency and lower consumption across operations. HALCOR has developed an equation for predicting energy consumption and continuously improves the overall energy consumption model of the tubes plant monthly. The goal is to create sub-models for energy prediction at various work centers, which together form a comprehensive energy consumption prediction model. As part of the Horizon program, HALCOR is actively participating in the PANDORA project, which aims to develop a reliable AIoT system capable of predicting the energy consumption of the extrusion press over various time scales, including hourly, daily, monthly, and yearly scenarios. This system will play a crucial role in optimizing energy usage and reducing

costs. By implementing this trustworthy AIoT system, HALCOR can accurately predict energy consumption on different time scales. This precision aids in better planning and scheduling of operations to optimize energy use. For example, production schedules can be adjusted to align with lower energy rates, or machinery usage can be optimized to reduce peak load demands. Accurate energy predictions help HALCOR reduce its carbon footprint by minimizing unnecessary energy consumption and aligning operations with sustainability goals. This contributes to the reduction of Scope 1, Scope 2 emissions and is crucial for HALCOR's participation in programs like the European Emissions Trading System (ETS).

Business needs/opportunities

PANDORA Technologies addresses HALCOR's needs by offering advanced predictive modeling capabilities, enhancing data synthesis, supporting operational reliability, and facilitating long-term planning and optimization efforts.

- By accurately predicting energy consumption in the extrusion process, PANDORA supports HALCOR's goal of optimizing energy usage, thereby reducing operational costs and increasing efficiency.
- With the generation of synthetic data, PANDORA expands the size of the ground truth dataset, overcoming limitations posed by a lack of actual data and large data volumes. This enhances the accuracy and robustness of the predictive models.

PANDORA's models not only predict short-term energy consumption but also provide forecasts for longer periods ahead. This capability supports strategic planning, resource allocation, and decision-making to achieve environmental targets and sustainable operations.

Desired outcomes by PANDORA

The desired outcomes revolve around enhancing operational efficiency, reducing costs, supporting sustainability goals, and leveraging data-driven insights to drive continuous improvement and competitive advantage within HALCOR's operation. Development of a user-friendly tool that allows easy access to predictive insights, enabling users to make informed decisions based on energy consumption forecasts and analysis. This tool will provide the following functionalities:

- monitoring the operation of the Press (PRS) in terms of energy consumption,
- visualization of consumption and load forecasting based on the production plan,
- ability to receive production plans for various time periods with the aim of accurately predicting energy consumption (h/shift/d/w/y),
- creation of automated energy consumption reports for the PRS and its individual mechanisms,
- identification of optimal operating conditions and creation of benchmarks for the press,
- automatic notifications for meter issues,
- calculation of synchronization and load scenarios for mechanisms during the day,
- real-time monitoring of PRS mechanisms and comparison of current operation with benchmarks.

3.6.2 Detailed Pilot Trial Cases description

Overall system description

The entry point is the creation of a single “mother” tube from a heated billet (large solid cylinder) through extrusion with hydraulic press. The 15 to 30 meter long “mother” tubes are reduced in

diameter and wall thickness by either drawing or cold rolling at the proceeding production stages. Further reductions are performed at Breakdown lines and Spinner Blocks by drawing the tube further with successive passes, until the final or semi-final dimension is reached. The tubes can be finished either with a smooth inner surface or with a grooved integral enhanced inner surface in numerous profiles. The final dimensions and form of the tube, either coiled or straightened in lengths, is given in finishing lines. Further processing, if required, can be performed, such as degreasing, annealing, cutting to shorter lengths, insulating with PE foam and sheathing with plastic coating. The final step of production is the packaging and the storing of the tubes. **Figure 12** illustrates this production flow, outlining each key stage in the manufacturing process.

Figure 12: Production flow chart

Detailed Description of the Extrusion Process:

The scope of the PANDORA project is to focus on the extrusion process of the copper tubes. An overview of this process is presented in a series of figures (**Figure 13-Figure 19**). The detailed steps involved in this process are outlined below:

- i. The process begins with a copper billet being loaded into the natural gas furnaces. Just before entering, the billet’s engraved QR Code is scanned via an image-based QR camera, creating a unique ID (Pack ID) for each billet (see **Figure 13**).

Figure 13: QR Code Scanning for Billet Identification

- ii. The billet is then heated to approximately 800°C for about 1.5 hours to make it easier to shape and extrude. Each of the two natural gas furnaces consists of one preheating and six heating zones. Data about the billet's temperature and heating duration are collected for every zone, and the total energy consumed for each billet is also stored for every Pack ID (see **Figure 14**).

Figure 14: Natural Gas Furnace Heating Zones

- iii. Afterwards, the billet is loaded into an electric inductive furnace and positioned near three coils that generate an electromagnetic field, inducing an electrical current in the billet and generating heat through resistance. This step ensures quick and uniform heating, essential for high-quality extruded copper tubing. During this phase, critical data such as entering and exiting temperature, heating duration, and total energy consumed per billet are collected and stored for every Pack ID (see **Figure 15**).

Figure 15: Inductive Furnace Heating Setup

- iv. To enhance the quality of specific productions, an additional step of deoxidization takes place, where the billet is washed with water immediately after induction heating. This step is applied before induction heating when temperature precision before extrusion is crucial (see **Figure 16**).

Figure 16: Deoxidization Process for Billet Preparation

- v. Once the billet reaches the desired temperature (near 900°C), it is inserted into a preheated container (400–450°C setpoint), pierced with a mandrel, and pushed through a die using the hydraulic piston of the extrusion press. During this phase, critical data on the hydraulic pump pressures, piston positions, and duration of extrusion are collected (see **Figure 17**).

Figure 17: Extrusion Press and Preheated Container Setup

- vi. As the billet is pushed through the die and mandrel, it takes the desired inner and outer diameter, forming a continuous length of copper tube (Mother Tube) underwater, in a temperature- and level-controlled water reservoir. The water bath cools the extruded tube rapidly to room temperature, preventing oxidation, distortion, or deformation. The tube is water- and air-sealed at the edges (see **Figure 18**).

Figure 18: Cooling and Sealing Process for Extruded Tubes

- vii. Finally, the mother tube is surfaced (out of the water bath), and its edges are trimmed using saws (see **Figure 19**).

Figure 19: Surface and trimming process for Extruded Tubes

All the data mentioned above are provided by Programmable Logic Controllers installed across the production line. This data is accessible through an SQL Database containing a wide dataset for each unique Pack ID. Data unrelated to the billets' process conditions is stored and monitored by PLC analyser software.

Extrusion Press - Overview

Figure 20: Overview of extrusion press

Operational environment characteristics:

The operational environment for the press extrusion process (**Figure 20**) includes key factors such as temperature, pressure etc. Data from real-time monitoring and historical records are used to track performance and trends. The data collected are either time series (process parameters) or come from PLC Analyser’s real-time monitoring of the machine with detailed documentation on operating conditions, energy use, and maintenance schedules. Furthermore, an MES software tracks and documents the availability and performance of the extrusion Press machine. Examples of the data collected will be further discussed on “Data Description” section down below. These factors help in understanding and optimizing the press extrusion process.

Pilot infrastructure, main components, tools and deployment environment

The pilot infrastructure for the extrusion press process includes the following main components and tools: Plant’s Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system, Manufacturing Execution System (MES), Energy Monitoring System, Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) system, PLC analyser, and advanced reporting tools. PLC Analyser, visualized in **Figure 21**, offers a real time monitoring of all the critical I/O values of all the PLCs of the Press Department (Main Press, Gas Furnaces, Hydraulic Pumps, Inductive Furnace, Cooling Bath, Run Out Table, etc), as well as storage of the trends of those values (historical data). This system provides the ability to diagnose, analyze and also predict possible malfunctions of the equipment, being one of the most effective tools for the maintenance department.

Figure 21: Visualisation of PCL analyser

SCADA system offers the operator the ability to supervise and control the equipment of the press and also the ability receive crucial alarms that indicate undesired operating conditions. Through the Power Monitoring System, we have the ability to collect and analyze power measurement data (Apparent Power, Real Power, Reactive Power, Power Factors, etc) provided by multiple installed sensors within any specific time period. Due to the high number of sensors, we can achieve a detailed overview of energy consumption both for machine and departmental level. The structure of the whole Power Monitoring System and more specifically the Press Department meters are presented in **Figure 22-Figure 24**:

Figure 22: Power Monitoring System structure (view 1/3)

Figure 23: Power Monitoring System structure (view 2/3)

Figure 24: Power Monitoring System structure (view 3/3)

IoT components- sensors, actuators, processing, operating systems:

For our process monitoring, we employ sensors finely tuned to capture critical data points, ensuring optimal performance and efficiency. Simultaneously, we integrate sensors dedicated to monitoring our machinery. This comprehensive approach enables us to maintain a holistic view of our operations, facilitating proactive maintenance and maximizing productivity. The sensors contain among others: Energy Meters, Temperature sensors, pressure sensors, absolute and incremental encoders, position sensors (inductive, capacitive, on-off switches), level sensors (ultrasound), flow meters, etc. The actuators used are mainly hydraulic, electric and pneumatic.

Data description

For the extrusion press, we monitor approximately 100 different parameters. Some of the parameters from the MES software are listed in **Table 9**, while those from the PLC Analyser can be found in **Table 10**

Table 9: Parameters from MES software:

Parameter	Type	Description
CalendarTime	Int	Sum of calendar time in sec
Available Time	Int	Sum of calendar time the machine is scheduled for production in sec
Running Time	Int	Sum of time the machine is in production (Up Time) in sec
Not Running Time	Int	Sum of time the machine is stopped (Down Time separated in Procedural, Setup, Unplanned and Breakdown stops) in sec
Excluded Time	Int	Sum of calendar time the machine is not scheduled for production in sec
Speed Loss Time	Int	Sum of running time lost due to machine produced slower than the target time in sec
Availability %	Int	Performance of the machine in %
Performance %	Int	Performance of the machine in %
Inventory Produced	Int	Number of tubes produced in counts
OEE %	Int	Overall Equipment Efficiency of the machine in %

Table 10: Time series parameters from PLC analyser

Parameter	Type	Description
Press_Extrusion.Hours	Time	Time of Extrusion
Start-End Date	Date	Calendar date of Extrusion (0:00-0:00)
Production_Date	Date	Production date of Extrusion (7:00-7:00)
Pack_ID	String (40)	Unique identifier for the Extrusion
Auto_Billet_Loading_Duration	Int	Duration in sec of auto loading billet in press (from Transporter to center of press)
Beck_Pressure_Antiflow	Int	Beck water pressure in bar during antiflow (not extrusion time)
Beck_Pressure_Extrusion	Int	Beck water pressure in bar during extrusion
Billet_Length_After_Upset	Int	Billet Length in mm after upset
Billet_Length_Before_Upset	Int	Billet Length in mm before upset
Butt_Thickness_Act	Int	Butt thickness actual in mm
Butt_Thickness_Set	Int	Butt thickness setpoint in mm
Container_Position	Int	Container position in mm at start of extrusion cycle
Container_Sealing_Pressure_Max	Int	Container sealing max pressure in bar
Container_Temp_Die_Side	Int	Container Temperature in °C at Die side at the beginning of extrusion
Container_Temp_Middle_Zone	Int	Container Temperature in °C at Middle zone at the beginning of extrusion
Container_Temp_Ram_Side	Int	Container Temperature in °C at Ram side at the beginning of extrusion
Dummy_Block_Temp	Int	Dummy block temperature in °C
Extrusion_Length	Int	Length in mm of produced mother tube
Extrusion_Pressure_Avg	Int	Extrusion average pressure in bar at first 3 seconds of extrusion
Extrusion_Pressure_Max	Int	Extrusion maximum pressure in bar
Lift_Before_Piercing	Int	Ram back movement in mm before piercing
Mandrel_Drift	Int	Mandrel drift in mm at end of extrusion
Mandrel_Pressure_Max	Int	Mandrel maximum pressure in bar during piercing

Mandrel_Stop_IF_Die_Act	Int	Mandrel actual stop position in mm in front of die
Mandrel_Stop_IF_Die_Set	Int	Mandrel stop position setpoint in mm in front of die
Nitrogen_Flow	Int	Nitrogen Flow in lt/min
Number_Of_Billet	Int	Number of Billet that shown on the main operating panel of press (could be reset from the operator)
Press_Duration	Int	Press Duration in sec (Extrusion duration)
Puller_Clamp_Position	Int	Puller actual clamp positioning, distance from edge of tube in mm
Ram_Movement_Extrusion	Int	Ram movement in mm during extrusion step
Ram_Movement_Prextrusion	Int	Ram movement in mm during preextrusion step
Ram_Speed_Avg	Float	Average speed of Ram in mm/sec after puller engages and just before ramping down puller.
Ram_Speed_Max	Float	Max speed of Ram in mm/sec during extrusion
SKU_Recipe	Int	SKU Recipe of produced tube
Tool_Container_Extrusion_Counter	Int	Tool Container Extrusion Counter
Tool_Die_Extrusion_Counter	Int	Tool Die Extrusion Counter
Tool_Die_Extrusion_Ratio	Float	Tool Die Extrusion Ratio
Tool_ID_Container	Int	Container Tool ID (data from MES)
Tool_ID_Die	Int	Die Tool ID (data from MES)
Tool_ID_Dummy_Block	Int	Dummy Block Tool ID (data from MES)
Tool_ID_Dummy_Block_Counter	Int	Tool Dummy Block Extrusion Counter
Tool_ID_Mandrel	Int	Mandrel Tool ID (data from MES)
Tool_Mandrel_Extrusion_Counter	Int	Tool Mandrel Extrusion Counter
Total_Press_Cycle_Duration	Int	Total Press cycle Duration in sec
Upset_After_Ext_Act	Int	Upset Ram actual movement in mm after extrusion
Upset_After_Ext_Set	Int	Upset Ram setpoint movement in mm after extrusion
Water_Bath_Temperature	Int	Water bath Temperature in °C
Billet_Length	Int	Billet length coming from pusher sensor
IBE_Billet_Heating_Energy_KWH	Float	Total power consumption in KWH
IBE_CrossSection_Exit_Temperature	Int	Infrared temp measurement when heating finishes in °C
IBE_CrossSection_Temperature	Int	Infrared temp measurement when heating starts in °C
IBE_Duration	Int	Total duration of heating in sec
IBE_Temp_Set	Int	Set point of heating in °C
IBE_Zone1_Entrance_Temperature	Int	Infrared temp measurement when heating starts in °C
IBE_Zone1_Exit_Temperature	Int	Infrared temp measurement when heating finishes in °C
IBE_Zone2_Entrance_Temperature	Int	Infrared temp measurement when heating starts in °C
IBE_Zone2_Exit_Temperature	Int	Infrared temp measurement when heating finishes in °C
IBE_Zone3_Entrance_Temperature	Int	Infrared temp measurement when heating starts in °C
IBE_Zone3_Exit_Temperature	Int	Infrared temp measurement when heating finishes in °C
Duration_On_Furnace_Tottal	Int	Total duration of billet inside the furnace in sec
Duration_On_Zone1	Int	Total duration of billet in zone 1 in sec
Duration_On_Zone2	Int	Total duration of billet in zone 2 in sec

Duration_On_Zone3	Int	Total duration of billet in zone 3 in sec
Duration_On_Zone4	Int	Total duration of billet in zone 4 in sec
Duration_On_Zone5	Int	Total duration of billet in zone 5 in sec
Duration_On_Zone6	Int	Total duration of billet in zone 6 in sec
GBE	Int	Number of Gas Furnace used
GBE_Temp_Set	Int	Set point of Gas Furnace in °C
Heat_Number	String (20)	QR Code Billet acquired by scanning at entry (in conjunction with Foundry)
Zone1_Burner_Starts	Int	Number of burner firing-ups in zone 1
Zone2_Burner_Starts	Int	Number of burner firing-ups in zone 2
Zone3_Burner_Starts	Int	Number of burner firing-ups in zone 3
Zone4_Burner_Starts	Int	Number of burner firing-ups in zone 4
Zone5_Burner_Starts	Int	Number of burner firing-ups in zone 5
Zone6_Burner_Starts	Int	Number of burner firing-ups in zone 6
Zone1_Temp	Int	Infrared temp measurement just before leaving the heating zone 1 in °C
Zone2_Temp	Int	Infrared temp measurement just before leaving the heating zone 2 in °C
Zone3_Temp	Int	Infrared temp measurement just before leaving the heating zone 3 in °C
Zone4_Temp	Int	Infrared temp measurement just before leaving the heating zone 4 in °C
Zone5_Temp	Int	Infrared temp measurement just before leaving the heating zone 5 in °C
Zone6_Temp	Int	Infrared temp measurement just before leaving the heating zone 6 in °C
Press_Back_Saw	Int	Back-end piece cut off weight in gr
Press_Container	Int	Butt weight in gr
Press_Container_Cell	Int	Cell weight in gr
Press_Front_Saw_StartPiece	Int	Front end piece cut off weight in gr
Press_Front_Saw_EndPiece	Int	Back-end piece cut off weight (only for Pilger productions) in gr

4. Experimental Protocol

This section outlines the methodology for the experimental evaluation and validation of the PANDORA framework, providing a comprehensive approach that considers both technological and business aspects essential for developing a robust experimental protocol.

4.1 Introduction

The experimentation protocol is divided into two distinct cycles and is an active, continuous process throughout the project lifecycle. The 1st Cycle establishes the foundational elements of the project. It focuses on the AIoT trial scenarios and encompasses various categories of industrial requirements. During this phase, the PANDORA reference architecture plays a critical role in ensuring that all technical specifications are adhered to, thus guiding the development of the final framework to align with user needs and expectations. This cycle ensures that the system architecture meets the diverse technical demands necessary to support the solution's capabilities. The 2nd Cycle is dedicated to the deployment and evaluation of the PANDORA framework in specific industrial environments. This stage emphasizes practical application, where the framework is tested and assessed based on the actual business contexts it is designed to serve. As illustrated in **Figure 25**, an experimental setup will be defined, along with a detailed execution plan that outlines the stages of implementation. The primary focus of this cycle is to validate the framework's performance against the business requirements and objectives that were identified in the 1st Cycle. It involves close collaboration with industry stakeholders to ensure that the deployment not only meets technical standards but also delivers value in real-world operational settings. Overall, this two-cycle approach ensures that the PANDORA framework is both technically robust and viable from a business perspective, evolving through continuous feedback and iterative improvements throughout its lifecycle.

Figure 25: Experimental protocol of PANDORA

The primary focus of this cycle is to validate the framework's performance against the business requirements and objectives that were identified in the 1st Cycle. It involves close collaboration with industry stakeholders to ensure that the deployment not only meets technical standards but also delivers value in real-world operational settings. Overall, this two-cycle approach ensures that the PANDORA framework is both technically robust and viable from a business perspective, evolving through continuous feedback and iterative improvements throughout its lifecycle.

4.2 Methodology

4.2.1 The Requirements Analysis Framework

To support the realization of five (5) trial cases that will demonstrate incremental advancements and beyond state-of-the-art progress across a spectrum of interconnected, data-driven scientific achievements, the PANDORA project has structured a comprehensive Requirements Analysis Framework [4] early on. This framework serves to systematically identify, capture, document, and analyze the diverse categories of requirements, needs, and expectations of stakeholders regarding the final solution. The framework is designed to ensure that the developed solution aligns with both technological and practical considerations. It is divided into three (3) interrelated categories that form the foundation for the requirements analysis:

- **Business Requirements:** The business requirements represent the overarching goals and strategic priorities of the industrial stakeholders involved in the PANDORA project. These

requirements are essential for ensuring that the final solution aligns with the broader organizational vision, market trends, and value propositions. Furthermore, business requirements guide the project's trajectory to ensure it delivers measurable business outcomes and contributes to long-term success.

- **Data requirements:** The data requirements category focuses on the technical specifications and guidelines needed to manage and process data effectively throughout the project. It encompasses various aspects of data management, ensuring that the system is capable of handling the necessary data types, volumes, and complexities while maintaining high standards of quality and compliance. This category plays a crucial role in the success of the project, as data is at the core of most data-driven solutions.
- **Industrial/User Requirements:** These requirements focus on the practical and operational needs of the end users and industrial partners and result from the structured analysis of the previous requirements categories. Requirements of this category drive the system architecture and the technical specifications for the individual technologies of the framework. Furthermore, understanding user expectations is critical to ensuring that the solution is not only technologically sound but also intuitive, adaptable, and scalable within real-world applications.

Together, these categories form a holistic framework that ensures all aspects of the solution—from strategic objectives to technical implementation and user interaction—are thoroughly considered and addressed. **Figure 26** illustrates this interconnected framework, highlighting how these categories collaborate to create a robust foundation for the project’s success. The sub-categories will be analyzed in Section 4.2.3 together with the templates that circulated among the project partners.

Figure 26: Requirements Analysis Framework

4.2.2 GAP analysis

Developing robust AIoT trial scenarios in five diverse industrial settings is essential to ensure the technology is widely applicable, scalable, and robust enough for different industries and at the same time poses significant challenges with the main one to define realistic, feasible, and ambitious trial scenarios objectives that align with both the R&D goals and the operational

constraints of industrial providers. Therefore, a GAP analysis was incorporated during the development process for identifying and addressing discrepancies between the current state of industrial capabilities and the desired outcomes of the AIoT trials. GAP analysis [5] provides a detailed understanding of the current state versus desired future outcomes, which helps in creating a roadmap for AIoT implementation. In developing each trial scenario, we adhered to a structured four-step process. The first step involved the industrial partners conducting an assessment to identify the current state of their operations and procedures. This initial stage provided a comprehensive understanding of how their processes currently function, highlighting both strengths and limitations. The second step, a critical phase of the gap analysis, focused on defining the organization's desired future state. This involves setting clear objectives about where they want to be, outlining the improvements, efficiencies, or innovations that they aim to achieve. Essentially, this step is about envisioning the ideal or optimal operational state they aspire to reach. With both the current and future states clearly defined, the third step was to conduct a detailed comparison to identify the gaps—those areas where the most significant differences exist between present capabilities and future goals. This analysis helped pinpoint critical deficiencies and areas for improvement. By understanding these discrepancies, organizations could better target their efforts on the specific challenges that need to be addressed. Finally, the fourth step involved devising actionable strategies to bridge these gaps and achieve the target state. At this point, a technical partner was assigned to each use case, playing a key role in guiding and supporting the industrial partners. The technical partners facilitated the process by linking the most relevant PANDORA technology solutions to the identified gaps. Their expertise ensured that the proposed solutions were well-aligned with the specific needs of each organization, helping to drive a more effective transition towards their desired future state.

4.2.3 Way of Working

A common way of working towards the analysis of the requirements and the development of the AIoT trial scenarios was adopted in all use cases by incorporating the methodologies described in Sections 4.2.1 and 4.2.2, in a single template that was circulated among the contributors of the task. For each use case a technical partner was assigned to support and provide guidelines to the industrial partners in each stage of the definition of the scenarios.

The requirements analysis process begins with the first activity, scoping, which focuses on defining the business context and objectives of the scenario, along with the associated KPIs that will serve as benchmarks. This step is aimed at directing users' attention toward determining the boundaries of the solution and helps outline the initial scope of the system. The next activity (elicitation) follows a hierarchical approach where high-level business requirements are specified and then broken down into data requirements. by providing information about the data specifications for each scenario and the respective source (sensors, edge devices, monitoring or industrial systems, business software etc.). Finally, with the same approach user requirements are derived, whose analysis results in the definition of the system requirements.

In parallel, each project team was working on the actual implementation of the scenario by identifying the current state of the operations as a result of the existing technology capacity and the final conditions that they desire. The technology gaps were analyzed, and the relevant PANDORA strategy was proposed. Documenting the industrial context, specific workflows, operational environments, and industry-specific terminology ensure that all technical partners are familiar with the intricacies of each industrial sector. The purpose of the final activity (validation) is to ensure that the trial scenarios and the relevant requirements are realistic and achievable within the given constraints. Scenarios need to be ambitious enough to push the boundaries of AIoT technologies, yet realistic enough to demonstrate tangible benefits to industrial partners. It helps avoid setting goals that are too ambitious or out of reach due to existing technological or operational barriers, thereby improving the chances of project success. During the validation phase, the documented requirements, desired outcomes, and workflows were extensively

reviewed and discussed in a series of in-person meetings and remotely conducted workshops. These sessions involved the participation of all key stakeholders, including technical partners, industry experts, and use case (UC) providers. To streamline the process and ensure comprehensive input, a mutually developed template and questionnaire (see Section 4.2.1) was used. This tool facilitated the structured collection of information from multiple stakeholders, ensuring consistency in the feedback and enabling a detailed analysis of the requirements.

4.2.4 Scenario & Requirements Template

The template of the questionnaire we used to capture the requirements and develop the trial scenarios of the 5 organizations representing the manufacturing, critical infrastructure and smart building industries is presented in **Table 11**. The following template outlines the detailed categories and requirements considered essential for capturing each trial scenario and aligning it with the PANDORA project phases and objectives. This structured approach ensures all scenarios are comprehensively documented across business, technical, and evaluation dimensions. The template components are described below:

- Scenario Template
 - Scenario ID: A specific format was proposed to facilitate consistent tracking of scenarios across organizations
 - Scenario Name: Name designated by the use case author to uniquely identify each scenario
 - Authors: Names of the author(s) and associated organization(s)
 - Reviewer(s) and Other Stakeholders: Names of persons responsible for scenario reviews, along with any partners involved
 - Scenario Short Description: A brief 2-3 sentence summary requested from each author to provide a quick overview
 - PANDORA Phases: Identification of the applicable project phases (Phase I or Phase II)
- Business Requirements: This section captures the organization's overarching objectives and the role of each scenario within the business context
 - Business Goals: High-level business vision and strategic goals the scenario seeks to address
 - Data Preparation & Analysis Goals: Expected outcomes concerning Phase I of PANDORA, focusing on creating trustworthy, comprehensive dataset
 - AIoT Operational Goals: Operational objectives aligned with Phase II, targeting autonomous and energy-efficient AIoT operations
 - Business KPIs: Key performance indicators used to measure progress toward achieving the objectives
- Context & Workflow: Detailed description of the operational context, infrastructure, and workflow steps required to execute the scenario
 - Software & Hardware Components: Hardware and software systems currently in use or planned for the scenario
 - Workflow Description:
 - Initial Conditions: Description of pre-PANDORA operational and data conditions, highlighting opportunities for improvement
 - Final Conditions: Expected outcomes after implementing the PANDORA framework

- Identified Gaps & Relevant PANDORA Strategies: List of gaps or challenges and their alignment with project strategies
- Main Phase: Step-by-step breakdown of the primary operational phase, optionally presented with a sequence diagram
- Data Requirements: Specifies the data needed for scenario implementation and evaluation
 - Available Data: Relevant datasets for executing and evaluating the scenario
 - Data Sources: Sources from which data can be retrieved or made available
- User Requirements: Details the functional and feature requirements for the final framework
 - ID: Unique identification number for each requirement
 - UR Description: Standardized description of each requirement, e.g., “The PANDORA framework is able to/provides...”.
 - Priority: Priority assigned by the use case author, using modalities:
 - SHALL: Essential requirements critical to the scenario's success
 - SHOULD: Important but not essential requirements that would aid in achieving scenario goals
 - MAY: Optional requirements, valuable but non-critical, based on available resources
- Evaluation: Information for assessing technical effectiveness within each scenario context
 - KPI ID: KPI identifier as outlined in the Grand Agreement
 - Benchmark/Baseline: Benchmark or baseline against which progress will be measured
 - Target Value: Expected target for each KPI, as defined in the Grand Agreement
 - Monitoring Period: Designated period for KPI tracking and reporting
 - Responsible Partner: The partner responsible for monitoring and maintaining each KPI

This structured template was shared with industrial partners, along with specific guidelines and examples, to aid in accurately capturing scenario requirements and ensuring alignment with project goals and capabilities.

Table 11: Scenario template

Scenario Template			
Scenario ID	<i>Please specify</i>	Scenario name	<i>Please specify</i>
Authors	<i>Please specify</i>	Reviewers & other stakeholders	<i>Please specify</i>
Scenario short description	<i>Provide a summary of the scenario</i>		

PANDORA Phases	<i>Indicate the relevant phases (Phase I or/and Phase II)</i>	
A. Business Requirements		
Understanding business objectives	High-level business requirements	
What are the business objectives that the scenario serves?	Business Goals	<i>Please specify</i>
	Data Preparation & Analysis Goals	<i>Please specify</i>
	AIoT Operational Goals	<i>Please specify</i>
	Business KPIs	<i>Please specify</i>
B. Context and Workflow		
Software/Hardware components		
<i>Please specify</i>		
Workflow description		
<u>Initial conditions (before PANDORA):</u> <i>Please specify</i>		
<u>Final (foreseen) conditions:</u> <i>Please specify</i>		
<u>Identified gap & Relevant PANDORA Strategies:</u> <i>Please specify</i>		
<u>Main phase:</u> <i>Please specify (sequence diagram optionally)</i>		
C. Data Requirements		

Available data: <i>List the relevant data</i>				
Available data sources: <i>Indicate the sources where data is or will be retrieved</i>				
D. Industrial/User Requirements				
What are the requirements with respect to the PANDORA framework for the specific scenario?	ID	UR Description	Priority	
	UR1	<i>Please specify the requirement</i>	Select	
	URx			
E. Evaluation				
KPI id	Benchmark/Baseline	KPI target value	Monitoring Period	Responsible Partner
<i>Please specify</i>	<i>Information will be added later in the project</i>	<i>Please specify</i>	<i>Information will be added later in the project</i>	<i>Please specify</i>

4.3 AIoT Trial Scenarios

Table 12 provides an overview of the scenarios that will be realized in the context of the PANDORA project, while the filled-in templates for each scenario are provided in Sections 4.3.1 to 4.3.10.

Table 12: Scenarios overview

No	Provider	Sector	Business Objective	Scenario Name	Scenario ID	Enabled PANDORA Strategies	User Requirements	Available Data
UC 5	HALCOR	Manufacturing	Energy savings, optimized resource allocation based on data-driven decisions	Next-hour(s) consumption prediction	UC5S1	Strategy 1 Strategy 2 Strategy 3 Strategy 4 Strategy 5 Strategy 6 Strategy 7 Strategy 9 Strategy 10	Total: 15 Shall: 5 Should: 6 May: 2	ERP data, sensor data, analytical data, energy consumption data, production plans
			Energy savings, optimized processes & increase of productivity	Consumption estimation based on a production plan (production schedule)	UC5S2	Strategy 4 Strategy 5 Strategy 6 Strategy 10		

UC 2	EAB	Smart Buildings	Support 5G enabled deployments by promoting safety	Communication aware safe robot planning	UC2S1	Strategy 1 Strategy 4 Strategy 6 Strategy 8 Strategy 11	Total: 14 Shall: 6 Should: 5 May: 3	Robot sensing data, Robot SLAM data, Domain knowledge of environment generated via the mapping, 5G datasets
			Optimize the performance, cost, and efficiency of systems that operate within constrained networks	Trustworthy closed loop communication control	UC2S2	Strategy 1 Strategy 3 Strategy 4 Strategy 6 Strategy 7 Strategy 9 Strategy 11		
UC 1	SAG	Manufacturing	Accurate & fast sorting processes to enhance production efficiency	Delay too high	UC1S1	Strategy 1 Strategy 2 Strategy 3 Strategy 5 Strategy 6 Strategy 7 Strategy 8 Strategy 9 Strategy 10 Strategy 11	Total: 6 Shall: 2 Should: 2 May: 2	Servers related data (CPU & network metrics), Physical environment data (conveyor belt speed, arm sorter position etc.), Cycle times, Switches & Routers related data
			Optimized resource allocation to avoid idle times during sorting products	Cycle times too high	UC2S2	Strategy 1 Strategy 5 Strategy 6 Strategy 7 Strategy 8 Strategy 10 Strategy 11		
UC 4	FRA	Critical Infrastructure Plants	Ensure safe operations & maintain the desired service level	Increased operational safety	UC4S1	Strategy 2 Strategy 3 Strategy 4 Strategy 5 Strategy 6 Strategy 7 Strategy 9	Total: 11 Shall: 9 Should: 2	Continuous temperature & pressure readings, sensor data
			Enhance safety monitoring, risk management & decision making through simulations in a test environment	Continuous system improvement	UC4S1	Strategy 2 Strategy 3 Strategy 6 Strategy 7		
UC 3	PCL	Manufacturing	Accurate predictions for quality check on	Synthetic image data generation based on	UC3S1	Strategy 1 Strategy 2 Strategy 4 Strategy 6	Total: 8 Shall: 4 Should: 2 May: 2	Image data in png format, PDF

			printed shaver parts	product images		Strategy 7 Strategy 10		graphical design, Production data on product quality, CAD files of the shaver chests, ISI files with graphic designs
			Automated quality inspection system can be developed before product is made and/or production line is industrialized	Synthetic image data generation based on CAD drawings/3D models	UC3S2	Strategy 1 Strategy 2 Strategy 4 Strategy 6 Strategy 7 Strategy 10		

4.3.1 Use Case 1 - Delay too high (SAG)

Scenario			
Scenario ID	UC1S1	Scenario name	Delay too High
Authors	Dr. Arne Bröring (Siemens AG)	Reviewers & other stakeholders	Vladimir Kurbalija, Miloš Savić, Dušan Jakovetić (UNSPMF)
Scenario short description	In an industrial production cell, networked devices and software components control the correct sorting of work pieces. The network gets clogged, and the logic flow gets interrupted.		
PANDORA Phases	Phase I (Data Pipelines for Customizable and Trustworthy Datasets) and Phase II (AI services for continual, green and autonomous AIoT systems operation)		
A. Business Requirements			
Understanding business objectives	High-level business requirements		
What are the objectives that the scenario serves?	Business Goals	Support the product lines “IE” and “SCALANCE” in becoming more reliable. Provide elements for highly reliable, IE/network infrastructure	
	Data Preparation & Analysis Goals	Creating dataset(s) that enable the creation of AI to predict failures in IE / network infrastructures.	
	AIoT Operational Goals	Creating AI model(s) that predict critical failures in IE / network infrastructures.	
	Business KPIs	Realistic training data creation modelling infrastructure failure events and allowing AI trained models to predict infrastructure failures with an accuracy of 90%.	

B. Context and Workflow
<p>Software/Hardware components</p>
<p>The pilot infrastructure will be a laboratory that implements a small-scale production environment consisting of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • industrial communication networks, • edge computing devices and data center that run apps, • virtual PLC and AI apps to compute control logic and AI inference, • conveyor belt, arm sorter, camera and light barrier to transport work pieces. <p>To follow the future trend of virtualization (with the purpose of cost saving and improved maintenance), a vPLC (instead of a PLC) is utilized for the logic control. The vPLC is running as an edge app (which is essentially a Docker container) in an edge computing device or within the data center of an industrial plant. For data collection in the infrastructure, we will measure at different routers and switches traffic metrics, such as queue length, used bandwidth, packet loss. We will use protocols such as Netconf and SNMP to collect those data. Further, we will collect statistics about the network traffic (e.g., OPC-UA requests) on the servers and will collect at the same time CPU load and RAM usage. We will use tools such as OpenTelemetry to collect the data in Prometheus, Jaeger, or similar systems. The components of the infrastructure are listed below:</p> <p>Software:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Siemens Industrial Edge • Siemens SIMATIC S7 vPLC⁶ • AI inference server app⁷ • Grafana <p>Hardware:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Siemens IPC 1047E⁸ • ET200 • Routed IP network • Conveyor belt • Light barrier • Network camera • Arm sorter
<p>Workflow description</p>
<p>The scenario’s workflow is depicted in Figure 1:</p> <p><u>Initial conditions (before PANDORA):</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The conveyor belt is transporting work pieces. The light barrier triggers a camera, and an arm sorter is triggered to sort out “bad” work pieces. Therefore, the camera images are classified by an AI app in “good” or “bad”. A virtual programmable logic controller (vPLC) implements this control logic. The camera, light barrier, and arm sorter are connected via ET200. • The edge & local data center are managed by Siemens’ Industrial Edge (IE). Edge devices run app execution environment. The edge apps, sensors (e.g., cameras), actuators, and vPLC can communicate via industrial networks. The edge apps (vPLC and AI Server) are orchestrated to optimally use networked edge infrastructure. • Since the vPLC runs in a data center, a routed IP network is setup. VXLAN tunnel enables PROFINET traffic vPLC <-> ET200. Hence, the traffic prioritization implemented on OSI layer 2, is lost on OSI layer 3.

⁶ <https://www.siemens.com/global/en/products/automation/systems/industrial/plc/simatic-s7-1500/virtual-plc.html>

⁷ https://www.dex.siemens.com/edge/build-your-solution/ai-inference-server-dk?cclcl=en_EN

⁸ <https://mall.industry.siemens.com/mall/de/de/Catalog/Product/?mlfb=6BK1801-1>

Thus, traffic streams are sharing network, which may lead to clogging.

Final (foreseen) conditions:

- We measure at different routers and switches traffic metrics, such as queue length, used bandwidth, packet loss.
- We use protocols such as Netconf and SNMP to collect the data.
- We will develop a PANDORA AI model that can predict the traffic delay between vPLC and ET200 based on the collected data (as input to the model). A data collection mechanism will be employed to aggregate the traffic metrics from various routers and switches. Following this, feature analysis and dimensionality reduction techniques will be applied to retain only the most relevant information, ensuring efficient and accurate traffic delay predictions by the AI model.
- As ground truth (and labels for the AI), we will conduct network measurements at switch A and switch B to gather the true delays during the occurrence of certain events.
- In case a network clogging is predicted, the relevant apps are re-allocated to a server that utilizes a different network path. Alternatively, the upload of images to the cloud is paused / cancelled.

Identified gap & Relevant PANDORA Strategies:

In Phase I, PANDORA methods should:

- Enable collection and aggregation of data (**Task 5.1**) to efficiently manage and harness diverse data, as there is a great variety of available data sources (as can be seen in C) that will be used to achieve the scenarios' goals.
- Increase number of training data points through synthetic data generation (**Task 3.1, Strategy 1**) of “normal” as well as “anomalous” data points (reflecting infrastructure failures). Datasets collected under realistic conditions will not be enough to train the PANDORA AI models predicting edge / network infrastructure failures, as these failures are very rare. Thereby, examples of “infrastructure failures” are the clogging of network edges as well as CPU or RAM overload of server machines, which host relevant edge apps. Resulting from such “infrastructure failures” are “application failures” in the running edge apps, e.g., if pre-configured cycle times of the vPLC cannot be met. These “application failures” can then result in “functional failures” of the production environment, e.g., the incorrect sorting of work pieces. Thus, we will use methods and techniques developed in Task 3.1 (synthetic data generation) to increase the number of training data points. A model for synthetic data generation will be defined according to the guidelines provided by Task 3.1. The model should be able to generate both normal data points (reflecting regular working conditions) and anomalous data points (reflecting infrastructure failures). In addition to having lots of data samples, finding and retaining the most important attributes of each point is also important, as it can boost the performance of AI models, increase the explainability and reduces the processing time of the system.
- Enable finding and retaining the most important attributes of each point is also important, as it can boost the performance of AI models, increase the explainability and reduce the processing time of the system (**Task 3.5, Strategy 5**). Hence, a mechanism will be developed that based on feature importances and correlations applies dimensionality reduction techniques to retain only the most important information of each datapoint
- Enable relevant uncertainty quantification to minimize and prevent potential type I and type II errors (false positives and false negatives) (**Task 3.2, Strategy 2**).
- Enable integration or discovery of domain knowledge in/from the historical data (**Task 3.3, Strategy 3**).

In Phase II, PANDORA methods should:

- Increase the degree of autonomy, efficiency, robustness and intelligence of the production cell by continuous model updates (**Task 4.1, Strategy 7**).
- Enable appropriate explanations for end-users monitoring and controlling the production cell (**Task 4.2, Strategy 9**).
- Enable efficient inference mechanisms (**Task 4.4, Strategy 10**).
- Encapsulate techniques in appropriate as-a-service components (**Task 5.4**).
- Enable efficient and collaborative model learning (**Task 4.3, Strategy 8**), since the factory may contain more than one production cell operating in an edge-cloud computing infrastructure.
- Enable model inference mechanisms (**Task 4.5, Strategy 11**).

Main phase:

- In the first step, a “normal” mode is established, i.e., the infrastructure handles rare cases of “bad” work pieces and traffic C (of camera pictures to the cloud) without causing blocking traffic A or B.
- In the second step, an event occurs that many work pieces are sorted out as “bad” and their images are uploaded to the cloud, causing increased traffic C.

- Pre-PANDORA, this would result in work pieces being sorted into the wrong categories, because network traffic delays the correct handling of control logic.
- With PANDORA, the “PANDORA AI” model predicts network clogging in advance.
- The relevant apps are re-allocated to a server that utilizes a different network path. Alternatively, the upload of images to the cloud is paused / cancelled.

C. Data Requirements

Available data:

- Server machine data, such as compute Metrics (e.g., user CPU Time, system CPU Time, load average over 1, 5, 15 minutes, per-core CPU Usage) and network Metrics (e.g. bytes sent/received, packets dropped, send/receive errors).
- Data of the physical environment (e.g., conveyor belt speed, count of work pieces per minute, AI result of last camera image)..
- Data from the network devices (switches & routers), such as bandwidth utilization, connection statistics, error counts etc.
- Ground truth data, such as the delay between vPLC and ET200, or the cycle times of the vPLC will be measured while conducting measurements campaigns. The cycle time refers to the amount of time it takes for the vPLC to complete one full scan of its control program (i.e., reading all its input devices, program execution based on the input data, updating the output devices based on the results of the program execution, and performing internal tasks, such as diagnostics or communication with other systems). This value is crucial for ensuring that the system responds fast enough to control the process in real-time.

Available data sources:
The data is collected via OpenTelemetry and on each networked device data is collected and contributed.

D. User Requirements

	ID	UR Description	Priority
What are the requirements with respect to the PANDORA framework for the specific scenario?	UR1.1	PANDORA framework produces synthetic data based on a simulated environment to train AI models (T3.1).	Shall
	UR1.2	PANDORA framework provides an AI model to predict network outages and critical situations (T4.1, T4.4).	Shall
	UR1.3	PANDORA framework outputs explanations (T3.3, T4.2) as well as uncertainty assessments (T3.2) alongside predictions.	May
	UR1.4	PANDORA framework is able to support the distributed / federated learning of the AI model as well as its inference (T4.3, T4.5, T5.4).	Should
	UR1.5	PANDORA framework can gather and process data from various sources to ensure that the necessary information is available for training and evaluating AI models (T5.1).	May
	UR1.6	PANDORA framework can use methods to identify and keep only the most important data information, which helps improve the accuracy, understanding, and efficiency of AI models (T3.5).	Should

E. Evaluation

KPI id	Benchmark	KPI target value	Monitoring Period	Responsible Partner
KPI2.2.1		Increase models accuracy by 20%		IMT
KPI2.2.2		Reduction in model execution time by 20%		IMT
KPI2.2.3		Percentage of less operational data required for an		IMT

		experiment due to the quality of synthetic data > 15%		
KPI1.2.1		Increase accuracy of uncertainty prediction by 15%		DLR
KPI1.2.2		Deployment of at least one tool on uncertainty quantification for an energy efficiency problem > 1		DLR
KPI2.1.1		Decrease periodic human inspections on models due to encapsulation of knowledge from the smart spaces by 20%		UNIBO
KPI2.4.1		Improved quality of the understandability related output that supports the tracing of the domain-informed AI decisions by 20%		UNIBO
KPI3.1.1		Observed energy efficiency saved costs increase by 15%		UNSPMF
KPI3.1.2		Accuracy of federated learning and inference methods for data lifecycle management, subject to computing continuum infrastructure characteristics - 70%		UNSPMF
KPI1.1.2		Number of models trained >= 10		SAG
KPI2.3.1		Increased accuracy levels of real-time observations to capture out-of-distribution events by 20%		SAG & ITML
KPI2.3.2		Number of models deployed across the cloud continuum >= 3		SAG
KPI1.5.2		Decrease in data redundancy (Dimensionality		ITML

		reduction) >= 50 %	
KPI1.5.1		Number of models trained >= 3	ITML

4.3.2 Use case 1 - Cycle times too high (SAG)

Scenario ID information			
Scenario ID	UC1S2	Scenario name	Cycle Times too High
Authors	Dr. Arne Bröring (Siemens AG)	Reviewers & other stakeholders	Vladimir Kurbalija, Miloš Savić, Dušan Jakovetić (UNSPMF)
Scenario short description	In an industrial production cell, networked devices and software components control the correct sorting of work pieces. In a shift change, many technical workers want to access simultaneously the infrastructure, which leads to compute resource overload and too high cycle times in the logic control. The cycle time refers to the amount of time it takes for the PLC to complete one full scan of its control program (i.e., reading all its input devices, program execution based on the input data, updating the output devices based on the results of the program execution, and performing internal tasks, such as diagnostics or communication with other systems). This value is crucial for ensuring that the system responds fast enough to control the process in real-time.		
PANDORA Phases	Phase I (Data Pipelines for Customizable and Trustworthy Datasets) and Phase II (AI services for continual, green and autonomous AIoT systems operation)		
A. Business Requirements			
Understanding business objectives	High-level business requirements		
What are the objectives that the scenario serves?	Business Goals	Support the product lines “IE” and “SCALANCE” in becoming more reliable.	
	Data Preparation & Analysis Goals	The focus is on developing AI-based methods for predicting network and compute resource consumption. Further, historical data could be used to predict peak usage times and implement load balancing strategies to prevent future overloads.	
	AIoT Operational Goals	The focus is on ensuring the smooth and efficient functioning of the production cell during high-demand periods like shift changes. Implementing real-time monitoring and adaptive resource management could help maintain operational efficiency during peak access times.	
	Business KPIs	Realistic training data creation modelling infrastructure failure events and allowing AI trained models to predict infrastructure failures with an accuracy of 90%.	
B. Context and Workflow			
Software/Hardware components			

The pilot infrastructure will be a laboratory that implements a small-scale production environment consisting of:

- industrial communication networks,
- edge computing devices and data center that run apps,
- virtual PLC and AI apps to compute control logic and AI inference,
- conveyor belt, arm sorter, camera and light barrier to transport work pieces.

To follow the future trend of virtualization (with the purpose of cost saving and improved maintenance), a vPLC (instead of a PLC) is utilized for the logic control. The vPLC is running as an edge app (which is essentially a Docker container) in an edge computing device or within the data center of an industrial plant. For data collection in the infrastructure, we will measure at different routers and switches traffic metrics, such as queue length, used bandwidth, packet loss. We will use protocols such as Netconf and SNMP to collect those data. Further, we will collect statistics about the network traffic (e.g., OPC-UA requests) on the servers and will collect at the same time CPU load and RAM usage. We will use tools such as OpenTelemetry to collect the data in Prometheus, Jaeger, or similar systems. The components of the infrastructure are listed below:

Software:

- Siemens Industrial Edge
- Siemens SIMATIC S7 vPLC⁹
- AI inference server app¹⁰
- Grafana

Hardware:

- Siemens IPC 1047E¹¹
- ET200
- Routed IP network
- Conveyor belt
- Light barrier
- Network camera
- Arm sorter

Workflow description

The scenario's workflow is depicted in Figure 1:

Initial conditions (before PANDORA):

- The conveyor belt is transporting work pieces. The light barrier triggers a camera, and an arm sorter is triggered to sort out "bad" work pieces. Therefore, the camera images are classified by an AI app in "good" or "bad". A virtual programmable logic controller (vPLC) implements this control logic. The camera, light barrier, and arm sorter are connected via ET200.
- The edge & local data center are managed by Siemens' Industrial Edge (IE). Edge devices run app execution environment. The edge apps, sensors (e.g., cameras), actuators, and vPLC can communicate via industrial networks. The edge apps (vPLC and AI Server) are orchestrated to optimally use networked edge infrastructure.
- An OPC-UA server is installed on the vPLC and allows querying of data. A second server hosts a database and a graph visualization tool (such as Grafana). Technicians can access this tool to visualize the data from the vPLC.

Final (foreseen) conditions:

⁹ <https://www.siemens.com/global/en/products/automation/systems/industrial/plc/simatic-s7-1500/virtual-plc.html>

¹⁰ https://www.dex.siemens.com/edge/build-your-solution/ai-inference-server-dk?cclci=en_EN

¹¹ <https://mall.industry.siemens.com/mall/de/de/Catalog/Product/?mlfb=6BK1801-1>

- We measure at different routers and switches traffic metrics, such as queue length, used bandwidth, packet loss. In addition, we measure CPU and RAM usage and similar metrics at the server machines. A data collection mechanism will be implemented to aggregate these diverse metrics, ensuring comprehensive data availability.
- We will develop a PANDORA AI model that can predict the cycle times of the vPLC based on the collected data (as input to the model). To enhance the model's performance, feature analysis and dimensionality reduction techniques will be applied to focus on the most relevant attributes of the collected dataset, reducing data volume and improving prediction accuracy.
- As ground truth (and labels for the AI), we will gather the true cycle times during the occurrence of certain events.
- In case the AI predicts that cycle times are getting too high, the relevant apps are re-allocated to another server with more resources. Alternatively, the Grafana queries are cancelled.

Identified gap & Relevant PANDORA Strategies:

In Phase I, PANDORA methods should:

- Enable collection and aggregation of data (**Task 5.1**) to efficiently manage and harness diverse data, as there is a great variety of available data sources (as can be seen in C) that will be used to achieve the scenarios' goals.
- Increase number of training data points through synthetic data generation (**Task 3.1, Strategy 1**) of “normal” as well as “anomalous” data points (reflecting infrastructure failures). Datasets collected under realistic conditions will not be enough to train the PANDORA AI models predicting edge / network infrastructure failures, as these failures are very rare. Thereby, examples of “infrastructure failures” are the clogging of network edges as well as CPU or RAM overload of server machines, which host relevant edge apps. Resulting from such “infrastructure failures” are “application failures” in the running edge apps, e.g., if pre-configured cycle times of the vPLC cannot be met. These “application failures” can then result in “functional failures” of the production environment, e.g., the incorrect sorting of work pieces. Thus, we will use methods and techniques developed in Task 3.1 (synthetic data generation) to increase the number of training data points. A model for synthetic data generation will be defined according to the guidelines provided by Task 3.1. The model should be able to generate both normal data points (reflecting regular working conditions) and anomalous data points (reflecting infrastructure failures). In addition to having lots of data samples, finding and retaining the most important attributes of each point is also important, as it can boost the performance of AI models, increase the explainability and reduces the processing time of the system.
- Enable finding and retaining the most important attributes of each point is also important, as it can boost the performance of AI models, increase the explainability and reduce the processing time of the system (**Task 3.5, Strategy 5**). Hence, a mechanism will be developed that based on feature importances and correlations applies dimensionality reduction techniques to retain only the most important information of each datapoint

In Phase II, PANDORA methods should:

- Increase the degree of autonomy, efficiency, robustness and intelligence of the production cell by continuous model updates (**Task 4.1, Strategy 7**).
- Enable efficient inference mechanisms (**Task 4.4, Strategy 10**).
- Encapsulate techniques in appropriate as-a-service components (**Task 5.4**).
- Enable efficient and collaborative model learning (**Task 4.3, Strategy 8**), since the factory may contain more than one production cell operating in an edge-cloud computing infrastructure.
- Enable model inference mechanisms (**Task 4.5, Strategy 11**).

Main phase:

- Initially, the infrastructure works fine as it is designed for “normal” amounts of data requests. Then, an event occurs: a worker shift change happens, and the new technicians coming onto the shop floor are accessing Grafana. high CPU & RAM load on the vPLC. As a result, control tasks are not fulfilled and cycle times are missed, and work pieces are sorted wrongly.
- With PANDORA, the “PANDORA AI” model predicts this situation in advance.
- The relevant apps are re-allocated to a server that is more powerful. Alternatively, the Grafana queries are being cancelled.

C. Data Requirements

Available data:

- Server machine data, such as compute Metrics (e.g., user CPU Time, system CPU Time, load average over 1, 5, 15 minutes, per-core CPU Usage) and network Metrics (e.g. bytes sent/received, packets dropped, send/receive errors)
- Data of the physical environment (e.g., conveyor belt speed, count of work pieces per minute, AI result of last camera image)
- Data from the network devices (switches & routers), such as router Health (CPU Usage, Memory Usage), bandwidth utilization, connection statistics, error counts etc.
- Ground truth data, such as the delay between vPLC and ET200, or the cycle times of the vPLC

Available data sources:

The data is collected via OpenTelemetry and on each networked device data is collected and contributed.

D. User Requirements

	ID	UR Description	Priority
What are the requirements with respect to the PANDORA framework for the specific scenario?	UR1.1	PANDORA framework produces synthetic data based on a simulated environment to train AI models (T3.1).	Shall
	UR1.3	PANDORA framework provides an AI model to predict network outages and critical situations (T4.1, T4.4).	Shall
	UR1.4	PANDORA framework should support the distributed / federated learning of the AI model as well as its inference (T4.3, T4.5, T5.4).	Should
	UR1.5	PANDORA framework can gather and process data from various sources to ensure that the necessary information is available for training and evaluating AI models (T5.1).	May
	UR1.6	PANDORA framework can use methods to identify and keep only the most important data information, which helps improve the accuracy, understanding, and efficiency of AI models (T3.5).	Should

E. Evaluation

KPI id	Benchmark	KPI target value	Monitoring Period	Responsible Partner
KPI2.2.1		Increase models accuracy by 20%		IMT
KPI2.2.2		Reduction in model execution time by 20%		IMT
KPI2.2.3		Percentage of less operational data required for an experiment due to the quality of synthetic data > 15%		IMT
KPI1.2.1		Increase accuracy of uncertainty prediction by 15%		DLR
KPI1.2.2		Deployment of at least one tool on uncertainty quantification for an energy efficiency problem > 1		DLR
KPI2.1.1		Decrease periodic human inspections on models due to encapsulation of knowledge from the smart spaces by 20%		UNIBO

KPI3.1.1		Observed energy efficiency saved costs increase by 15%		UNSPMF
KPI3.1.2		Accuracy of federated learning and inference methods for data lifecycle management, subject to computing continuum infrastructure characteristics - 70%		UNSPMF
KPI1.1.2		Number of models trained ≥ 10		SAG
KPI2.3.1		Increased accuracy levels of real-time observations to capture out-of-distribution events by 20%		SAG & ITML
KPI2.3.2		Number of models deployed across the cloud continuum ≥ 3		SAG
KPI1.5.2		Decrease in data redundancy (Dimensionality reduction) $\geq 50\%$		ITML
KPI1.5.1		Number of models trained ≥ 3		ITML

4.3.3 Use case 2 - Communication aware safe robot planning (EAB)

Scenario ID information			
Scenario ID	UC2S1	Scenario name	Communication aware safe robot planning
Authors	Ajay Kattepur (EAB) Marin Orlic (EAB), Alessandro Previti (EAB)	Reviewers & other stakeholders	George Bouloukakis (IMT), Kostalas Nikos (AEGIS), Houssam Hajj Hassan (IMT)
Scenario short description	The 1 st scenario involves communication aware robot planning. 5G connected robots must autonomously traverse an indoor location to meet the intents.		
PANDORA Phases	Phase I (Data Pipelines for Customizable and Trustworthy Datasets) and Phase II (AI services for continual, green and autonomous AIoT systems operation)		
A. Business Requirements			
Understanding business objectives	High-level business requirements		
What are the objectives that the scenario serves?	Business Goals	Demonstrate the use of indoor 5G for reliable communication within industrial/enterprise environments.	
	Data Preparation & Analysis Goals	Synthetic IoT data of the environment to improve quality of training and generalize across a subset of smart spaces.	
	AIoT Operation Goals	Intents may be provided to the robots to:	

		Maintain speed Ensure specific communication throughput and low latency Prevent collision with obstacles
	Business KPIs	Accuracy of maintaining robust communication: Ensure that the intents on throughput and latency are maintained through the trajectory of the robot, Target: < 10% deviation Safety criticality (avoiding obstacles): Ensure that the safety conditions are maintained through the course of the operation, Target: Safe Path Deviation (SPD) < 5% Reduced battery consumption of robot: Plan the shortest path that ensures completion of goal with minimal battery usage, Target: 10% improvement from baseline Superior convergence times, Target: training times reduced by 10% Make decisions with high inference accuracy and react quickly to changes in its environment, Target: improved accuracy by 10%

B. Context and Workflow

Software/Hardware components

Software: ROS, robot controller, AI based robot path planner, AI based communication scheduler
Hardware: Robot with associated sensors and actuators, 5G antennas and base stations, Edge server

Workflow description

Initial conditions (before PANDORA):

- Robots typically follow pre-set topologies and are unable to adapt to new requirements (new intent targets on communication, changes in robot goals, robot speed variations).
- Robots may have unreliable connectivity and QoS throughout the navigation process.
- Safety constraints may not be met by the algorithms.

Final (foreseen) conditions:

- Automated planning systems incorporated with the robot enables autonomous operations.
- Reliable connectivity and QoS targets are ensured as constraints in the system.
- Safety intents are guaranteed by the algorithms.

Identified gap & Relevant PANDORA Strategies:

The following strategies are included as techniques to fill the gaps:

STRATEGY	UCSCENARIO USAGE	GOAL MAPPING
1	To generate datasets for uncertainty reduction and what-if analysis	Synthetic IoT data of the environment (Mostly connectivity data, as that is what is collected in the dataset) to improve quality of training and generalize across a subset of smart spaces.
4	To generate missing values or annotate dataset with symbolic knowledge	Synthetic IoT data of the environment to improve quality of training and generalize across a subset of smart spaces.
6	Needed for safe AI within robotic navigation	Prevent collision with obstacles

8	Federated Learning representations will be used to create models forming compact data representations and unsupervised anomaly detection models.	Maintain speed and ensure that there is specific communication throughput & latency.
11	Split Computing and Distributed Computing techniques will be used to provide efficient computations	Ensure speed and path changes efficiently computed with new intents.

Main phase:

The following steps are envisioned in the scenario:

- The user (or requirements system) inputs the domain model of the environment (map of location, constraints) to the robot planner.
- The user specifies the goal to be performed to the robot planner.
- Additional safety constraints may be specified, for instance maintaining speed, avoiding obstacles, preventing battery drain.
- Communication constraints are specified on throughput or signal quality, that are to be maintained.
- The network topology and locations of the 5G antennae are specified.
- The planning system generates a safe plan for robot navigation, that consists of a series of steps.
- The plan is dispatched to the robot controller for execution.
- The plan is executed step wise by the robot.
- The plan execution completes.

C. Data Requirements

Available data:

- Robot sensing data (Lidar, odometry, camera) collected from the robot
- Robot SLAM data collected from the robot
- Domain knowledge of environment generated via the mapping (Map of the environment as knowledge graphs RDF / JSON files. Additional hardware information on robot speed/model as well as 5G base station location, obstacle material
- 5G datasets (signal strength, throughput) collected from the radio performance measures

Available data sources:

- Robot sensors and ROS software
- 5G performance measure counters
- Map / domain knowledge of the environment

D. User Requirements

	No	UR Description	Priority
What are the requirements with respect to the PANDORA framework for the specific scenario?	UR1	PANDORA framework is able to generalize datasets across new terrains and/or obstacles	Should
	UR2	PANDORA framework can generate synthetic datasets with the necessary semantic information	Should
	UR3	PANDORA framework provides verification that the generated dataset for robot navigation reflects realistic scenarios	Shall
	UR4	PANDORA framework is able to use the validated dataset for obstacle avoidance and/or planning purposes	Shall
	UR5	PANDORA framework utilizes a federation of robots to detect anomalous behavior or intent issues	Shall
	UR6	PANDORA framework is able to generate missing data and annotations on the raw dataset	May
	UR7	PANDORA framework deploys the models using split or distributed computing topologies for efficiency	May
	UR8	The system must implement access control mechanisms to verify	Should

		and authenticate users (actors) before granting access to PANDORA's resources.		
E. Evaluation				
KPI id	Benchmark	KPI target value	Monitoring Period	Responsible Partner
KPI2.2.1		Increased model accuracy by 20%		IMT
KPI2.2.2		Reduction in model execution time by 20%		IMT
KPI2.2.3		Percentage of less operational data required for an experiment due to the quality of synthetic data by >15%		IMT
KPI1.3.2		Increase accuracy of models trained, based on the PANDORA labelling and annotation by 20%		UNSPMF
KPI1.3.3		Reduce human interventions by 50%		UNSPMF
KPI1.4.1		Decrease periodic human inspections on models by 20%		UNSPMF
KPI1.3.1		Increase labelling and annotation accuracy by 20%		UNSPMF
KPI3.3.1		Improvement of model re- training time >=10%		NTUA
KPI1.1.1		Increase models accuracy by 20%		SAG
KPI3.2.1		Overall implementation of the PANDORA traceability matrix at the end of the project >=95%		IMT
KPI3.1.3		Decrease in the response time for AI models inference >=20%		NTUA

4.3.4 Use case 2 - Trustworthy closed loop communication control (EAB)

Scenario ID information				
Scenario ID	UC2S2	Scenario name		Trustworthy closed loop communication control
Authors	Ajay Kattapur (EAB) Marin Orlic (EAB), Alessandro Previti (EAB)	Reviewers & other stakeholders	George Kostalas	Bouloukakis Nikos (IMT), (AEGIS),

		Houssam Hajj Hassan (IMT)
Scenario short description	The 2 nd scenario involves autonomous network control. The indoor 5G devices must be configured to meet communication intents.	
PANDORA Phases	Phase I (Data Pipelines for Customizable and Trustworthy Datasets) and Phase II (AI services for continual, green and autonomous AIoT systems operation)	
A. Business Requirements		
Understanding business objectives	High-level business requirements	
What are the objectives that the scenario serves?	Business Goals	Demonstrate the use of indoor 5G for reliable communication within industrial/enterprise environments.
	Data Preparation & Analysis Goals	There is high variability in the collected datasets for indoor 5G (measured in closed environments). The dataset should be appended to take care of: Changes in objects or human participants Changes in safety requirements Changes in number of users Changes in position of antennas
	AIoT Operation Goals	Intents may be provided to the robots to: Ensure specific communication throughput and low latency Prevent collision with obstacles Explain the 5G configuration Predictive learning models employed
	Business KPIs	Accuracy of maintaining robust communication KPIs: Throughput, latency, signal to interference and noise ratio can be specified to be maintained over intent expectations, Target: less than 10% deviation Prediction of deviation in QoS and autonomous actions, Target: >90% Superior convergence times, Target: training times reduced by 10% Make decisions with high inference accuracy and react quickly to changes in its environment, Target: improved accuracy by 10% Human operator can understand the AI's rationale, Target: Interpretability Ratio >95%
B. Context and Workflow		

Software/Hardware components		
Software: ROS, robot controller, AI based robot path planner, AI based communication scheduler Hardware: Robot with associated sensors and actuators, 5G antennas and base stations, Edge server		
Workflow description		
<u>Initial conditions (before PANDORA):</u> The current deployments of 5G connected robots have the following limitations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Robots may have unreliable connectivity and QoS throughout the navigation process. There is high variation in the collected datasets (outliers) that can cause machine learning algorithms to fail. Safety constraints may not be met by the algorithms. 		
<u>Final (foreseen) conditions:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reliable connectivity and QoS targets are ensured as constraints in the system. Safety intents are guaranteed by the algorithms using additional symbolic knowledge Via the use of AI techniques and data preparation, reduced uncertainty in QoS performance throughout the indoor environment may be guaranteed. 		
<u>Identified gap & Relevant PANDORA Strategies:</u>		
STRATEGY	SCENARIO USAGE	GOAL MAPPING
1	To generate datasets for uncertainty reduction and what-if analysis	There is high variability in the collected datasets for indoor 5G (measured in closed environments). The 5g connectivity dataset should be appended to take care of: i) changes in objects or human participants, ii) changes in safety requirements (dynamic obstacles, number of obstacles, distance), iii) changes in number of users, iv) changes in position of antennas
3	Needed to explain AI model outputs	Enable domain-informed explanations of the 5G configuration choices for the monitoring users.
4	To generate missing values or annotate dataset with symbolic knowledge	There is high variability in the collected datasets for indoor 5G (measured in closed environments).
6	Needed for safe AI for 5G configuration with intents	There is high variability in the collected datasets for indoor 5G (measured in closed environments).
7	We will use continual learning associated techniques to perform intent driven networking	Ensure specific communication throughput and low latency Prevent collision with obstacles
9	Needed to explain AI algorithm outputs	Enable domain-informed explanations of the 5G configuration choices for the monitoring users.
11	Split Computing and Distributed Computing techniques will be used to provide efficient computations	Ensure specific communication throughput and low latency Prevent collision with obstacles
<u>Main phase:</u> The following steps are envisioned in the scenario and illustrated in Figure 27: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The user (or requirements system) inputs the domain model of the environment (map of location, constraints) to the 5G planner. 5G datasets are collected by the planning system in the domain environment. The user specifies the goal to be performed to the 5G planner. The user specifies the goal to be performed to the robot planner. Communication constraints are specified on throughput or signal quality, that are to be maintained. Safety constraints on robot motion, obstacle avoidance and communication constraints provided. 		

- Planner sends initial configuration to the 5G controller.
- The robot controller triggers movement towards goals (driven by the robot plan).
- The AI prediction system determines the possibility of intent deviation.
- The AI prediction system informs the explainer on the predicted intent deviation.
- The 5G planner can trigger a closed loop configuration change.
- The 5G planner can also ask the robot controller to limit sensing rates to reduce network traffic.
- Model explanations are provided to the user.

Trustworthy closed loop communication control

Figure 27: UC2S2 workflow

C. Data Requirements

Available data:

- Robot sensing data (Lidar, odometry, camera) collected from the robot
- Robot SLAM data collected from the robot
- Domain knowledge of environment generated via the mapping (Map of the environment as knowledge graphs RDF / JSON files. Additional hardware information on robot speed/model as well as 5G base station location, obstacle material.)
- 5G datasets (signal strength, throughput) collected from the radio performance measures

Available data sources:

- Robot sensors and ROS software

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5G performance measure counters • Map / domain knowledge of the environment 				
D. User Requirements				
What are the requirements with respect to the PANDORA framework for the specific scenario?	ID	UR Description	Priority	
	UR1	PANDORA framework is able to employ synthetic datasets that capture variations in multiple factors (such as obstacles, antenna position)	Should	
	UR2	PANDORA framework can verify the validity of the synthetic dataset that are aimed to capture variations caused by multiple factors (such as obstacles, antenna position)	Shall	
	UR3	PANDORA framework provides accurate predictions for possible deviations in 5G throughput and latency	Shall	
	UR4	PANDORA framework is able to incorporate predictions into models that guide autonomous actions over the 5G network	Should	
	UR5	PANDORA framework is able to provide intuitive explanations for AI-based autonomous decisions	Shall	
	UR6	PANDORA framework is able to generate missing data and annotations on the raw dataset	May	
	UR7	PANDORA framework deploys the models using split or distributed computing topologies for efficiency	May	
	UR8	PANDORA framework will implement access control mechanisms to verify and authenticate users (actors) before granting access to PANDORA's resources.	Should	
E. Evaluation				
KPI id	Benchmark	KPI target value	Monitoring Period	Responsible Partner
KPI2.2.1		Increased model accuracy by 20%		IMT
KPI1.3.1		Increase labelling and annotation accuracy by 20%		UNSPMF
KPI3.3.1		Improvement of model re- training time >=10%		NTUA
KPI3.1.3		Increase in the response time for AI models inference by 20%		NTUA
KPI2.4.1		Improved quality of the understandability related output that supports the tracing of the domain-informed AI decisions >20%		CYU
KPI3.2		Overall implementation of the PANDORA traceability matrix at the end of the project >=95%		EAB & IMT

KPI3.1.3		Decrease in the response time for AI models inference $\geq 20\%$		NTUA
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4.3.5 Use case 3 - Synthetic image data generation based on product images (PCL)

Scenario ID information			
Scenario ID	UC3S1	Scenario name	Synthetic image data generation based on product images
Author	Christian van Kammen (PCL)	Reviewers & other stakeholders	Erik Koehorst (PCL), Erik Bloemsma (PCL), Maria Pateraki (NTUA), Konstantinos Tserpes (NTUA)
Scenario short description	To reduce the lead time for new automated visual inspection systems, synthetic image data will be created based on a limited sample of real images, taken with a physical camera setup, from a shaver part & design that need to be inspected. This sample contains good products and a limited set of products with possible visual defects. These pictures are input for the synthetic data creation. This synthetic data will then be used to train a classification algorithm to inspect visual quality print designs on shaver parts.		
PANDORA Phases	Phase I (Data Pipelines for Customizable and Trustworthy Datasets) and Phase II (AI services for continual, green and autonomous AIoT systems operation)		

A. Business Requirements	
Understanding business objectives	High-level business requirements
What are the objectives that the scenario serves?	<p>Business Goals</p> <p>Reduce time to market for new products Enable smaller batches Reduce innovation costs</p> <p>By developing solutions that enable automated visual quality control without losing time for teaching and adapting the algorithms with a lot of real samples with defects for each new design or part.</p>
	<p>Data Preparation & Analysis Goals</p> <p>The generated synthetic data helps the AI system to learn and understand the expected quality and appearance of the print designs without the need to have a huge number of real products made upfront.</p>
	<p>AIoT Operational Goals</p> <p>Response time Number of false positives Accuracy</p>
	<p>Business KPIs</p> <p>Reconfiguration effort to adapt or create models for new vision tasks. Target is to use less than 50 real data samples to generate synthetic data.</p> <p>Credibility of synthetic images used for training the AI system. The target is to maintain less than a 10% deviation from a benchmark test conducted on real dataset images.</p>

		Integration effort for the base model to existing production system and continuous update of the model based on real production images.
B. Context and Workflow		
Software/Hardware components		
<p>Off-line demonstrator:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frame for demonstrator (already available) • Lens (multiple versions available, best to be chosen) • Camera (Basler ace UacA2440-20gc) • Carrier for the ink jetted product (chest) • Light dome • PC / Server/data storage for images and inference of AI model • Printed shaver products (chest in colours Adriatic and Champagne Gold, with print in Philips and Norelco version, good and bad products with all failure types) <p>Software (<i>available and supported by Philips</i>):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Python (Pytorch, Tensorflow, Keras, OpenCV, Sci-kit learn) • MLFlow • Kubernetes framework for model inference • Production data 		
Workflow description		
<p><u>Initial conditions (before PANDORA)</u></p> <p>In existing situation all inkjet printed shaver parts are visually inspected by human eyes. The first check is done at the machine at the unloading location. A second manual 100% check of the production batch is done at the decorations Quality department. A different part, the inkjet printed one-blade parts, are already in line checked with an automated vision system, but this system is not flexible and teaching a new product will take a lot of effort and product samples (including errors). Furthermore, with the flexibility of the inkjet printer, there is a desire to print smaller volume batches with more product variation. An automated visual inspection system that is flexible and quick to configure to new print designs is needed, to reduce the amount of manual inspection labour.</p> <p><u>Main phase:</u></p> <p>During the main phase, the following steps will be executed:</p> <p>Philips:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specify demonstrator requirements and build demonstrator. • Generate data (images) of inkjet printed shaver parts (good products and products with print defects) with the new demonstrator setup and deliver to technical partners. • List of all error types will be shared, incl. examples of real products for Adriatic blue chests. For every failure type, pictures of the limit boundary samples will be made and shared as well as more a more severe variant of all failure types. • We will start with Champagne Gold chests; later Adriatic blue chests can be added to the datasets for further testing and optimizing. • Demonstrator will be expanded with AI inference function to test and evaluate trained algorithms. <p>Technical partners:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop algorithms to generate synthetic data. • Develop classification/anomaly algorithm to perform quality check on chest parts. • (Together with Philips) Test and evaluate algorithm on the demonstrator with new images. <p>The research questions formulated for technical partners are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How many image samples are needed to train a data generation algorithm for the inkjet printed chests? How many good samples, and how many samples of each defect category? 		

- Difficulties:
- Generally, large amounts of data (> 10.000 images) are needed. Are there ways to decrease the amount of data that is needed? Pretrained algorithms? Good quality images with fixed product positions and less environmental noise?
- How well does synthetic data correlate to real world samples?

Difficulties that may appear:

- Quality of Synthetic Data: Better quality and diversity in synthetic data translate to better performance with real data.
- Domain Shift: Differences between synthetic and real images can cause a drop in performance.
- Can the classification algorithm trained on synthetic data be fed with real world samples? Does this influence the performance of the classification algorithm?
- Difficulties:
- Generalization: The model might not generalize well if there are subtle but important differences between the synthetic and real data.
- Overfitting: The model may overfit to the synthetic data's characteristics, which could reduce performance on real-world images.

Final (foreseen) conditions:

Accurate predictions for quality check on printed shaver parts from an AI algorithm that is trained on synthetic data.

Identified gap & Relevant PANDORA Strategies:

The main question is the following: Is synthetic data generation a suitable option to quickly learn a model through visual quality inspection, without the need for a large amount of product samples?

Unknown how many image samples are needed to train data generation algorithms.

The following strategies are included as techniques to fill the gaps:

STRATEGY	SCENARIO USAGE	GOAL MAPPING
1	To generate synthetic datasets for enrichment of small real image dataset	Synthetic data of product images to improve quality of training and generalize across a subset of defects.
2	To generate synthetic datasets for uncertainty reduction of defect predictions	Synthetic data of product images to improve quality of training and generalize across a subset of defects
4	To annotate dataset of real production images automatically with defect type to get insight in failure type pareto.	(Semi) automated annotations, labelling of defects in real production images
6	Offline V&V of the overall complete dataset to prove if vision check trained on synthetic data performs on same level as trained with real images.	Validate performance of delivered solution
7	To update the base model with real product images	Improve the accuracy of the base model by continuous updating with real images
10	Use Continual Inference Networks to speed up the inference of DL models	Increase speed of the generated model

C. Data Requirements

Available data:

- Image data in png format (from good and bad products, as soon as demonstrator setup is built)
- PDF graphical design of the print design
- Step file of 3D geometry

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overview and description of all possible defect types 				
Available data sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> High quality image dataset of shaver chests in PNG-format MES system for production data 				
D. User Requirements				
What are the requirements with respect to the PANDORA framework for the specific scenario?	ID	UR Description	Priority	
	UR1	PANDORA framework provides a scalable and flexible image creation process to produce synthetic data.	Shall	
	UR2	PANDORA framework requires as input a limited sample of a X<50 images captured from a physical camera setup (demonstrator) to generate an accurate synthetic dataset.	Shall	
	UR3	PANDORA framework generates images that contain all failure types as provided by the Philips team	May	
	UR4	PANDORA framework provides annotated synthetic image datasets	Should	
	UR5	PANDORA framework provides models that can handle multiple background colors and graphic print designs	Shall	
	UR6	PANDORA framework can be supported by Philips (for example, Python source code)	Should	
	UR7	PANDORA framework will give insight into the defect types of real images (which can be used for making a pareto)	May	
E. Evaluation				
KPI id	Benchmark	KPI target value	Monitoring Period / amounts	Responsible Partner
KPI3.1.1		Observed energy efficiency saved costs increase by 15%		UNSPMF
KPI3.1.2		Accuracy of federated learning and inference methods for data lifecycle management, subject to computing continuum infrastructure characteristics increased by 70%		UNSPMF
KPI3.3.1		Improvement of model re-training time by 10%		NTUA
KPI3.3.2		Increase of model validation cycles by 20%		NTUA
KPI2.2.1		Increase models accuracy by 20%		IMT
KPI2.2.2		Reduction in model execution time by 20%		IMT
KPI2.2.3		Percentage of less operational data		IMT

		required for an experiment due to the quality of synthetic data by 15%		
KPI1.2.1		Increase accuracy of uncertainty prediction by 15%		DLR
KPI1.2.2		Deployment of at least one tool on uncertainty quantification for an energy efficiency problem by >1		DLR
KPI1.3.1		Increase labelling and annotation accuracy by 20%		UNSPMF
KPI1.3.2		Increase accuracy of models trained, based on the PANDORA labelling and annotation by 20%		UNSPMF
KPI1.3.3		Reduce human interventions by 50%		UNSPMF
KPI1.4.1		Decrease periodic human inspections on models by 20%		UNSPMF

4.3.6 Use case 3 - Synthetic image data generation based on CAD drawings/3D models (PCL)

Scenario ID information			
Scenario ID	UC3S2	Scenario name	Synthetic image data generation based on CAD drawings/3D models.
Authors	Christian van Kammen (PCL)	Reviewers & other stakeholders	Erik Koehorst (PCL), Erik Bloemsma (PCL), Maria Pateraki (NTUA), Konstantinos Tserpes (NTUA)
Scenario short description	To reduce the lead time for new automated visual inspection systems, synthetic image data will be rendered and generated from CAD drawings/3D models. 3D models are rendered to generate realistic images of the products, with and without randomized defects, and with environmental influences, i.e. lighting influences, reflections, dust, size and location variations, etc. This synthetic image data will then be used to train a classification algorithm to inspect visual quality print designs on shaver parts.		
PANDORA Phases	Phase I (Data Pipelines for Customizable and Trustworthy Datasets) and Phase II (AI services for continual, green and autonomous AIoT systems operation)		
A. Business Requirements			
Understanding business objectives	High-level business requirements		
What are the objectives that the scenario serves?	Business Goals	Reduce time to market for new products. Enable smaller batches. Reduce innovation costs	

		By developing solutions that enable automated visual quality control without losing time for teaching and adapting the algorithms with a lot of real samples with defects for each new design or part.
	Data Preparation & Analysis Goals	The generated synthetic data helps the AI system to learn and understand the expected quality and appearance of the print designs without the need to have a huge number of real products made upfront.
	AIoT Operational Goals	Response time Number of false positives Accuracy
	Business KPIs	Reconfiguration effort to adapt or create models for new vision tasks. Target is to use only CAD information and/or print design. Credibility of synthetic images used for training the AI system. The target is to maintain less than a 10% deviation from a benchmark test conducted on real dataset images. Integration effort for the base model to existing production system and continuous update of the model based on real production images.

B. Context and Workflow

Software/Hardware components

Off-line demonstrator:

- Frame for demonstrator (already available)
- Lens (multiple versions available, best to be chosen)
- Camera (Basler ace UacA2440-20gc)
- Carrier for the ink jetted product (chest)
- Light dome
- PC / Server/data storage for images and inference of AI model
- Printed shaver products (chest in colours Adriatic and Champagne Gold, with print in Philips and Norelco version, good and bad products with all failure types)

Software:

- Python (Pytorch, Tensorflow, Keras, OpenCV, Sci-kit learn)
- MLFlow
- Kubernetes framework for model inference
- CAD software

Workflow description

Initial conditions (before PANDORA):

In existing situation all inkjet printed shaver parts are visually inspected by human eyes. The first check is done at the machine at the unloading location. A second manual 100% check of the production batch is done at the decorations Quality department. A different part, the inkjet printed one-blade parts, are already in line checked with an automated vision system, but this system is not flexible and teaching a new product will take a lot of effort and product samples (including errors). Furthermore, with the flexibility of the inkjet printer, there is a desire to print smaller volume batches with more product variation. An automated visual inspection system that is flexible and quick to configure to new print designs is needed, to reduce the amount of manual inspection labour.

Main phase:

During the main phase, the following steps will be executed:

Philips:

- Provide CAD model of shaver chests.
- Provide print designs.
- Provide information on the defects that appear on inkjet printed parts (this information can be obtained from scenario 1)
- Provide material information of the shaver parts.
- Provide demonstrator to test and evaluate trained models and compare to real-world samples.

Technical partners:

- Generate synthetic dataset from a CAD model of a shaver chest (in Champagne Gold), with and without product defects, based on the same defects as in scenario1.
- Develop detection algorithm to perform quality check on chest parts.
- Improve and update the algorithms so it makes it possible to generate pictures quickly for a different type of inkjet printed part. Options to try: Different text (Norelco instead of Philips), different ink colours, different background colour, etc.
- (Together with Philips) Test and evaluate algorithm on the demonstrator with new images.

The research questions formulated for technical partners are the following:

- What method to use to create synthetic images for a product part?
- What input data is needed to generate and render images?
- How to make sure the simulated defects correlate to real world defects?
- How well does the synthetic data set correlate to real world samples?
- Can the classification algorithm trained on synthetic data be fed with real world samples? Does this influence the performance of the classification algorithm? Need for continuous learning for detection algorithm?
- What type of detection algorithm to use with this type of synthetic data, classification or anomaly detection?

Final (foreseen) conditions:

Accurate predictions for quality check on printed shaver parts from a classification algorithm that is trained on synthetic generated data. Automated quality inspection system can be developed before product is made and/or production line is industrialized.

Identified gap & Relevant PANDORA Strategies:

- Unknown what information is needed to generate images from a 3D model.
- Do we want to connect also to other parties working on this topic, like:
- Visual inspection with AI of synthetic image datasets (preml.io)
- <https://developer.nvidia.com/blog/how-to-train-a-defect-detection-model-using-synthetic-data-with-nvidia-omniverse-replicator/>

The following strategies are included as techniques to fill the gaps:

STRATEGY	SCENARIO USAGE	GOAL MAPPING
1	To generate synthetic datasets for enrichment of small real image dataset	Synthetic data of product images to improve quality of training and generalize across a subset of defects.
2	To generate synthetic datasets for uncertainty reduction of defect predictions	Synthetic data of product images to improve quality of training and generalize across a subset of defects
4	To annotate dataset of real production images automatically with defect type to get insight in failure type pareto.	(Semi) automated annotations, labelling of defects in real production images

6	Offline V&V of the overall complete dataset to prove if vision check trained on synthetic data performs on same level as trained with real images.	Validate performance of delivered solution
7	To update the base model with real product images	Improve the accuracy of the base model by continuous updating with real images
10	Use Continual Inference Networks to speed up the inference of DL models	Increase speed of the generated model

C. Data Requirements

Available data:

- CAD file of the shaver chests (3D geometry)
- PDF graphical design
- If needed, ISI files which contain the graphic designs and direct input for the printer
- Production data on product quality (input from scenerio1 should be used)

Available data sources:

- High quality product image dataset of shaver chests in PNG-format from scenario1
- (3D) CAD files of shaver chests
- ISI files of print designs
- MES system for production data

D. User Requirements

What are the requirements with respect to the PANDORA framework for the specific scenario?	ID	UR Description	Priority
	UR1	PANDORA framework provides a scalable and flexible image creation process to produce synthetic data.	Shall
	UR2	PANDORA framework requires as input a limited sample of a X<50 images captured from a physical camera setup (demonstrator) to generate an accurate synthetic dataset. Difference with scenario1 is that these images will be from another graphical design (so in this case the Adriatic blue chest, while synthetic images from the champagne gold chest have to be created)	Shall
	UR3	PANDORA framework generates images that contain all failure types as provided by the Philips team	May
	UR4	PANDORA framework provides annotated synthetic image datasets	Should
	UR5	PANDORA framework provides models that can handle multiple background colors and graphic print designs	Shall
	UR6	PANDORA framework can be supported by Philips (for example, Python source code)	Should
	UR7	PANDORA framework is able to generate synthetic image data based on CAD drawings/3D models	Shall

E. Evaluation

KPI id	Benchmark	KPI target value	Monitoring Period / amounts	Responsible Partner
KPI3.1.1		Observed energy efficiency saved costs increase by 15%		UNSPMF
KPI3.1.2		Accuracy of		UNSPMF

		federated learning and inference methods for data lifecycle management, subject to computing continuum infrastructure characteristics increased by 70%		
KPI3.3.1		Improvement of model re-training time by 10%		NTUA
KPI3.3.2		Increase of model validation cycles by 20%		NTUA
KPI2.2.1		Increase models accuracy by 20%		IMT
KPI2.2.2		Reduction in model execution time by 20%		IMT
KPI2.2.3		Percentage of less operational data required for an experiment due to the quality of synthetic data by 15%		IMT
KPI1.2.1		Increase accuracy of uncertainty prediction by 15%		DLR
KPI1.2.2		Deployment of at least one tool on uncertainty quantification for an energy efficiency problem by >1		DLR
KPI1.3.1		Increase labelling and annotation accuracy by 20%		UNSPMF
KPI1.3.2		Increase accuracy of models trained, based on the PANDORA labelling and annotation by 20%		UNSPMF

KPI1.3.3		Reduce human interventions by 50%		UNSPMF
KPI1.4.1		Decrease periodic human inspections on models by 20%		UNSPMF

4.3.7 Use case 4 - Increased operational safety (FRA)

Scenario ID information			
Scenario ID	UC4S1	Scenario name	Increased Operational safety
Authors	Oumayma Mejri (FRA), Martin Glückler (FRA), Esin Öztürk (FRA), Francis Wamba Fomi (FRA)	Reviewers & other stakeholders	Maria Pateraki (NTUA), Georgios Bouloukakis (IMT), Nikos Kostalas (AEGIS), Alexandros Iosifidis (AU)
Scenario short description	The use of AI can help adapt a more sophisticated safety and minimized operational cost system for the hydrogen refuelling station. Use of measurement data together with failures/error logs that would be correlated with timestamps to be able to predict anomalies like shutdowns of the station components in a proactive manner, which would help to increase the safety and availability.		
PANDORA Phases	Phase I (Data Pipelines for Customizable and Trustworthy Datasets) and Phase II (AI services for continual, green and autonomous AIoT systems operation)		

A. Business Requirements	
Understanding business objectives	High-level business requirements
What are the objectives that the scenario serves?	<p>Business Goals</p> <p>Detection of anomalies at early stages and to predict potential risks like components shutdowns or hot spots in advance, to increase the safety, availability and performance of the hydrogen refuelling stations.</p>
	<p>Data Preparation & Analysis Goals</p> <p>Several data is generated by the sensors located in the station, such data include temperature, pressure and error logs, labelling to anomaly's would be added to ease the detection process. The data would be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Synchronized annotated Labelled <p>The processed data can be used in a trustworthy manner to identify a reliable decision-making process for the ML.</p>
	<p>AIoT Operational Goals</p> <p>Implementation of an AI model should be able to:</p> <p>Detect HRS anomalies at early stage (Advanced Pattern Recognition) using unsupervised and/or supervised learning, with different anomaly conditions.</p>

		<p>Component shutdown Extreme high pressure Temperature out of range Identification of anomalies contributing factors with explainability. (strategy 9)</p>
	<p>Business KPIs</p>	<p>Detection of anomaly event prediction with supervised or unsupervised learning to avoid sudden system/component shutdown due to component failure, with across conditions such as component shutdown, extreme high pressure or temperature out of range. Target: Achieve an anomaly detection accuracy of 80%, accounting for diverse conditions and anomaly types. Explainability of Anomaly Contributing Factors, by identifying them and explaining the anomalies with clear insight. Ensure 80% of detected anomalies include explanations that are understandable and actionable, verified by HRS experts.</p>

B. Context and Workflow

Software/Hardware components

The Hydrogen refueling station has a different range of components ranging from hardware to software, and not all components are used for the completion of the scenario.

Hardware:
 The list of following hardware are the main entities that serve the achievement of the scenario, and this hardware represent the focus of our data (gathering data about these components is essential):

- 2 Compressors
- 2 Dispensers
- 4 High pressure tanks
- 2 Low pressure tanks
- Data server
- Main PLC

Software:

- HMI interface which is used for continuous monitoring of the state of station.

Workflow description

Initial conditions (before PANDORA):

At the Bielefeld Station, there is continuous monitoring to ensure safety and the healthy running of the process. In cases that threaten safety of component health, the relevant component or the entire system goes to the shutdown. Data would be processed, initial needed inputs would be chosen, different sources of input would be used such as temperature, pressure or flow, in addition some warning data such as error logs would be used as categorical data and could be used to be able determine if a component is about to fail or go in shutdown mode. All mentioned data would have to be pre-processed and go through the different phases of synchronization, labelling and annotation, to be able to reach a state where it be used as an input for the ML model.

Final (foreseen) conditions:

- **Automated Anomaly Detection:** The AI system continuously monitors sensor data and warning logs, autonomously detecting early-stage anomalies and predicting potential failures.
- **Anomaly Contributing Factor Identification with Explainability:** The system continuously monitors sensor data to detect the identified anomalies, with pinpointing the contributing factors and provides clear explanations to enhance understanding, supporting timely and informed decision-making.

Identified gap & Relevant PANDORA Strategies:

STRATEGY	SCENARIO USAGE	GOAL MAPPING
2	Quantify the uncertainty in the model predictions to better assess the reliability of anomaly detection results.	Using this strategy can help improve the decision-making process in order to reduce false positives.
3	Enable domain-informed data analysis for explainable AI	Derive useful insights about the data generation process and the causal relationships in the historical data.
4	Streamlines data preparation process by automating the labelling and annotations of dataset	This enhances the quality of input data for training and can expedite the training process.
5	Data summarization, dimensionality reduction, and fusion	Aid data redundancy and identify inherent clusters, helping the anomaly detection system focus on relevant patterns for more accurate and explainable predictions.
6	This can be used to help confirm true positives, implement verification and validation process to ensure the anomaly detection system preforms reliably and accurate with different operational conditions.	Identification of false positives along with human verification factor.
7	Model construction	Make predictions for failures and anomaly detection.
9	Explanations for model outputs. Employ a hybrid learning-reasoning approach to enhance explainability and causal understanding of anomalies	Make prediction and detection outputs explainable to facilitate better insights for decision making process.

Main phase:

The following two tasks are envisioned for the main phase of the system:

- Anomaly Detection and Pattern Recognition: The AI model, using both unsupervised and supervised learning approaches, should be trained to recognize early-stage anomalies in sensor data (e.g., temperature, pressure, flow). The model distinguishes between normal component behavior and abnormal (anomalous) conditions, ensuring timely detection of potential issues.
- Anomaly Contributing Factor Identification with Explainability: Once an anomaly is detected, the system identifies and explains the contributing factors, offering clear and actionable insights. These explanations help HRS experts understand the root causes of anomalies, supporting timely decision-making for mitigation. The AI system uses explainability techniques to ensure that 80% of detected anomalies provide understandable and expert-verified explanations, facilitating a deeper understanding of abnormal conditions.

. The intermediate stages to achieve the tasks are illustrated in the next Figure 28:

Figure 28: UC4S1 workflow

C. Data Requirements

Available data:

Measurement data as well as alarms/system errors are recorded through the PLC systems from the hydrogen refuelling station (HRS) in Bielefeld. The recorded measurement data come from different sensors installed on different equipment like compressors, valves, tanks, etc. located in different sectors in the station. The data collected can be split as follows:

- Numeric or continuous data such as temperature, pressure or flow changes, for the monitoring and control of different components (trends).
- Binary data such as positions of valves or switches (ON/OFF)
- String/text data and/or categorical data such as monitoring alarms and system shutdowns/errors (events)

The data preparation will consist in collecting the measurement data from the last 2 years. In the second step, a data understanding and description will be done. For each measurement sensor/parameter, the data type (numeric, binary/categorical or string/text like event description) and data source/path (HRS/System/Subsystem/Component/Sensor) will be identified and protocolled. The data exported from the Bielefeld station (measurement data and event logs) will then be cleaned, structured and imported in a time series data base (InfluxDB), to be reused for different kind of applications e.g. export as CSV, visual analytics, etc.). At the end of the data preparation, there will be 3 kinds of information available in InfluxDB:

- Sensor/Parameter data description (type, source/path)
- Sensor/Parameter time series data (data frame 1)
- Event logs (errors, shutdowns and alarms) as time series data (data frame 2)

Using the date and time information of both time series data in InfluxDB (data frame 1 and 2), it is possible to join both and finally create one unique data frame with annotated/labelled data and export it as CSV file. The data will be:

- Annotated
- Labelled
- synchronized

Available data sources:

From Covalion database, data is retrieved from the PLC that is generated through different sensors. According to P&ID (please check the attachment) of the Bielefeld HRS there are 13 temperature transmitters, 14 pressure transmitters, 13 pressure indicators, 3 flow transmitters, 76 valve position data sources in whole system. However, in the datasets we received from Covalion, not all sensors are used as input source.

Temperature:

- Sensors: Temperature Transmitters (TTs) located near compressors, dispensers, storage tanks, pipelines, and valves.
- Data Type: Continuous temperature readings that could show different temperature values, where temperature fluctuations can be noticed if it exists.

Pressure Data Sources:

- Sensors: Pressure Transmitters (PTs) and Indicators (PIs) throughout the system.
- Data Type: Continuous pressure readings.
- Possible observations via the monitoring: Leaks (pressure drops), blockages (pressure spikes), and irregularities indicating pump or compressor issues.

Valve Position Data Sources:

- Sensors: Valve Position Indicators and Actuators monitoring the open/closed status of valves.
- Data Type: Status over time (open, closed).

Flow Data Sources:

- Sensors: Flow Transmitters (FTs) measuring the flow rate.
- Data Type: Continuous flow measurements.

Issues Detected: Blockages, leaks, and overflows in the system.

All of these sensors store its data in a central data server located in the station.

D. User Requirements

What are the requirements with respect to the PANDORA framework for the specific scenario?	ID	UR Description	Priority
	UR1	PANDORA framework detects operational anomalies in HRS components early using time series data and error logs.	Shall
	UR2	PANDORA framework is able to predict potential component failures or shutdowns in advance to enhance safety and reliability.	Shall
	UR3	PANDORA framework is able to identify anomalies with an accuracy of 80%.	Shall
	UR4	PANDORA framework will provide metrics to evaluate performance against KPIs, including anomaly detection and prediction accuracy.	Shall
	UR5	PANDORA framework would facilitate anomaly detection by providing contextual data for experts to address and confirm identified anomalies.	Shall
	UR6	PANDORA framework helps ensure the model provides explainable outputs, allowing users to understand the rationale behind anomaly detection and predictions.	should

E. Evaluation

KPI id	Benchmark	KPI target value	Monitoring Period	Responsible Partner
KPI2.4.1		Improved quality of the understandability		CYU

		related output that supports the tracing of the domain-informed AI decisions by 20%		
KPI1.2.1		Increase accuracy of uncertainty prediction by 15%		DLR
KPI2.1.1		Decrease periodic human inspections on models due to encapsulation of knowledge from the smart spaces by 20%		UNIBO
KPI1.5.1		Number of models trained ≥ 3		ITML
KPI3.1.2		Accuracy of federated learning and inference methods for data lifecycle management, subject to computing continuum infrastructure characteristics by 70%		UNSPMF
KPI1.3.2		Increase accuracy of models trained, based on the PANDORA labelling and annotation by 20%		UNSPMF

4.3.8 Use case 4 – Continuous system improvement (FRA)

Scenario ID information			
Scenario ID	UC4S2	Scenario name	Continuous system Improvement
Authors	Oumayma Mejri (FRA), Martin Glückler (FRA), Esin Öztürk (FRA), Francis Wamba Fomi (FRA)	Reviewers & other stakeholders	Maria Pateraki (NTUA), Georgios Bouloukakis (IMT), Nikos Kostalas (AEGIS), Alexandros Iosifidis (AU)
Scenario short description	This scenario serves as an extension of our 1 st scenario, where it focuses on enhancing the implemented model in the first scenario on the continuous learning and optimization of the AI models used in anomaly detection. By regularly retraining models with new labelled data from recent anomaly detections, the system continuously refines its accuracy and robustness. Expert validation of detected anomalies ensures that feedback is integrated to improve the decision-making process and mitigate future system failures.		
PANDORA Phases	Phase I (Data Pipelines for Customizable and Trustworthy Datasets) and Phase II (AI services for continual, green and autonomous AIoT systems operation)		
A. Business Requirements			
Understanding business objectives	High-level business requirements		

<p>What are the objectives that the scenario serves?</p>	<p>Business Goals</p>	<p>The detection of anomalies in the first scenario would be employed in order to be able to serve the continuous learning of the model by using expert validation and integrate feedback, over time the system will be able to reduce false positives and improve the detection reliability by ensuring higher performance and operational safety.</p>
	<p>Data Preparation & Analysis Goals</p>	<p>The data used relies on both original data used in the 1st scenario and the output generated from the first scenario, would serve as an input to help be able make an output for this scenario.</p> <p>Collection of output from scenario 1: Use of anomaly detection results Annotate anomaly data. Labelling of anomaly data</p>
	<p>AIoT Operational Goals</p>	<p>The Implementation of an AI model should be able to:</p> <p>Preform continuous learning: Regular model retraining using data from the first scenario to be able to improve detection accuracy and reduce false positives.</p> <p>Expert feedback integration: Integrate expert feedback into the model in order to help refine the detection and enhance system reliability.</p>
	<p>Business KPIs</p>	<p>Model accuracy improvement. Target: Achieve an anomaly detection accuracy improvement of 10%.</p> <p>Reduction of false positive anomaly detection. Target: reduction of the false positives by 10% per retraining cycle.</p> <p>Continuous system performance improvement with each iteration of model retraining and validation. Target: 10% improvement overall</p>

B. Context and Workflow

Software/Hardware components

The Hydrogen refueling station has a different range of components ranging from hardware to software, and not all components are used for the completion of the scenario.

Hardware:

The list of following hardware are the main entities that serve the achievement of the scenario, and this hardware represent the focus of our data (gathering data about these components is essential):

- 2 Compressors
- 2 Dispensers
- 4 High pressure tanks
- 2 Low pressure tanks
- Data server
- Main PLC

<p>Software:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> HMI interface which is used for continuous monitoring of the state of station. 																	
<p>Workflow description</p>																	
<p><u>Initial conditions (before PANDORA):</u></p> <p>Data output from the first scenario would be processed, and the use of the results of the anomaly detection and explainability model from scenario 1 would be used to refine and improve system performance.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data output from scenario 1 would be collected and integrated: Use of anomaly detection results (from Scenario 1) as the primary input for retraining and model optimization. Possibility of use of same data from first scenario in addition to data output from scenario 1 Update dataset Annotate and label newly acquired data based on expert feedback for the detected anomalies, ensuring that false positives are accurately categorized. <p><u>Final (foreseen) conditions:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continuous Learning: Periodic retraining of the AI model using updated datasets to enhance accuracy and robustness. Expert Feedback Integration and false positive reduction: Regular validation of anomaly detection results by domain experts, whose insights will fine-tune the model, with a focus on minimizing false positives to refine the model based on past performance. <p><u>Identified gap & Relevant PANDORA Strategies:</u></p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>STRATEGY</th> <th>SCENARIO USAGE</th> <th>GOAL MAPPING</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Quantifying uncertainty in model predictions allows to assess the reliability of the anomaly detection results more effectively.</td> <td>Using this strategy can help improve the decision-making process in order to reduce false positives.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Leveraging domain knowledge for explainable learning</td> <td>using domain knowledge and leveraging it to improve anomaly detection accuracy</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Implement verification and validation processes to ensure the anomaly detection system performs reliably under different operational conditions.</td> <td>Confirms true positives and aids in identifying false positives with human verification, ensuring robust model performance.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>Regularly retrain the AI model using new anomaly data and expert feedback, allowing the system to adapt to evolving conditions and improve over time</td> <td>Improve the system's ability to continuously learn and adapt</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p><u>Main phase:</u></p> <p>The following steps are envisioned for the main phase of the system:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continuous Learning: To improve detection accuracy and robustness, the AI system undergoes regular retraining using newly labelled data from anomaly detection results. Periodically retrain the AI model using newly updated and annotated datasets from anomaly detection results. Incorporate recent sensor data and historical anomalies to enhance the model's detection accuracy and robustness over time. Ensure that retraining cycles are scheduled regularly to keep the AI model adaptable to changing operational conditions. 			STRATEGY	SCENARIO USAGE	GOAL MAPPING	2	Quantifying uncertainty in model predictions allows to assess the reliability of the anomaly detection results more effectively.	Using this strategy can help improve the decision-making process in order to reduce false positives.	3	Leveraging domain knowledge for explainable learning	using domain knowledge and leveraging it to improve anomaly detection accuracy	6	Implement verification and validation processes to ensure the anomaly detection system performs reliably under different operational conditions.	Confirms true positives and aids in identifying false positives with human verification, ensuring robust model performance.	7	Regularly retrain the AI model using new anomaly data and expert feedback, allowing the system to adapt to evolving conditions and improve over time	Improve the system's ability to continuously learn and adapt
STRATEGY	SCENARIO USAGE	GOAL MAPPING															
2	Quantifying uncertainty in model predictions allows to assess the reliability of the anomaly detection results more effectively.	Using this strategy can help improve the decision-making process in order to reduce false positives.															
3	Leveraging domain knowledge for explainable learning	using domain knowledge and leveraging it to improve anomaly detection accuracy															
6	Implement verification and validation processes to ensure the anomaly detection system performs reliably under different operational conditions.	Confirms true positives and aids in identifying false positives with human verification, ensuring robust model performance.															
7	Regularly retrain the AI model using new anomaly data and expert feedback, allowing the system to adapt to evolving conditions and improve over time	Improve the system's ability to continuously learn and adapt															

- Expert feedback integration and false positives minimization: While the AI model operates autonomously, detected anomalies and their contributing factors are periodically reviewed by HRS experts for validation. Expert feedback helps fine-tune the model by refining event lists and optimizing detection algorithms. This ensures continuous improvement in reducing false positives and enhancing system reliability over time.
- Anomalies detected by the AI system will undergo regular validation by HRS domain experts.
- Experts will review false positives, providing insights on system behaviour, which will be used to improve model accuracy.
- This process ensures that expert knowledge is continuously integrated, refining the decision-making capabilities of the AI model.
- Focus on reducing false positives through iterative model updates based on expert feedback.

C. Data Requirements

Available data:

The data used in this scenario includes both raw sensor data and the output from the anomaly detection system implemented in Scenario 1. These datasets are essential for the periodic retraining and continuous improvement of the AI model.

- Data output from scenario 1 would be annotated and labelled, which includes:
- Detected anomalies: The data used in this scenario includes both raw sensor data and the output from the anomaly detection system implemented in Scenario 1. These datasets are essential for the periodic retraining and continuous improvement of the AI model.
- False positives: Instances where anomalies were incorrectly flagged, including feedback from domain experts that help refine the model in future iterations.
- Combined Dataset: use of combined dataset would be applicable as sensor data and scenario 1 output data (detected anomalies, contributing factors) are integrated and synchronized for use in retraining the AI model. This combined dataset is crucial for improving system robustness and accuracy over time.

Measurement data as well as alarms/system errors are recorded through the PLC systems from the hydrogen refuelling station (HRS) in Bielefeld. The recorded measurement data come from different sensors installed on different equipment like compressors, valves, tanks, etc. located in different sectors in the station. The data collected can be split as follows:

- Numeric or continuous data such as temperature, pressure or flow changes, for the monitoring and control of different components (trends).
- Binary data such as positions of valves or switches (ON/OFF)
- String/text data and/or categorical data such as monitoring alarms and system shutdowns/errors (events)

The data preparation will consist in collecting the measurement data from the last 2 years in the second step, a data understanding and description will be done. For each measurement sensor/parameter, the data type (numeric, binary/categorical or string/text like event description) and data source/path (HRS/System/Subsystem/Component/Sensor) will be identified and protocolled. The data exported from the Bielefeld station (measurement data and event logs) will then be cleaned, structured and imported in a time series data base (InfluxDB), to be reused for different kind of applications e.g. export as CSV, visual analytics, etc.). At the end of the data preparation, there will be 3 kinds of information available in InfluxDB:

- Sensor/Parameter data description (type, source/path)
- Sensor/Parameter time series data (data frame 1)
- Event logs (errors, shutdowns and alarms) as time series data (data frame 2)

Using the date and time information of both time series data in InfluxDB (data frame 1 and 2), it is possible to join both and finally create one unique data frame with annotated/labelled data and export it as CSV file.

Available data sources:

From Covalion database, data is retrieved from the PLC that is generated through different sensors. According to P&ID (please check the attachment) of the Bielefeld HRS there are 13 temperature transmitters, 14 pressure transmitters, 13 pressure indicators, 3 flow transmitters, 76 valve position data sources in whole system. However, in the datasets we received from Covalion, not all sensors are used as input source.

Temperature:

- Sensors: Temperature Transmitters (TTs) located near compressors, dispensers, storage tanks, pipelines, and valves.
- Data Type: Continuous temperature readings that could show different temperature values, where temperature fluctuations can be noticed if it exists.

Pressure Data Sources:

- Sensors: Pressure Transmitters (PTs) and Indicators (PIs) throughout the system.
- Data Type: Continuous pressure readings.
- Possible observations via the monitoring: Leaks (pressure drops), blockages (pressure spikes), and irregularities indicating pump or compressor issues.

Valve Position Data Sources:

- Sensors: Valve Position Indicators and Actuators monitoring the open/closed status of valves.
- Data Type: Status over time (open, closed).

Flow Data Sources:

- Sensors: Flow Transmitters (FTs) measuring the flow rate.
- Data Type: Continuous flow measurements.

Issues Detected: Blockages, leaks, and overflows in the system.

All of these sensors store its data in a central data server located in the station.

D. User Requirements

	ID	UR Description	Priority
What are the requirements with respect to the PANDORA framework for the specific scenario?	UR1	PANDORA framework will be retrained periodically using updated datasets acquired ensuring continuous improvement in detection accuracy and robustness	Shall
	UR2	PANDORA framework allows domain experts to validate detected anomalies and integrate their feedback in the model	Shall
	UR3	PANDORA framework provides a functional element of reducing false positives by refining the anomaly detection model based on experts' insight	Shall
	UR4	PANDORA framework continuously monitors and report on key performance metrics, such as anomaly detection accuracy and false positive rates, to track and guide model improvements	Shall
	UR5	PANDORA framework automatically schedules and execute model retraining at defined intervals or when performance metrics indicate the need for improvement	Should

E. Evaluation

KPI id	Benchmark	KPI target value	Monitoring Period	Responsible Partner
KPI1.2.1		Increase accuracy of uncertainty prediction by 15%		DLR
KPI3.1.2		Accuracy of federated learning and inference methods for data lifecycle management, subject to computing continuum infrastructure		UNSPMF

		characteristics by 70%		
KPI2.1.1		Decrease periodic human inspections on models due to encapsulation of knowledge from the smart spaces by 20%		UNIBO

4.3.9 Use case 5 - Next-hour(s) consumption prediction (HALCOR)

Scenario ID information			
Scenario ID	UC5S1	Scenario name	Next-hour(s) consumption prediction
Authors	Efstathia Ziata (Halcor)	Reviewers & other stakeholders	Konstantinos Tserpes (NTUA), Aikaterini Tzompanaki (CYU), Alexandros Iosifidis (AU), Dimitris Reppas (ITML)
Scenario short description	Prediction of the energy consumption of the extrusion press based on past consumption patterns		
PANDORA Phases	Phase I (Data Pipelines for Customizable and Trustworthy Datasets) and Phase II (AI services for continual, green and autonomous AIoT systems operation)		
A. Business Requirements			
Understanding business objectives	High-level business requirements		
What are the objectives that the scenario serves?	Business Goals	Predict energy consumption based on recent and past energy and/or use of press patterns	
	Data Preparation & Analysis Goals	Data collection from multiple systems (incl. sensor networks) at a very low granularity (e.g. hourly) and a very long period (e.g., >24 months)	
	AIoT Operational Goals	Deliver real time data from sensors and other systems. Adapt prediction model on new conditions (changes in press settings, new products, changes in equipment/infrastructure, etc)	
	Business KPIs	Energy Cost Savings >= 2% Model Accuracy Improvement >= 10% Operational Efficiency Gain >= 2%	
B. Context and Workflow			
Software/Hardware components			
Data collection components (owned by HALCOR):			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plant's Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system Manufacturing Execution System (MES) (fault/status-related data, human entered data, coarse-grained) Energy Monitoring System Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) system PLC analyser (sensor data, fine granularity) advanced reporting tools 			
UI components:			

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dashboard with statistics, query submission mechanisms and result presentation views • web-based client
<p>Workflow description</p> <p><u>Initial conditions (before PANDORA):</u></p> <p>Existing tools for energy consumption prediction are using baseline technologies and are simple statistical tools (logistic regression) that do not take into consideration the production plan, nor the conditions that lead to a specific energy consumption value. The actual forecasting accuracy is limited and the method cannot scale to different time periods.</p> <p><u>Main phase:</u></p> <p>During the main phase, the following steps will be followed:</p> <p>Training:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A model that identifies consumption patterns (timeseries) will be created. <p>Inference:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The user will use the web-based GUI to request a prediction of the energy consumption for the extrusion press for the next hour. • The systems will collect data from the underlying HALCOR systems, executing prepared queries. Those data will provide the current situation of the press operation (and its components) • The system will collect the actual energy consumption from previous hours. • The system will run those data to make a prediction of the forthcoming hours' energy consumption. • The prediction, along with a confidence score and an explanation will be posted back to the user through the GUI and then stored to some storage for future reference. <p><u>Final (foreseen) conditions:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explainable, accurate, on demand predictions of the press energy consumption • Real-time Monitoring of the press's energy consumption with visualizations that compare current performance against benchmarks. • Identification of optimal operating conditions for the press, creating benchmarks for energy efficiency • Generation of automated energy consumption reports, with alerts for potential issues such as meter failures <p><u>Identified gap & Relevant PANDORA Strategies:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The duration of the periods for which the model will investigate for a pattern in the energy consumption is unknown and it is to be defined. • There is a great variety of available data sources (as can be seen in C) that will be used to achieve the scenarios' goals. To manage and utilize this diverse data effectively, a mechanism will be developed in T5.1 to collect and aggregate it. • It is unclear which of the data are contributing to a model that fits the energy consumption. Strategy #5 will help determine the most critical data features, optimizing the model's performance and ensuring it focuses on the factors that truly influence energy consumption. Strategy 3 can also participate in this problem, by finding causal structures from the data, with respect to the target variable (energy consumption). The model needs to adapt to previously unseen changes (new products, new machinery, new handlers) that affect the observations (Strategy 7). • Sensor data will be read at real time and runtime inference capabilities are expected to be required (Strategy #10). An explanation will be provided together with the prediction (Strategy 9). • There is uncertainty regarding the reliability of the predictions, particularly in how well the model can generalize to new or unseen conditions, which necessitates a robust uncertainty quantification strategy to assess the confidence in the energy consumption forecasts. (Strategy #2: Uncertainty Quantification) • Even though there are large amounts of data there are so many possible combinations of input conditions that it is not possible to rely only on those data to cover all possible cases. Some strategy for synthetic data generation and/or data augmentation could help (Strategy #1: Synthetic Data Generation).

C. Data Requirements				
Available data: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ERP data • fault/status-related data, human entered data, coarse-grained • sensor data, fine granularity • analytical data • energy consumption data • production plans 				
Available data sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plant’s Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system • Manufacturing Execution System (MES) (fault/status-related data, human entered data, coarse-grained) • Energy Monitoring System • Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) system • PLC analyser (sensor data, fine granularity) • advanced reporting tools • production plan logs 				
D. User Requirements				
What are the requirements with respect to the PANDORA framework for the specific scenario?	ID	UR Description		Priority
	UR1	PANDORA framework provides accurate and timely predictions, within specified error margins, across various time frames (e.g., next hour, day, etc.), with results generated in real-time or within a few seconds.		Shall
	UR2	PANDORA framework provides that models remain reliable over different time frames and operational conditions, and its algorithms shall be updated regularly to reflect changes in operations and environment.		Shall
	UR3	PANDORA framework provides an easy to navigate user interface with a feedback mechanism on input data validity, and report prediction processing status		Should
	UR4	PANDORA framework provides an analysis of reasons for deviations in energy consumption predictions, highlighting factors that contribute to unexpected variations and supporting users in understanding prediction outcomes.		Should
	UR5	PANDORA framework provides a mechanism for users to give feedback on the system's predictions and usability.		Should
	UR6	PANDORA framework is able to create benchmarks for optimal energy performance and generate automated alerts for significant deviations, failures, or anomalies		Should
	UR7	PANDORA framework is able to identify and prioritize the most relevant features and data sources that contribute to accurate energy consumption predictions, reducing data processing time and enhancing model explainability		May
	UR8	PANDORA framework provides real-time monitoring of the press's consumption, displaying current data and trends		Should
	UR9	PANDORA framework provides detailed reports that include predicted energy consumption, variance from typical consumption, and confidence intervals		Shall
E. Evaluation				
KPI id	Benchmark	KPI target value	Monitoring Period	Responsible

				Partner
KPI1.1.2		Number of models trained ≥ 10)		SAG
KPI1.2.1		Increase accuracy of uncertainty prediction by 15%		DLR
KPI1.2.2		Deployment of at least one tool on uncertainty quantification for an energy efficiency problem)		DLR
KPI2.4.1		Improved quality of the understandability related output that supports the tracing of the domain-informed AI decisions $>20\%$).		CYU
KPI3.1.1		Observed energy efficiency saved costs increase by 15%		FRA & HALCOR
KPI4.1.1		Number of scenario variations defined per domain ≥ 2		FRA
KPI5.1.1		Number of industrial sectors reached ≥ 5		DIE, STS
KPI1.5.2		Decrease in data redundancy (Dimensionality reduction) $\geq 50\%$		ITML
KPI1.5.1		Number of models trained ≥ 3		ITML

4.3.10 Use case 5 - Consumption estimation based on a production plan (HALCOR)

Scenario ID information			
Scenario ID	UC5S2	Scenario name	Consumption estimation based on a production plan (production schedule)
Authors	Efstathia Ziata (Halcor)	Reviewers & other stakeholders	Konstantinos Tserpes (NTUA) Aikaterini Tzompanaki (CYU) Alexandros Iosifidis (AU) Dimitris Reppas (ITML)
Scenario short description	Estimation of the energy consumption of the extrusion press based on production planning.		
PANDORA Phases	Phase I (Data Pipelines for Customizable and Trustworthy Datasets) and Phase II (AI services for continual, green and autonomous AIoT systems operation)		
A. Business Requirements			
Understanding	High-level business requirements		

business objectives		
What are the objectives that the scenario serves?	Business Goals	Retrieve estimates of energy consumption based on the planned use of the press (production plan)
	Data Preparation & Analysis Goals	Data collection from multiple systems (incl. sensor networks) at a very low granularity (e.g. hourly) and a very long period (e.g., >24 months)
	AIoT Operational Goals	Deliver real time data from sensors and other systems. Adapt estimation model on new conditions (changes in press settings, new products, changes in equipment/infrastructure, etc)
	Business KPIs	Energy Cost Savings >= 2% Model Accuracy Improvement >= 10% Operational Efficiency Gain >= 2%
B. Context and Workflow		
Software/Hardware components		
<p>Data collection components (owned by HALCOR):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plant’s Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system • Manufacturing Execution System (MES) (fault/status-related data, human entered data, coarse-grained) • Energy Monitoring System • Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) system • PLC analyser (sensor data, fine granularity) • advanced reporting tools <p>UI components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dashboard with statistics, query submission mechanisms and result presentation views • web-based client 		
Workflow description		
<p><u>Initial conditions (before PANDORA):</u></p> <p>Existing tools for energy consumption prediction are using baseline technologies and are simple statistical tools (logistic regression) that do not take into consideration the production plan, nor the conditions that lead to a specific energy consumption value. The actual prediction/forecasting accuracy is limited and the method cannot scale to different time periods.</p> <p><u>Main phase:</u></p> <p>During the main phase, the following steps will be followed:</p> <p>Training:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A model that correlates consumption with current conditions (from sensor data etc) will be created. • A model that correlated consumption with specific product production <p>Inference:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The user will use the web-based GUI to request an estimation of the energy consumption for the extrusion press for a future period based on a production plan. • The system will collect or request through the GUI data about future period production plan. • The system will run those data from one or more models and make an estimation of the future period energy consumption. • The estimation, along with a confidence score will be posted back to the user through the GUI and then stored to some storage for future reference. 		

Final (foreseen) conditions:

- Accurate, on demand predictions of the press energy consumption
- Real-time Monitoring of the press’s energy consumption with visualizations that compare current performance against benchmarks.
- Identification of optimal operating conditions for the press, creating benchmarks for energy efficiency
- Generation of automated energy consumption reports, with alerts for potential issues such as meter failures

Identified gap & Relevant PANDORA Strategies:

- The dataset that links the product to the press settings is scrubbed and with missing values (strategy #4: semi-automated annotations)
- One unknown variable is the downtime. There is limited information about why it happened, just that it happened. (Strategy #7: Robust and resilient learning)
- The model needs to adapt to previously unseen changes (new products, new machinery, new handlers) that affect the observations (Strategy #9: Continual DL)
- Sensor data will be read at real time and runtime inference capabilities are expected to be required (Strategy #10)
- There is a great variety of available data sources (as can be seen in C) that will be used to achieve the scenarios' goals. To manage and utilize this diverse data effectively, a mechanism will be developed in T5.1 to collect and aggregate it.
- The duration of the periods for which the model will estimate the energy consumption is unknown and it is to be defined by the user.
- Unclear whether one or more models are required for identifying patterns in historical data and correlating current conditions and production plans with consumption.
- Unclear how consumption patterns can contribute to the prediction or whether the production plans are so dominant that nothing else is needed. Strategy #5 will help determine the most critical data features, optimizing the model’s performance and ensuring it focuses on the factors that influence energy consumption.

C. Data Requirements

Available data:

- ERP data
- fault/status-related data, human entered data, coarse-grained.
- sensor data, fine granularity
- analytical data
- energy consumption data
- production plans

Available data sources:

- Plant’s Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system
- Manufacturing Execution System (MES) (fault/status-related data, human entered data, coarse-grained)
- Energy Monitoring System
- Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) system
- PLC analyser (sensor data, fine granularity)
- advanced reporting tools
- production plan logs

D. User Requirements

	ID	UR Description	Priority
	UR1	PANDORA framework provides accurate and timely predictions,	Sha

What are the requirements with respect to the PANDORA framework for the specific scenario?		within specified error margins, across various time frames (e.g., next hour, day, etc.), with results generated in real-time or within a few seconds.	II
	UR2	PANDORA framework provides an easy-to-use interface for users to define prediction windows, production plans, and other relevant parameters efficiently	Should
	UR3	PANDORA framework is able to generate predictions quickly, ideally within seconds, to support dynamic decision-making	Should
	UR4	PANDORA framework provides detailed reports that include predicted energy consumption, variance from typical consumption, and confidence intervals	Should
	UR5	PANDORA framework is able to automatically generate alerts for unusual, predicted energy usage, enabling proactive management actions	May
	UR6	PANDORA framework allows users to define parameters such as production shifts, machine settings, and operational constraints that may impact energy consumption	Should
	UR7	PANDORA framework provides a mechanism for users to give feedback on the system's predictions and usability.	Should
	UR8	PANDORA framework is able to create benchmarks for optimal energy performance and generate automated alerts for significant deviations, failures, or anomalies	Should
	UR9	PANDORA framework is able to identify and prioritize the most relevant features and data sources that contribute to accurate energy consumption predictions, reducing data processing time and enhancing model explainability	May

E. Evaluation

KPI id	Benchmark	KPI target value	Monitoring Period	Responsible Partner
KPI1.1.2		Number of models trained ≥ 10)		SAG
KPI1.2.1		Increase accuracy of uncertainty prediction by 15%		DLR
KPI1.2.2		Deployment of at least one tool on uncertainty quantification for an energy efficiency problem)		DLR
KPI2.4.1		Improved quality of the understandability related output that supports the tracing of the domain-informed AI decisions $>20\%$).		CYU
KPI3.1.1		Observed energy efficiency saved costs increase by 15%		UNSPMF
KPI4.1.1		Number of scenario variations defined per domain ≥ 2		AEGIS

KPI5.1.1		Number of industrial sectors reached >=5		DIE, STS
KPI1.5.2		Decrease in data redundancy (Dimensionality reduction) >= 50 %		ITML
KPI1.5.1		Number of models trained >= 3		ITML

4.4 PANDORA strategies mapping

After developing the AIoT trial scenarios for each use case, we mapped the strategic involvement in each scenario, as summarized in **Table 13**. This step forms part of the validation activity and represents the final phase of the workflow outlined in Section 4.2.3, ensuring that the technical partners are both capable and interested in deploying their individual technologies within each scenario. This outcome resulted from an iterative process, including in-person meetings, bilateral discussions, and workshops, where numerous technical and operational concerns were addressed to finalize the technology deployment plan. Additionally, it is important to emphasize that the architecture definition (T2.4) task leaders and technical contributors provided essential support in the creation of this table.

Table 13: Mapping strategies with scenarios

PANDORA Strategies	Short Description	Tasks	Components	UC1 S1	UC1 S2	UC2 S1	UC2 S2	UC3 S1	UC3 S2	UC4 S1	UC4 S2	UC5 S1	UC5 S2	PANDORA Strategies
Strategy 1	ML-enabled scalable synthetic data generation	T3.1	SDG	x	x	x	x	x	x			x		Strategy 1
Strategy 2	Novel approach to AI-based uncertainty quantification modelling and development	T3.2	QU-MAD	x				x	x	x	x	x		Strategy 2
Strategy 3	Leveraging domain knowledge for explainable learning	T3.3	DEL	x			x			x	x	x		Strategy 3
Strategy 4	(Semi-)automated annotations, labelling, and self-supervised completion and augmentation	T3.4	DACL			x	x	x	x	x		x	x	Strategy 4
Strategy 5	Data summarization, dimensionality reduction, and fusion	T3.5	DRFE	x	x					x		x	x	Strategy 5
Strategy 6	Offline verification and validation (V&V) of the overall complete dataset	T6.3	V&V	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Strategy 6
Strategy 7	Self-validated, causal, robust, and resilient continuous learning for an increased degree of long-	T4.1	CRV	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x		Strategy 7

	term autonomy and intelligence.													
Strategy 8	Federated Representation Learning (FRL) of compact representations to minimize the data needs and manipulations	T4.3	FRLM	x	x	x								Strategy 8
Strategy 9	Domain-informed, causal and explainable AI-based on a hybrid learning-reasoning approach to achieve multiple ways of continuous learning	T4.2	DICE	x			x			x		x		Strategy 9
Strategy 10	Continual Inference Networks to speed up the inference of DL models	T4.4	CIM	x	x			x	x			x	x	Strategy 10
Strategy 11	Adaptive distribution and optimization of AI inference in the cloud-edge computing continuum	T4.5	ADOA	x	x	x	x							Strategy 11

4.5 Industrial requirements mapping

The following section outlines the consolidated industrial requirements that have been collaboratively developed through a co-creation approach with the technical providers. This process has enabled a thorough integration of end-user perspectives into the requirements. The **Table 14-Table 18** serve as a guide for technology development within each Use Case (UC), pinpointing the specific needs and prioritized requirements of end-users. These requirements represent the anticipated functionalities of the PANDORA framework as envisioned by end-users, reflecting their expectations for performance, usability, and technical capabilities. By aligning the framework's design with these requirements, the project aims to ensure that the PANDORA framework delivers targeted, high-impact solutions that address real-world industrial challenges and optimize user satisfaction.

Table 14: SAG URs -Predictive edge in production cells

ID	Requirement	Scenario	Priority
UR1	PANDORA framework produces synthetic data based on a simulated environment to train AI models	S1, S2	Shall
UR2	PANDORA framework provides an AI model to predict network outages and critical situations	S1, S2	Shall

UR3	PANDORA framework outputs explanations as well as uncertainty assessments alongside predictions	S1	May
UR4	PANDORA framework is able to support the distributed / federated learning of the AI model as well as its inference	S1, S2	Should
UR5	PANDORA framework can gather and process data from various sources to ensure that the necessary information is available for training and evaluating AI models	S1, S2	May
UR6	PANDORA framework can use methods to identify and keep only the most important data information, which helps improve the accuracy, understanding, and efficiency of AI models	S1, S2	Should

Table 15: EAB URs -5G enabled Smart Building

ID	Requirement	Scenario	Priority
UR7	PANDORA framework is able to generalize datasets across new terrains and/or obstacles	S1	Should
UR8	PANDORA framework can generate synthetic datasets with the necessary semantic information	S1	Should
UR9	PANDORA framework provides verification that the generated dataset for robot navigation reflects realistic scenarios	S1	Shall
UR10	PANDORA framework is able to use the validated dataset for obstacle avoidance and/or planning purposes	S1	Shall
UR11	PANDORA framework utilizes a federation of robots to detect anomalous behavior or intent issues	S1	Shall
UR12	PANDORA framework is able to generate missing data and annotations on the raw dataset	S1	May

UR13	PANDORA framework deploys the models using split or distributed computing topologies for efficiency	S1	May
UR14	The system must implement access control mechanisms to verify and authenticate users (actors) before granting access to PANDORA's resources.	S1, S2	Should
UR15	PANDORA framework is able to employ synthetic datasets that capture variations in multiple factors (such as obstacles, antenna position)	S2	Should
UR16	PANDORA framework can verify the validity of the synthetic dataset that are aimed to capture variations caused by multiple factors (such as obstacles, antenna position)	S2	Shall
UR17	PANDORA framework provides accurate predictions for possible deviations in 5G throughput and latency	S2	Shall
UR18	PANDORA framework is able to incorporate predictions into models that guide autonomous actions over the 5G network	S2	Should
UR19	PANDORA framework is able to provide intuitive explanations for AI-based autonomous decisions	S2	Shall
UR20	PANDORA framework is able to generate missing data and annotations on the raw dataset	S2	May

Table 16: PCL URs - Predictive Edge Applications in Production

ID	Requirement	Scenario	Priority
UR21	PANDORA framework provides a scalable and flexible image creation process to produce synthetic data	S1, S2	Shall
UR22	PANDORA framework requires as input a limited sample of a X<50 images captured from a physical camera setup (demonstrator) to generate an accurate synthetic dataset (S1) Difference with scenario1 is that these images will be from another graphical design (so in this case the Adriatic blue chest, while synthetic images from the champagne gold chest have to be created) (S2)	S1, S2	Shall

UR23	PANDORA framework generates images that contain all failure types as provided by the Phillips team	S1, S2	May
UR24	PANDORA framework provides annotated synthetic image datasets	S1, S2	Should
UR25	PANDORA framework provides models that can handle multiple background colors and graphic print designs	S1, S2	Shall
UR26	PANDORA framework will give insight into the defect types of real images (which can be used for making a pareto)	S1	May
UR27	PANDORA framework can be supported by Philips (for example, Python source code)	S1, S2	Should
UR28	PANDORA framework is able to generate synthetic image data based on CAD drawings/3D models	S2	Shall

Table 17: FRA URs - AI driven Operations in Critical Hydrogen Infrastructures

ID	Requirement	Scenario	Priority
UR30	PANDORA framework detects operational anomalies in HRS components early using time series data and error logs	S1	Shall
UR31	PANDORA framework is able to predict potential component failures or shutdowns in advance to enhance safety and reliability	S1	Shall
UR32	PANDORA framework is able to identify anomalies with an accuracy of 80%	S1	Shall
UR33	PANDORA framework will provide metrics to evaluate performance against KPIs, including anomaly detection and prediction accuracy	S1	Shall
UR34	PANDORA framework would facilitate anomaly detection by providing contextual data for experts to address and confirm identified anomalies	S1	Shall
UR35	PANDORA framework helps ensure the model provides explainable outputs, allowing users to	S1	Should

	understand the rationale behind anomaly detection and predictions		
UR36	PANDORA framework will be retrained periodically using updated datasets acquired ensuring continuous improvement in detection accuracy and robustness	S2	Shall
UR37	PANDORA framework allows domain experts to validate detected anomalies and integrate their feedback in the model	S2	Shall
UR38	PANDORA framework provides a functional element of reducing false positives by refining the anomaly detection model based on experts' insight	S2	Shall
UR39	PANDORA framework continuously monitors and report on key performance metrics, such as anomaly detection accuracy and false positive rates, to track and guide model improvements	S2	Shall
UR40	PANDORA framework automatically schedules and execute model retraining at defined intervals or when performance metrics indicate the need for improvement	S2	Should

Table 18: HALCOR URs - Manufacturing AIoT Sensing Infrastructures

ID	Requirement	Scenario	Priority
UR41	PANDORA framework provides accurate and timely predictions, within specified error margins, across various time frames (e.g., next hour, day, etc.), with results generated in real-time or within a few seconds.	S1, S2	Shall
UR42	PANDORA framework provides that models remain reliable over different time frames and operational conditions, and its algorithms shall be updated regularly to reflect changes in operations and environment	S1	Shall
UR43	PANDORA framework provides an easy to navigate user interface with a feedback mechanism on input data validity, and report prediction processing status	S1	Should
UR44	PANDORA framework provides an analysis of reasons for deviations in energy consumption predictions, highlighting factors that contribute to unexpected variations and supporting users in understanding prediction outcomes.	S1	Should
UR45	PANDORA framework provides a mechanism for users to give feedback on the system's predictions and usability.	S1	Should

UR46	PANDORA framework provides real-time monitoring of the press’s consumption, displaying current data and trends	S2	Should
UR47	PANDORA framework is able to create benchmarks for optimal energy performance and generate automated alerts for significant deviations, failures, or anomalies	S1	Should
UR48	PANDORA framework is able to identify and prioritize the most relevant features and data sources that contribute to accurate energy consumption predictions, reducing data processing time and enhancing model explainability	S1, S2	May
UR49	PANDORA framework provides an easy-to-use interface for users to define prediction windows, production plans, and other relevant parameters efficiently	S2	Should
UR50	PANDORA framework is able to generate predictions quickly, ideally within seconds, to support dynamic decision-making	S2	Shall
UR51	PANDORA framework provides detailed reports that include predicted energy consumption, variance from typical consumption, and confidence intervals	S2	Shall
UR52	PANDORA framework is able to Automatically generate alerts for unusual, predicted energy usage, enabling proactive management actions	S2	May
UR53	PANDORA framework allows users to define parameters such as production shifts, machine settings, and operational constraints that may impact energy consumption	S2	Shall

5. The PANDORA experimentation process

5.1 Experimentation Lifecycle

This section outlines the experimentation process for our project, detailing the structured phases that guide the iterative and incremental approach to defining, executing, and analyzing experiments. The PANDORA experimentation process follows the basic steps that must be performed in any empirical study [6]. This lifecycle ensures that all experimental activities align with project goals and stakeholder expectations, enabling systematic verification and validation of the developed solutions.

The experimentation lifecycle, presented in **Figure 29**, consists of four main phases:

- **Scoping:** This initial phase focuses on defining the scope and objectives of each experiment. Using a design verification template and a design validation template, we establish the boundaries, goals, and context for experimentation. During this phase, we identify the primary questions to address, the anticipated outcomes, and the key metrics for success. Scoping also includes defining the technological and business requirements that will shape the experimental design.
- **Planning:** In the planning phase, we refine the experimental setup by specifying the experimental design, including the detailed definition of experiments, identification of participants, and the methods for conducting the experiments. This phase outlines both the logistical and technical requirements for execution, covering aspects such as roles, responsibilities, and expected resources. Planning ensures that each experiment is well-prepared and structured to provide reliable, actionable data.
- **Execution:** This phase involves the actual implementation of the experiments based on the defined plans. Execution focuses on performing both validation and verification activities to assess the technology against project requirements and stakeholder needs. Verification activities check the technical performance, while validation activities ensure the solutions align with business objectives and user needs. This step involves close collaboration between technical experts and stakeholders to capture comprehensive data for further analysis.
- **Analysis:** The final phase is centered on analyzing the results obtained from the execution phase. This includes visualizing data to highlight key findings, interpreting the outcomes, and assessing their implications for project objectives. Analysis helps identify areas for improvement and refines the understanding of both technical and business value. The insights gained in this phase guide iterative improvements, leading to enhanced experimentation in subsequent cycles.

The experimentation process is designed to be iterative and incremental, allowing for continuous refinement and alignment with evolving project requirements. This adaptive approach includes two definition phases (scoping and planning) and two operational phases (execution and analysis), ensuring that experiments remain relevant as project definitions and requirements evolve. By balancing verification (technical performance) and validation (business alignment), this process addresses the comprehensive needs of all stakeholders, creating a robust foundation for impactful experimentation results.

Figure 29: The PANDORA experimentation process

5.1.1 Scoping

The scoping phase serves as the foundation of the experimentation lifecycle, guiding the initial focus on defining the verification and validation objectives. The aim of this phase is to establish a clear understanding of what the experiments are intended to measure and why these measurements are essential for the project's goals. By clarifying the scope, we ensure that each experimental activity has a well-defined purpose, aligned with both the technological ambitions and business objectives of the project.

To initiate this process, scoping begins with identifying the key objectives and questions that the experimentation process seeks to address. This step involves understanding the overarching goals of the project, the critical attributes of the platform or components under evaluation, and the stakeholder expectations surrounding these goals. By pinpointing these elements early on, we set the parameters for all subsequent experimentation phases and establish a shared vision for the desired outcomes.

In addition to defining objectives, this phase differentiates between two primary focuses: verification and validation. Verification addresses the technical quality of the solution, examining how closely the platform's components align with specified technical standards, performance criteria, and quality benchmarks. The purpose of verification is to ensure that the technology meets predefined technical specifications and functions as expected from an engineering standpoint. Validation, on the other hand, concentrates on how well the solution meets business needs and aligns with user requirements. It involves assessing whether the platform's features and functionalities effectively support business objectives and provide tangible value to end-users. Validation thus emphasizes user satisfaction, compliance with regulatory standards, and alignment with the project's high-level goals.

Scoping also involves setting the key metrics and success indicators for both verification and validation. These elements help define the baseline against which future measurements will be evaluated, providing a structured framework to assess the technology's performance over time. This phase includes determining the expected outcomes and acceptable tolerance levels for each metric, thus creating measurable targets that clarify the project's expectations. By establishing these targets upfront, the scoping phase enables the experimentation process to be both focused and adaptable, allowing for adjustments as project needs evolve.

Moreover, scoping includes the identification of technological and business requirements that will shape the experimental design. This involves recognizing the variables and dependencies within the system, understanding the factors that may influence performance, and considering the broader ecosystem in which the technology will operate. Recognizing these contextual elements ensures that the experiments account for relevant real-world conditions, thus enhancing the validity of the results.

In summary, scoping provides a structured approach to systematically assess what the project aims to achieve through verification and validation, laying the groundwork for a comprehensive, goal-oriented experimentation process. This phase ensures that all stakeholders are aligned in their understanding of the experimentation objectives and that there is a clear roadmap for the subsequent phases of planning, execution, and analysis.

Verification template

This section provides a template to systematically assess the quality of PANDORA's components by defining verification variables, relevant metrics, baseline values, and expected results aligned with project key results and KPIs. The verification template is a structured framework designed to evaluate the performance of technology components, ensuring that they meet defined metrics and contribute effectively to the project's goals. An objective of the verification template is to enable technology providers to monitor, refine and adjust the verification criteria that will be utilized to assess their contributions. By defining specific variables and applicable metrics, stakeholders can establish a clear baseline from which actual performance can be measured. The resulting templates will serve as questionnaires during the execution phases to collect and record actual measurements, facilitating a thorough evaluation of the technology's effectiveness. The verification template is presented in **Table 19** and seeks to answer the following main questions:

- What are the specific verification variables that will determine the quality of each component?
- How do these components align with the key results defined for the project?
- What metrics will be used to quantify the performance of each technology component?
- What are the baseline values for these metrics, and what expected results should we anticipate upon implementation?

Table 19: PANDORA verification template

PANDORA Strategies	Components	KPI id	Verification variable	Metric	Baseline Value	Expected Results	Verification Timeline	Actual Results	Risk/Challenge Identified	Follow-up Actions
Synthetic data generation (Strategy 1)	Synthetic data generation for time-series data (tSDG)	KPI2.2.1								
	Synthetic data generation for vision data (vSDG)	KPI2.2.2								
		KPI2.2.3								
Uncertainty quantification (Strategy 2)	Uncertainty quantification modelling and development (QU-MAD)	KPI1.2.1								
		KPI1.2.2								
Explainable Domain-	Leveraging domain	KPI2.1.1								
		KPI2.1.2								

informed modeling (Strategy 3)	knowledge for explainable learning (DEL)	KPI2.4.1								
Semi-automated annotations (Strategy 4)	Semi-automated annotations, labelling and self-supervised completion and augmentation (DAEL)	KPI1.3.1								
		KPI1.3.2								
		KPI1.3.3								
Data summarisation (Strategy 5)	Dimensionality Reduction and Feature Extraction Component (DRFEC)	KPI1.4.1								
		KPI1.5.1								
Verification & Validation (Strategy 6)	Verification and Validation (V&V)	KPI1.5.2								
		KPI3.3.1								
Robust and resilient learning (Strategy 7)	Self-validated, causal, robust, and resilient continuous learning for long-term autonomy and intelligence (CRV)	KPI3.3.2								
		KPI3.1.1								
		KPI3.1.2								
Parallel, Distributed & Federated representational learning (Strategy 8)	Federated Representational Learning (FRL) of compact representations to minimize the data needs and manipulations (FRLM)	KPI3.1.3								
		KPI1.1.1								
		KPI1.1.2								
Continuous, explainable and domain-informed AI (Strategy 9)	Domain-informed, causal and explainable AI based on a hybrid learning-reasoning approach for continuous learning (DICE)	KPI2.3.1								
		KPI2.3.2								
Continual Deep Learning (Strategy 10)	Continual Inference Networks to speed up the inference of DL models (CIM)	KPI2.4.1								
Split Deep Learning (Strategy 11)	Adaptive distribution and optimization of AI inferencing in the cloud-edge computing	KPI3.1.3								
		KPI2.4.1								

	continuum (ADOA)									
N/A	User Authentication (UA)	KPI3.2.1								
		KPI3.2.2								
N/A	AI as a Service (AlaaS)	KPI3.1.3								
N/A	Computing as a Service (CaaS)	KPI3.1.3								
N/A	Intent Manager (IM)	KPI3.1.3								

The verification template consists of several attributes designed to assess the effectiveness of PANDORA’s technology components and their alignment with the project’s strategic objectives. To start, PANDORA Strategies refer to the strategies developed within the project, outlining the overarching goals that guide the evaluation of various components. Meanwhile, Components represent the identified architectural elements that contribute to the project’s success. More details about PANDORA Strategies and technology Components can be found in D2.2 [1]. Some strategies consist of more than one component. To ensure accountability and effective implementation, the Responsible Partner attribute identifies the organization tasked with monitoring or verifying the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

Complementing this, the Related Tasks attribute specifies the particular tasks outlined in the PANDORA work plan that are directly related to the KPIs, providing clarity on the actions necessary to achieve project goals. In terms of performance measurement, the KPI id indicates the specific Key Performance Indicators used to evaluate the success of the applied strategies and technology components. Each KPI is further defined to clarify its purpose and relevance, with each KPI mapped to a specific Key Result (KR id, KR definition) and the project’s Enablers.

In addition, the Verification Variable identifies the specific variable used to verify the effectiveness of the PANDORA strategies, while the Metric provides a quantifiable measure mapped to these verification variables, enabling a structured evaluation process. To establish benchmarks, the Baseline Value serves as the starting point for comparison, showing the initial state of the metric before the implementation of the PANDORA strategies. The Expected Results attribute then articulates the anticipated outcomes for each metric following these strategies, outlining the improvements stakeholders aim to achieve.

Additionally, the Verification Timeline indicates the specific time period during which the verification activities are planned, aligning with project deliverables and action points (e.g., "Q2 2024," "Q3 2024"). The Actual Results attribute captures the quantifiable outcomes after implementing the PANDORA strategies, providing insights into the effectiveness of the technology components and informing any necessary adjustments or follow-up actions.

Finally, the Risk/Challenge Identified attribute highlights potential obstacles that could impact the success of the project, allowing stakeholders to proactively address these issues. The Follow-up Actions attribute outlines specific measures that will be taken to mitigate identified risks and ensure the continuous improvement of the project’s processes and outcomes. Note that certain attributes, namely Responsible Partner, Related Task, Enabler, KR ID, and KR Definition, are intentionally hidden in **Table 19** to save space. These columns can be found in the Annex of the document.

Validation template

This section outlines a template for evaluating the impact of PANDORA's platform on business objectives and compliance standards, focusing on user-oriented quality indicators and relevant metrics to validate performance and alignment with key project outcomes. The validation template serves as a systematic approach to assess how effectively the implemented solutions contribute to achieving business goals and meeting compliance requirements. By defining clear validation

variables and metrics, stakeholders can measure the actual performance against established expectations, thus ensuring accountability and transparency in evaluating the project’s success.

The validation template seeks to answer the following main questions:

- What specific scenarios will be used to evaluate the use case?
- Which validation variables will guide the assessment of each use case?
- What metrics are used to measure performance, and what baseline values are associated with them?
- What are the expected and actual outcomes following the application of PANDORA’s platform?
- How do these outcomes align with key results, and what additional insights or remarks should be documented?

The validation template, presented in **Table 20**, consists of several essential attributes designed to facilitate a comprehensive evaluation of PANDORA’s impact on the business objectives and compliance standards. This template will be used for each pilot UCs. Scenario identifies the specific situation or condition under which the use case is applied. The Validation Variable outlines the variable used to validate the PANDORA framework within a use case, ensuring a consistent approach to evaluation. In PANDORA, the validation variable can be captured as a Business KPI, during the Preparation of trustworthy datasets phase (design phase), or during the Autonomous and continuous AIoT operations phase (operation phase). The Metric specifies the quantitative measures used to evaluate the validation variable. The Baseline Value denotes the initial results achieved, serving as a comparative point prior to PANDORA’s implementation. Expected Results express the anticipated outcomes based on these metrics, establishing clear targets that stakeholders aim to meet. Meanwhile, Actual Results provide a record of the actual outcomes achieved, showing how the technology performed in practice. To align outcomes with project goals, Key Results (KRs) detail the specific objectives associated with each validation variable. Finally, the Notes/Comments section allows for observations, remarks, or additional context related to each validation metric, enabling stakeholders to document relevant insights such as issues encountered, unexpected outcomes, or follow-up actions.

Table 20: PANDORA validation template

Scenario	Validation variable	Metric	Baseline Value	Expected Results	Actual Results	KRs	Notes Comments
	Business KPIs						
	Preparation of trustworthy datasets						
	Autonomous and continuous AIoT operations						

5.1.2 Planning

The planning phase in the experimentation lifecycle translates the foundational objectives identified during scoping into a detailed, actionable experiment design. This phase defines the

structure and methodology that will drive the subsequent execution of experiments, establishing a framework for consistent, reliable data collection and analysis. Through precise planning, we ensure that experiments are both feasible and capable of delivering insights that align with PANDORA's overarching verification and validation objectives.

Planning begins with specifying the exact scope of each experiment, including the experimental design, objectives, and outcomes targeted for evaluation. This process involves creating detailed experiment definitions that clarify the variables to be tested, the hypotheses to be explored, and the specific technology components to be evaluated. Each experiment is crafted to probe critical questions surrounding the project's goals, ensuring that it provides valuable data that aligns with both technical and business objectives. In addition, planning involves identifying the factors that may affect experimental outcomes, such as environmental variables, dependencies within the technology stack, and specific requirements that reflect real-world conditions.

This phase also establishes the participants and roles necessary to execute the planned experiments. By determining who will be involved—whether technical experts, business stakeholders, or end-users—we ensure that experiments are enriched with diverse perspectives and insights. Additionally, each participant's role is clarified to foster accountability, streamline communication, and enhance collaboration. For each experiment, this phase identifies key stakeholders responsible for overseeing and validating experiment results, as well as team members responsible for data collection, documentation, and reporting.

Beyond the “who,” planning addresses the “how” by detailing the methods that will govern experiment execution. This includes identifying the tools, technologies, and methodologies required for consistent, repeatable experiments, such as data-gathering tools, sensors, and frameworks for qualitative and quantitative analysis. By establishing clear procedures for data collection and ensuring the fidelity of measurements, we create a solid foundation for reliable results. This level of detail helps avoid inconsistencies and ensures that each experiment adheres to a rigorous standard, providing data that can be trusted and traced throughout the lifecycle.

Importantly, the planning phase aligns each experiment with the objectives identified during scoping, refining the vision established earlier to ensure that it is operationally viable. As an integral part of the verification and validation (V&V) design, planning observations contribute directly to the refinement of V&V criteria. Any insights gained during planning can prompt adjustments in experiment design, highlighting additional metrics or validation variables that should be included to strengthen the overall evaluation framework. This process also encompasses risk management, anticipating potential challenges that could arise during execution and planning mitigating strategies to address them proactively.

Ultimately, the planning phase is where the theoretical foundations of experimentation take shape as structured, executable plans. By detailing the design, participants, and execution methods for each experiment, this phase ensures that each experiment can be conducted effectively, yielding meaningful data that will contribute to the iterative process of verification, validation, and improvement. This careful planning bridges the scoping and execution phases, setting the stage for a smooth and productive experimental process aligned with PANDORA's goals.

5.1.3 Execution

The execution phase in the experimentation lifecycle is where carefully designed and planned experiments come to life. This stage involves the active implementation of each experiment, using the structure and methodologies established in the definition phases (scoping, planning). Execution provides the empirical foundation for understanding the PANDORA platform's performance, testing the validity of predefined hypotheses, and gathering measurable insights on how well the system meets its technical and business objectives.

During execution, each experiment is conducted according to the specific criteria outlined in the definition phases. To this end, execution involves close coordination among the identified participants, who bring diverse roles and expertise, from technical validation specialists and data engineers to business stakeholders. These roles collaborate to ensure that experiments are run consistently across environments, capturing the complex dynamics of PANDORA's components in real-world conditions.

The execution phase also involves the real-time monitoring of variables and parameters relevant to each experiment, which is essential for gathering consistent and actionable data. Throughout this stage, both verification and validation activities are undertaken, each with a unique focus. Verification activities concentrate on assessing the technical performance of the platform's components, examining their efficiency, resilience, and compliance with the defined metrics. By contrast, validation activities target the alignment of the technology with user needs and business objectives, focusing on elements like user experience, satisfaction. This dual focus allows for a holistic assessment of the PANDORA platform, addressing both its technical integrity and its value to end-users.

Data capture and documentation are critical components of execution, as they create the primary resource for the subsequent analysis phase. Detailed logs of each experiment, including setup conditions, outcomes, and observed anomalies, provide a comprehensive record that can be revisited and referenced throughout the lifecycle. Additionally, this phase includes on-the-ground adjustments, where minor recalibrations may be made to address unforeseen issues while preserving the integrity of the experiment. These controlled adaptations enable flexibility without compromising the robustness of the collected data.

To maintain accountability and quality control, execution includes checkpoints and reviews at key intervals, where preliminary data is examined for accuracy and adherence to expected conditions. These checkpoints allow for early detection of any deviations from the experiment plan, enabling corrective actions that maintain the experiment's validity. In cases where experiments encounter technical challenges, such as hardware malfunctions or unexpected environmental changes, corrective protocols established during the planning phase are deployed to mitigate the impact on data integrity.

The execution phase is inherently iterative, with data collection cycles that may be repeated to verify initial findings or to deepen understanding of complex interactions within the system. This iterative approach supports a dynamic exploration of PANDORA's capabilities, providing stakeholders with a comprehensive understanding of both expected and unforeseen outcomes.

In summary, the execution phase translates theoretical plans into tangible results, systematically collecting data that will drive the analytical insights necessary for project refinement. This phase ensures that every aspect of experimentation is carefully managed, yielding trustworthy data that reflects the true capabilities and impact of the PANDORA platform. By rigorously adhering to planned methodologies and addressing any deviations with precision, the execution phase lays a strong groundwork for an effective and insightful analysis.

5.1.4 Analysis

The analysis phase is the final and essential step in the experimentation lifecycle, where the collected data is transformed into actionable insights. In this phase, experimental results are systematically interpreted and evaluated, revealing how effectively the PANDORA platform meets its technological and business objectives. Analysis serves not only to validate initial hypotheses but also to provide a comprehensive understanding of both anticipated and unexpected findings, offering a solid foundation for decision-making and continuous improvement.

Data interpretation in the analysis phase is guided by the metrics and benchmarks defined in the scoping and planning stages. By aligning actual results with expected outcomes, this step enables

an objective assessment of the platform's performance. Through statistical analyses, performance trends, and comparative assessments against baseline values, stakeholders gain a nuanced view of the platform's strengths and areas that may require refinement.

Beyond raw performance metrics, the analysis phase also focuses on understanding the broader implications of the findings. This includes evaluating the platform's impact on business goals, such as cost efficiency, or user satisfaction, thereby bridging the gap between technical validation and real-world relevance. In cases where experimental results diverge from initial expectations, the analysis delves into potential causal factors, such as environmental variables, user interaction patterns, or technological constraints. Such insights contribute to a richer understanding of the conditions under which the platform operates most effectively, highlighting any constraints or limitations that may impact its scalability or adaptability.

Equally critical in this phase is the collaborative review of findings with stakeholders, who bring diverse perspectives and expertise. This dialogue ensures that results are contextualized within the project's overarching goals and operational requirements. By engaging technical experts, business analysts, and end-users in the review process, the analysis phase fosters a shared understanding of the platform's performance, potential trade-offs, and the implications of various findings for future project phases. Such collaborative interpretation of results often brings new insights, as stakeholders may identify secondary benefits or unintended consequences that warrant further exploration.

The analysis phase also involves documenting findings comprehensively, creating a structured report that captures both quantitative results and qualitative insights. This report serves as an official record of the experiment's outcomes, detailing the methods used, observed performance against each benchmark, and a summary of the lessons learned. This documentation not only facilitates transparency but also provides a reference for refining future experimental cycles. By identifying patterns and trends in the data, the analysis phase informs strategic adjustments to subsequent experiments, ensuring that each iteration builds upon previous learnings and optimizes the platform's evolution.

Ultimately, the analysis phase transforms data into meaningful conclusions, guiding stakeholders toward a consensus on the platform's effectiveness and areas for enhancement. This final phase validates the platform's contributions to project objectives, supports evidence-based decision-making, and paves the way for ongoing improvement. By systematically evaluating the outcomes of experimentation and engaging stakeholders in the interpretation process, analysis completes the experimentation lifecycle, reinforcing the project's commitment to accountability, transparency, and impact.

6. Verification and validation (V&V) strategy of PANDORA

6.1 Verification variables of PANDORA strategies

This section presents the verification variables for each component of the PANDORA platform, aiming to systematically assess the quality and performance of these components through the use of a standardized verification template. **Figure 30** and **Figure 31** present a high-level architecture of PANDORA during Phase I (design) and Phase II (operation), respectively, summarizing all technical components involved. Both figures originate from D2.2 [1], where additional technical details are provided. Following the structure outlined in Section 5.1.1, the verification template provides a consistent framework to evaluate PANDORA’s technical components. The initial focus is on identifying relevant quality variables for each component, alongside preliminary metrics and baseline values, to establish a foundation for assessing each technology’s performance and effectiveness in meeting PANDORA’s overall objectives.

The verification template, presented in Section 5.1.1, captures the current understanding of each component’s quality variables and associated metrics, offering a structured basis for monitoring, assessment, and continuous improvement. As experimentation progresses, these initial values will serve as reference points, facilitating an evidence-based approach to evaluate and refine the PANDORA platform. In the current document an example of a prefilled verification template is presented in **Table 21**, evaluating the “Synthetic data generation for vision data” component. Note that this is an indicative entry and may be modified during the operation phase.

It is worth noting that while these templates aim to capture key aspects of each component’s quality, some elements may remain provisional. Specifically, metrics, baseline values, and benchmarks will undergo further refinement as additional data is gathered in subsequent experimentation phases. This iterative approach ensures that verification remains adaptable and responsive to evolving project requirements, allowing stakeholders to capture an increasingly precise picture of each component’s contribution to the platform’s success.

Figure 30: PANDORA high-level architecture (Phase I) [1]

Figure 31: PANDORA high-level architecture (Phase II) [1]

PANDORA Strategies	Components	KPI id	Verification variable	Metric	Baseline Value	Expected Results	Verification Timeliness	Actual Results	Risk/Challenge Identified	Follow-up Actions
Synthetic data generation (Strategy 1)	Synthetic data generation for time-series data (tSDG)	KPI2.2.1								
	Synthetic data generation for vision data (vSDG)	KPI2.2.2	Performance	Experiment runtime	2s	2s-20%	TBC	TBC	TBC	TBC
		KPI2.2.3								

Table 21: Verification variable indicative example

6.2 Validation variables of PANDORA strategies

This section details the validation variables selected to assess the impact and effectiveness of PANDORA’s technologies across five distinct use cases (UCs). Each use case is evaluated through the standardized validation template outlined in Section 5.1.1, offering a structured approach to gauge how effectively PANDORA’s solutions meet key business requirements and objectives. The validation process includes five UCs—SAG, EAB, PCL, FRA, and HALCOR—each with its unique set of validation variables. These variables are categorized into three areas: Business KPIs, Preparation of Trustworthy Datasets (representing PANDORA’s design phase), and Autonomous and Continuous AIoT Operations (aligned with PANDORA’s operational phase). This comprehensive assessment framework is specifically tailored to the objectives of each UC, with variables selected directly by users and derived from the scenario templates in Section 0. The tables that follow present the associated metrics, baseline values, and relevant benchmarks, establishing a foundation for ongoing evaluation and refinement. Since we are at an early stage of the project, the level of detail provided in each table varies, as many validation variables have not yet been identified by the end users. As the project progresses and approaches the validation phase, the templates will be systematically enriched and refined.

6.2.1 SAG UC Validation Overview

The validation process of the PANDORA solution in the SAG use case is summarized in the following validation table. This table will guide the assessment, be progressively completed, and serve as a monitoring tool. Any comments and identified risks can be documented here throughout the experimentation process.

Table 22: SAG UC Validation Overview

Scenario	Validation variable	Metric	Baseline Value	Expected Results	Actual Results	KRs	Notes Comments
Scenario 1: Delay too High, Scenario 2: Cycle Times too High	Business KPIs						
	Realistic Failure Event Representation	Similarity score	Current dataset realism				Ensure data covers all failure scenarios
	Model Accuracy	Prediction accuracy		>= 90% accuracy in failure prediction			Accuracy based on real-world testing and validation data.
Scenario 1: Delay too High, Scenario 2: Cycle Times too High	Preparation of trustworthy datasets						
	High-quality data availability	Percentage of missing data		Missing data < Baseline Value, ensuring data quality			Aim for minimal missing data for accurate model training
	Dataset Representation	Dataset completeness		Coverage of all major infrastructure failure types			Ensure dataset represents typical and critical failures
	Data Format Standardization	Format type		All data in standardized format			For easy integration and analysis
Scenario 2: Cycle Times too High	Historical Data Coverage	Time Period Coverage		Data should cover all seasons and usage patterns (daily, weekly, monthly)			Capture variations in usage patterns and trends.
	Peak Usage Prediction Accuracy	Prediction accuracy		>= of Baseline Value			Supports proactive load balancing strategies.
	Load Balancing Readiness	Load Balance Efficiency					Validation of load balancing strategies.
Scenario 1: Delay too High	Autonomous and continuous AIoT operations						
	Failure Prediction Accuracy	Prediction Accuracy		>= of Baseline Value			Ensures model reliability in failure prediction.

Scenario 2: Cycle Times too High	System Response Time	Average Response Time			Ensures that the system can respond quickly, even under high load.
Scenario 2: Cycle Times too High	Operational Efficiency During Peak Times	Efficiency Rate	Baseline efficiency	≥ 80% efficiency during peak times	Measures the operational efficiency during peak usage, ensuring minimal drop.
Scenario 1: Delay too High	Failure Prediction Accuracy	Prediction Accuracy		≥ of Baseline Value	Ensures model reliability in failure prediction.

6.2.2 EAB UC Validation Overview

The validation process of the PANDORA solution in the EAB use case is summarized in the following validation table. It will be referenced, further filled out, and used as a continuous monitoring tool, with space for comments and risk tracking throughout the experimentation phase.

Table 23: EAB UC Validation Overview

Scenario	Validation variable	Metric	Baseline Value	Expected Results	Actual Results	KRs	Notes Comments
Business KPIs							
Scenario 1: Communication aware safe robot planning, Scenario 2: Trustworthy closed loop communication control	Accuracy of maintaining robust communication KPIs	Deviation of throughput and latency during robot's trajectory		< 10% deviation			Accuracy of throughput and latency, tracked along robot's trajectory
	Superior convergence times	Training times for AI models		Training times reduced by 10%			
	Improved decision-making accuracy	Inference accuracy		improved accuracy by 10%			Measures how well the robot reacts to environmental changes
Scenario 1: Communication aware safe robot planning	Safety criticality (avoiding obstacles)	Safe Path Deviation (SPD)		SPD < 5%			SPD measures how well the robot avoids collisions
	Reduced battery consumption of robot	Battery consumption reduction percentage		10% improvement from baseline			Battery efficiency depends on path planning and battery usage analysis

Scenario 2: Trustworthy closed loop communication control	Prediction Accuracy of QoS Deviation and Autonomous Actions	Prediction accuracy	> 90% prediction accuracy	Measures how accurately the system predicts
	AI Interpretability	Interpretability Ratio (percentage of times the AI's decision-making rationale is understood by human operators)	Interpretability Ratio > 95%	This measures the effectiveness of the AI system in providing understandable explanations or rationales for its decisions.
Preparation of trustworthy datasets				
Scenario 1: Communication aware safe robot planning, Scenario 2: Trustworthy closed loop communication control	Data Compatibility	Data format standardization	Standardized format for easy integration	All IoT data should be standardized for smooth integration
Scenario 1: Communication aware safe robot planning	Realistic Synthetic Data Generation	Similarity score	Current dataset realism	Ensure synthetic data covers diverse smart space environments
Scenario 2: Trustworthy closed loop communication control	Adaptability and Robustness of the Collected Dataset	Data Consistency		Ensures that despite changes, the dataset remains comprehensive and accurate.
Autonomous and continuous AIoT operations				
Scenario 1: Communication aware safe robot planning, Scenario 2: Trustworthy closed loop communication control	Communication throughput	Latency		Ensure 5G network's low-latency requirements are met
	Collision avoidance	Collision Detection Accuracy		Evaluate accuracy of the system during operations
Scenario 2: Trustworthy closed loop communication control	AI Interpretability in the operation phase	Interpretability Ratio (percentage of times the AI's decision-making rationale is understood by human operators)		This measures the effectiveness of the AI system in providing understandable explanations

6.2.3 PCL UC Validation Overview

The validation process of the PANDORA solution in the PCL use case is captured in the following validation table. This table will be systematically completed and function as a monitoring tool, accommodating comments and any identified risks as the experimentation progresses.

Table 24: PCL UC Validation Overview

Scenario	Validation variable	Metric	Baseline Value	Expected Results	Actual Results	KRs	Notes Comments
Business KPIs							
Scenario 1 Synthetic image data generation based on product images	Reconfiguration effort to adapt or create models		~ 1000 parts	< 50 parts			
	Credibility of synthetic images		n/a	> 90%			
	Continuous learning possibilities		not possible	possible			
Scenario 2 Synthetic image data generation based on CAD drawings/3D models	Preparation of trustworthy datasets						
	Autonomous and continuous AIoT operations						

6.2.4 FRA UC Validation Overview

The validation process of the PANDORA solution in the FRA use case is summarized in the following validation table. It serves as an ongoing monitoring tool, with fields for additional input, comments, and risk tracking during all stages of experimentation.

Table 25: FRA UC Validation Overview

Scenario	Validation variable	Metric	Baseline Value	Expected Results	Actual Results	KRs	Notes Comments
Business KPIs							
Scenario 1: Increased Operational safety	Detection of anomaly and system shutdown for increased safety	accuracy or F1 score of the anomaly detection	N/A: such tasks are not currently carried	>80%.			
	Identification of anomaly contributing factors with explainability	verification of factor with expert feedback	N/A	>80%.			
Scenario 2: Continuous system Improvement	Achieve an anomaly detection accuracy improvement		N/A	>10%.			

<p><i>production plan (production schedule)</i></p>	<p><i>High quality data availability</i></p>	<p><i>Trend and Seasonality Representation</i></p>	<p><i>missing data</i></p> <p><i>> 1 year granularity</i></p>	<p><i>combination of the two metrics is desirable. For scenario 2, <10% missing data is desirable.</i></p>	<p><i>The dataset should capture at least one full cycle of any repeating patterns (e.g., annual seasonality) to avoid bias toward a particular period</i></p>	
	<p><i>Data compatibility</i></p>	<p><i>Data format standardization</i></p>	<p><i>json or csv</i></p>	<p><i>Data to be in a standardized data format</i></p>		
	<p>Autonomous and continuous AIoT operations</p>					
	<p><i>Automatic data integration</i></p>	<p><i>Data Sync Frequency</i></p>	<p><i><60 seconds</i></p>	<p><i>Depends on the various data sources and their complexity.</i></p>		
		<p><i>Data Integration Latency</i></p>	<p><i><30 seconds</i></p>	<p><i>Depends on the various data sources and their complexity.</i></p>		
<p><i>Automated alert system</i></p>	<p><i>Alert Accuracy (Precision)</i></p>	<p><i>≥ 90% accuracy</i></p>	<p><i>Depends on the requirements from Halcor</i></p>	<p><i>Based on either a threshold of energy consumption or some malfunction sensor reading</i></p>	<p><i>KR3.1 , KR3.2</i></p> <p><i>Percentage of alerts that are correct (true positives vs. false positives).</i></p> <p><i>Percentage of actual issues that are detected and alerted (true positives vs. false negatives).</i></p>	
	<p><i>Alert Sensitivity (Recall)</i></p>	<p><i>≥ 95% recall</i></p>				

7. Overall KPI collection, classification and monitoring

This section provides an overview of the project’s Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), organized to enable a structured approach to monitoring, evaluating, and achieving project goals. The aim of this section is to centralize all critical KPIs in a single reference table. This table serves as a comprehensive summary of all PANDORA's KPIs, organized into categories such as Technical KPIs, Impact KPIs, and Business KPIs. The main purpose of this table is to provide a clear, structured overview of the project’s objectives and performance measures, allowing team members to track the various dimensions of the project. By systematically organizing KPIs, this table helps in evaluating the project’s achievements, identifying areas needing attention, and ensuring alignment with the overall project goals. This table is not only crucial for real-time monitoring but also serves as a dynamic document that can be updated continually as the project progresses.

Each column in the table corresponds to a specific attribute of the KPI, providing essential details to facilitate a deeper understanding of the KPI’s context and target. The Work Package column specifies the major segment of the project to which the KPI belongs, defining its scope within the project's larger structure. The No column designates the unique identifier assigned to each KPI, making it easy to reference and track individual indicators. The GA No column indicates the Grant Agreement number, which is a unique identifier as well. The KPI Definition column gives a description of each KPI, outlining the performance aspect it aims to measure or achieve. The Target column outlines the original benchmark or goal for each KPI, defining the success criteria, such as a specific percentage or quantity improvement. Evaluation Methodology describes the approach or procedure that will be followed to assess progress and achieve the KPI (e.g., "Simulation-based testing"), ensuring a clear path to success. The specific attribute will be systematically enriched throughout the project. The Task column includes the task number associated with each KPI, which specifies its direct operational activities. Then, each KPI is also mapped with an Enabler and Objective described in the GA. The Leader column identifies the organization or team responsible for overseeing each KPI, ensuring accountability and streamlined project management. Finally, the PANDORA Phase column states the specific phase of the PANDORA project in which the task or KPI is executed. Additionally, some cells may contain asterisks (*), which denote areas where complementary comments or definitions are provided for enhanced understanding.

Table 27: Overall KPI table

Work Package	No	GA No	KPI definition	Target	Evaluation methodology	Enabler	Objective	Task	Leader	PANDORA Phase
Technical KPIs										
WP2	1	KPI6.1.1	Number of project outcome reports on the role of different disciplines	≥3		EN6.1	6	T2.2	UNSPMF	—
	2	KPI3.2.1	Overall implementation of the PANDORA traceability matrix at the end of the project	95%		EN3.2	3	T2.4	IMT	1 & 2

	3	KPI3.2 .2	Number of releases for cross discipline internal validation	≥3 ^{*12}		EN3.2	3	T2.4	IMT, EAB	1 & 2
	4	KPI4.1 .1	Number of scenario variations defined per domain	≥2		EN4.1	4	T2.5	AEGIS	1 & 2
WP3	5	KPI2.2 .1	Increase models accuracy ^{*13}	20%		EN2.2	2	T3.1	IMT	1
	6	KPI2.2 .2	Reduction in model execution time	20%		EN2.2	2	T3.1	IMT	1
	7	KPI2.2 .3	Percentage of less operational data required for an experiment due to the quality of synthetic data	>15%		EN2.2	2	T3.1	IMT	1
	8	KPI1.2 .1	Increase accuracy of uncertainty prediction	15%		EN1.2	1	T3.2	DLR	1
	9	KPI1.2 .2	Deployment of at least one tool on uncertainty quantification for an energy efficiency problem	>1		EN1.2	1	T3.2	DLR	1
	10	KPI2.1 .1	Decrease periodic human inspections on models due to encapsulation of knowledge from the smart spaces ^{*14}	20%*		EN2.1	2	T3.3	UNIBO	1
	11	KPI2.1 .2	Number of models defined per smart space ^{*15}	≥2*		EN2.1	2	T3.3	UNIBO	1
	12	KPI1.3 .1	Increase labelling and annotation accuracy	20%		EN1.3	1	T3.4	UNSPMF	1
	13	KPI1.3 .2	Increase accuracy of models trained, based on the PANDORA	20%		EN1.3	1	T3.4	UNSPMF	1

¹² KPI3.2.2: Redefined target equal to 2 releases for cross discipline internal validation. It aligns better with the GA

¹³ KPI2.2.1: Increase models accuracy when trained using synthetic data by 20% until an upper bound of 99% accuracy

¹⁴ KPI2.1.1: Redefinition-Number of libraries to derive ≥ 2

¹⁵ KPI2.1.1: Redefinition: Number of explanation techniques defined ≥ 1

			labelling and annotation							
	14	KPI1.3.3	Reduce human interventions	50%		EN1.3	1	T3.4	UNSPMF	1
	15	KPI1.4.1	Decrease periodic human inspections on models	20%		EN1.4	1	T3.4	UNSPMF	1
	16	KPI1.5.1	Number of models trained	≥3		EN1.5	1	T3.5	ITML	1
	17	KPI1.5.2	Decrease in data redundancy ^{*16}	50%		EN1.5	1	T3.5	ITML	1
WP4	18	KPI3.1.1	Observed energy efficiency saved costs increase	15%		EN3.1	3	T4.1	UNSPMF	2
	19	KPI3.1.2	Accuracy of federated learning and inference methods for data lifecycle management, subject to computing continuum infrastructure characteristics	70%		EN3.1	3	T4.1	UNSPMF	2
	20	KPI3.1.3	Decrease in the response time for AI models inference	20%		EN3.1	3	T4.5	NTUA	2
	21	KPI2.4.1	Improved quality of the understandability related output that supports the tracing of the domain-informed AI decisions ^{*17}	20%*		EN2.4	2	T4.2	CYU	2
	22	KPI1.1.1	Increase models accuracy	20%		EN1.1	1	T4.3	SAG	2
	23	KPI1.1.2	Number of models trained	≥10		EN1.1	1	T4.3	SAG	2
	24	KPI2.3.1	Increased accuracy levels of real-time observations to capture out-of-distribution events	20%		EN2.3	2	T4.3	SAG	2

¹⁶ KPI1.5.2: Redefinition: Data reduction

¹⁷ KPI2.4.1: Number of improved Co-12 evaluation properties characterising the quality of the provided explanations of continuous and domain-informed AI decisions >= 2

	25	KPI2.3 .2	Number of models deployed across the cloud continuum	≥3		EN2.3	2	T4.3	SAG, NTUA	2
WP5	26	KPI2.3 .1	Increased accuracy levels of real-time observations to capture out-of-distribution events	20%		EN2.3	2	T5.1 , T4.3	ITML, SAG	1 & 2
	27	KPI2.3 .2	Number of models deployed across the cloud continuum	≥3		EN2.3	2	T5.1	ITML	1 & 2
	28	KPI3.1 .1	Observed energy efficiency saved costs increase	15%		EN3.1	3	T5.4	FRA, HALCOR	1 & 2
	29	KPI3.1 .2	Accuracy of federated learning and inference methods for data lifecycle management, subject to computing continuum infrastructure characteristics	70%		EN3.1	3	T5.4	EAB	1 & 2
	30	KPI3.1 .3	Increase in the response time for AI models inference	20%		EN3.1	3	T5.4	EAB	1 & 2
	31	KPI3.2 .1	Overall implementation of the PANDORA traceability matrix at the end of the project	95%		EN3.2	3	T5.4	EAB	1 & 2
	32	KPI3.2 .2	Number of releases for cross discipline internal validation	≥3 ^{*18}		EN3.2	3	T5.4	EAB	1 & 2
WP6	33	KPI4.1 .1	Number of scenario variations defined per domain	≥2		EN4.1	4	T6.1	ΦPA	1 & 2

¹⁸ Same as footnote no3

	34	KPI3.4 .1	Number of tutorials produced	≥5		EN3.4	3	T6.2	FRA	1 & 2
	35	KPI3.4 .2	Overall satisfaction and usability of tutorials	≥85%		EN3.4	3	T6.2	FRA	1 & 2
	36	KPI4.2 .1	Number of dependent and independent verification and validation variables defined	≥15		EN4.2	4	T6.2	FRA	1 & 2
	37	KPI4.2 .2	At least two different disciplines involved in the approach per domain	≥2		EN4.2	4	T6.2	FRA	1 & 2
	38	KPI6.2 .1	Number of tutorials produced	≥5		EN6.2	6	T6.2	FRA	—
	39	KPI6.2 .2	Number of European digital platforms approached	≥3		EN6.2	6	T6.2	FRA	—
	40	KPI6.2 .3	Number of PANDORA resulting open-source tools and services shared with European digital platforms	≥5		EN6.2	6	T6.2	FRA	—
	41	KPI3.3 .1	Improvement of model re-training time	10%		EN3.3	3	T6.3	NTUA	1 & 2
	42	KPI3.3 .2	Increase of model validation cycles	20%		EN3.3	3	T6.3	NTUA	1 & 2
	Impact KPIs									
WP7	43	KPI5.1 .1	Number of industrial sectors reached	>=5		EN5.1	5	T7.1 , T7.2 , T7.6	DIE, STS	—
	44	KPI5.2 .1	Presentations to research coordination and industry alliance groups in the area of AI, Data and Robotics	>=5		EN5.2	5	T7.3 , T7.4	IDC	—
	45	KPI5.2 .2	Number of workshops co-organised with projects in relevant European and/or national initiatives	>=3		EN5.2	5	T7.3 , T7.4	IDC	—
	46	KPI5.3 .1	Number of collaborations with organisations outside the	>=2		EN5.3	5	T7.5	NTUA	—

			European territory organisations outside the European territory							
	47	KPI5.3.2	Number of produced reports on the outcome of international collaborations	>=2		EN5.3	5	T7.5	NTUA	—
	48	KPI5.4.1	Demonstration to open events and exhibitions	>=3		EN5.4	5	WP 7	IDC	—
	49	KPI5.4.2	Number of custom demos available for different industrial sectors	>=5		EN5.4	5	WP 7	IDC	—
	50	KPI6.3.1	Number of participations in open innovation challenge activities	>=2		EN6.3	6	T7.1, T7.3, T7.4	IDC	—
	51	KPI6.4.1	Number of tangible outcomes adopted by the AI, Data and Robotics ecosystem	>=1		EN6.4	6	T7.3	IDC	—
	52	KPI6.4.2	Presentations to other networking and standards groups	>=1		EN6.4	6	T7.3	IDC	—
	43	KPI5.1.1	Number of industrial sectors reached	>=5		EN5.1	5	T7.1, T7.2, T7.6	DIE, STS	—
	44	KPI5.2.1	Presentations to research coordination and industry alliance groups in the area of AI, Data and Robotics	>=5		EN5.2	5	T7.3, T7.4	IDC	—
	45	KPI5.2.2	Number of workshops co-organised with projects in relevant European and/or national initiatives	>=3		EN5.2	5	T7.3, T7.4	IDC	—
Business KPIs										
WP5, WP6	53	KPI3.1.1	Observed energy efficiency saved costs increase	15%		EN3.1	3	T5.4	FRA, HALCOR	1 & 2
	54	KPI4.1.1	Number of scenario variations	≥2		EN4.1	4	T6.1	FRA	1 & 2

		defined per domain								
55	KPI4.3.1	Number of experiments conducted with experts per domain	≥2		EN4.3	4	T6.4	PCL	1 & 2	
56	KPI4.3.2	Gender analysis conducted towards balanced gender participation in the experiments	-		EN4.3	4	T6.4	PCL	1 & 2	
57	KPI4.4.1	Overall perception of the PANDORA framework	≥80%		EN4.4	4	T6.5	NTUA	1 & 2	
58	KPI4.4.2	Overall usability and friendliness of the framework	≥85%		EN4.4	4	T6.5	NTUA	1 & 2	
59	KPI4.4.3	Overall acceptance and trust on the adoption of the PANDORA offering	≥75%		EN4.4	4	T6.5	NTUA	1 & 2	
60	—	Realistic training data creation modelling infrastructure failure events and allowing AI trained models to predict infrastructure failures with an accuracy of 90%.	90%		—	—	—	SAG	—	
61	—	Accuracy of maintaining robust communication KPIs: Ensure that the intents on throughput and latency are maintained through the trajectory of the robot,	10% DEVIATION		—	—	—	EAB	—	
62	—	Safety criticality (avoiding obstacles): Ensure that the safety conditions are maintained through the course of the operation	Safe Path Deviation (SPD) < 5%		—	—	—	EAB	—	
63	—	Reduced battery consumption of robot: Plan the	10% improvement from		—	—	—	EAB	—	

		shortest path that ensures completion of goal with minimal battery usage,	baseline						
64	—	Superior convergence times,	training times reduced by 10%		—	—	—	EAB	—
65	—	Make decisions with high inference accuracy and react quickly to changes in its environment	improved accuracy by 10%		—	—	—	EAB	—
66	—	Human operator can understand the AI's rationale	Interpretability ratio>95%		—	—	—	EAB	—
67	—	Prediction of deviation in QoS and autonomous actions	>90%		—	—	—	EAB	—
68	—	Reconfiguration effort to adapt or create models for new vision tasks.	less than 50 real data samples to generate synthetic data.		—	—	—	PCL	—
69	—	Credibility of synthetic images used for training the AI system.	less than a 10% deviation from a benchmark test conducted on real dataset images.		—	—	—	PCL	—
70	—	Integration effort for the base model to existing production system and continuous update of the model based on real production images.			—	—	—	PCL	—
71	—	Reconfiguration effort to adapt or create			—	—	—	PCL	—

		models for new vision tasks. Target is to use only CAD information and/or print design.							
72	—	Detection of anomaly event prediction with supervised or unsupervised learning to avoid sudden system/component shutdown due to component failure, with across conditions such as component shutdown, extreme high pressure or temperature out of range.	Achieve an anomaly detection accuracy of 80%, accounting for diverse conditions and anomaly types.		—	—	—	FRA	—
73	—	Explainability of Anomaly Contributing Factors, by identifying them and explaining the anomalies with clear insight.			—	—	—	FRA	—
74	—	Ensure 80% of detected anomalies include explanations that are understandable and actionable, verified by HRS experts.	80%		—	—	—	FRA	—
75	—	Model accuracy improvement .	anomaly detection accuracy improvement by 10%		—	—	—	FRA	—
76	—	Reduction of false positive anomaly detection	10% per retraining cycle.		—	—	—	FRA	—
77	—	Continuous system performance improvement with each iteration of model retraining and validation.	10% improvement		—	—	—	FRA	—

78	—	Energy Cost Savings	≥2%		—	—	—	HALCOR	—
79	—	Model Accuracy Improvement	≥10%		—	—	—	HALCOR	—
80	—	Operational Efficiency Gain	≥2%		—	—	—	HALCOR	—
53	KPI3.1 .1	Observed energy efficiency saved costs increase	15%		EN3.1	3	T5.4	FRA, HALCOR	1 & 2
54	KPI4.1 .1	Number of scenario variations defined per domain	≥2		EN4.1	4	T6.1	FRA	1 & 2
55	KPI4.3 .1	Number of experiments conducted with experts per domain	≥2		EN4.3	4	T6.4	PCL	1 & 2
56	KPI4.3 .2	Gender analysis conducted towards balanced gender participation in the experiments	-		EN4.3	4	T6.4	PCL	1 & 2
57	KPI4.4 .1	Overall perception of the PANDORA framework	≥80%		EN4.4	4	T6.5	NTUA	1 & 2
58	KPI4.4 .2	Overall usability and friendliness of the framework	≥85%		EN4.4	4	T6.5	NTUA	1 & 2

8. Conclusions

Deliverable D2.3 is the outcome of the work conducted in Task 2.5 and establishes the foundation for activities in technical work packages WP3 and WP4, as well as the integration and demonstration work packages WP5 and WP6. It outlines the PANDORA experimental protocols, providing an overview of existing systems and data across pilot cases, identifying gaps, collecting detailed user requirements, and aligning each use case with PANDORA's strategic objectives. The experimentation process defined here is iterative, involving two definition phases—scoping and planning—and two operational phases—execution and analysis.

A Verification & Validation (V&V) methodology is also provided, structured to meet both technical and business requirements. This methodology supports a comprehensive evaluation of PANDORA technologies by setting an initial range of verification and validation variables, prepared to adapt and expand as technologies are developed and implemented across use cases. This approach ensures alignment with high-level user and project objectives, supporting the systematic evaluation that will be carried out in Task 6.3.

Additionally, D2.3 compiles all PANDORA KPIs into a structured framework, including those defined in the Grant Agreement (GA) as well as new KPIs identified during the use case design phase. This framework facilitates efficient tracking and monitoring of project progress, allowing for effective assessment of achievements against targets and adjustments to meet overarching project objectives.

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Annex

Table 28: Verification Template-Hidden columns

Responsible Partner	Related Tasks	Enabler	KR id	KR definition
IMT	T3.1	EN2.2: Models, mechanisms, and tools for data preparation and enrichment through the generation of synthetic data	KR2.1	Definition of ML-based semantic models for smart spaces via event-driven generation of synthetic datasets
DLR	T3.2	EN1.2: Models, mechanisms, and tools for uncertainty modelling and quantification	KR1.2	Enhanced analysis, interpretation and understandability of data insights and optimised development and training of efficient and compact AI models for domain-driven IoT data management and use
UNIBO	T3.3	EN2.1: Models, mechanisms, and techniques for semantic and causal data model formulation of smart spaces EN2.4: A tool-based explainable AI and interpretation modelling framework for domain knowledge	KR2.1 KR2.2	Definition of ML-based semantic models for smart spaces via event-driven generation of synthetic datasets Analysis of existing domain knowledge, and experimental datasets, simulation models and tools
UNSPMF	T3.4	EN1.3: Models, mechanisms, and tools for (semi-) automated annotations and labelling EN1.3: Models, mechanisms, and tools for (semi-) automated annotations and labelling EN1.4: Models, mechanisms, and tools for self-supervision data completion and augmentation	KR1.3 KR1.2	Novel data preparation, completion, and dimensionality reduction for optimised data provision and consumption processes towards more efficient, accurate and robust AI models Enhanced analysis, interpretation and understandability of data insights and optimised development and training of efficient and compact AI models for domain-driven IoT data management and use
ITML	T3.5	EN1.5: Models, mechanisms, and tools for data summarisation and dimensionality reduction	KR1.3	Novel data preparation, completion, and dimensionality reduction for optimised data provision and consumption processes towards more efficient, accurate and robust AI models
NTUA	T6.3	EN3.3: Mechanisms and tools for model formal verification, self-validation (T6.3) and adaptation of the model structure to changing characteristics	KR3.3	Integration of both human-centric and enhanced model/data driven verification and validation for the optimisation and trustworthiness of AIoT operation
UNSPMF	T4.1	EN3.1: Scalable, and customisable AI-based methods, models and tools for deployment and autonomous operation of trustworthy and energy-efficient AIoT systems	KR3.1 KR3.2	Advances in the automation of data handling approaches for the continual, energy-efficient, privacy preserving and robust AIoT operation deployed in the computing continuum Encapsulating computing continuum infrastructure characteristics in optimising the lifecycle management of “data in AI” pipelines, ensuring efficient and trustworthy AI processes in the selection, deployment, inference and re-training of relevant data products

SAG	T4.3	EN1.1: Models, mechanisms, and tools for reliable and optimised data analysis upscale and speed up through federated representational and robust learning	KR1.1	Research advances in distributed, and federated learning approaches for fostering the adoption of trustworthy AI technologies towards delivering robust, efficient, and verifiable AI models that increase intelligence in “data for AI” pipelines across the computing continuum and scale up autonomy in AIoT operations for smart spaces
		EN2.3: Mechanisms, models, and solutions for capturing the necessary information and communicating it through compact data representations	KR2.3	Development of efficient, resilient, robust mechanisms and ML-based tools for the extraction and use of data knowledge, towards creating intelligence data pipelines in reproducing customisable and trustworthy datasets for model training and testing in AIoT deployments
CYU	T4.2	EN2.4: A tool-based explainable AI and interpretation modelling framework for domain knowledge	KR2.2	Analysis of existing domain knowledge, and experimental datasets, simulation models and tools
AU	T4.4	EN3.1: Scalable, and customisable AI-based methods, models and tools for deployment and autonomous operation of trustworthy and energy-efficient AIoT systems	KR3.1	Advances in the automation of data handling approaches for the continual, energy-efficient, privacy preserving and robust AIoT operation deployed in the computing continuum
NTUA	T4.5	EN2.4: A tool-based explainable AI and interpretation modelling framework for domain knowledge	KR2.2	Analysis of existing domain knowledge, and experimental datasets, simulation models and tools
CBRL	T5.4	EN3.2: Development of the PANDORA Framework (T2.4, T5.4) for the preparation and delivery of trustworthy datasets and the continuous and autonomous AIoT operation	KR3.1	Advances in the automation of data handling approaches for the continual, energy-efficient, privacy preserving and robust AIoT operation deployed in the computing continuum
EAB	T5.4	EN3.1: Scalable, and customisable AI-based methods, models and tools for deployment and autonomous operation of trustworthy and energy-efficient AIoT systems	KR3.1	Advances in the automation of data handling approaches for the continual, energy-efficient, privacy preserving and robust AIoT operation deployed in the computing continuum
EAB	T5.4	EN3.1: Scalable, and customisable AI-based methods, models and tools for deployment and autonomous operation of trustworthy and energy-efficient AIoT systems	KR3.1	Advances in the automation of data handling approaches for the continual, energy-efficient, privacy preserving and robust AIoT operation deployed in the computing continuum
EAB	T5.4	EN3.1: Scalable, and customisable AI-based methods, models and tools for deployment and autonomous operation of trustworthy and energy-efficient AIoT systems	KR3.1	Advances in the automation of data handling approaches for the continual, energy-efficient, privacy preserving and robust AIoT operation deployed in the computing continuum

